

**Influence of social media marketing on UK
consumers of pharmaceutical products**

By

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requirement for the degree of Doctor Business Administration
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DECLARATION

I declare that this study is the report of my research and all additional sources of information has been referenced. I have declared my published works, and the internet sources from which the quotes in the study are drawn have been fully referenced.

Signature Shubhra Nigam

Date 24/01/2021

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ABSTRACT

Social media is influencing various aspects of human as well as the interaction between businesses and customers. As a result, social media marketing has become popular. However, there is limited knowledge on how social media marketing is influencing the consumers of pharmaceutical products in European countries with health services comprehensively funded by the state. This study aims to investigate the influence of social media on UK consumers in the pharmaceutical industry. The objective is to study whether it is influencing them to buy pharmaceutical products such as over the counter or non-prescription drugs/medicines from the online pharmacy based on the information obtained from the social media and other websites. Thus the main aim and objectives of this research study is to investigate how the social media is changing the pharmaceutical industry and influencing its consumers and why the pharmaceutical consumers have accepted social media marketing networks for health related information and how it is influencing the pharmaceutical consumers to purchase over the counter drugs and non-prescription drugs from the online pharmacy. The study evaluates the key factors which influence how social media marketing contributes to the purchase of online and non-prescription drugs.

The study used quantitative and qualitative methods for collecting and analysing the data. Accordingly, 200 consumers of pharmaceutical products were used for the quantitative study and the data collected was analysed using SPSS to generate Spearman's correlation, Chi square test and Ordinal Regression. For the qualitative research 15 healthcare professionals such as pharmacist and doctors were selected from across the England for the in-dept interview using semi-structured questionnaire. Thematic analysis was used to evaluate the responses.

The study revealed that convenience was the main reason for purchasing the health-related products such as non-prescription drugs from the online pharmacy. Social media also provided knowledge on health-related issues. The study also brought out the facts that although consumers used social media and other websites for getting health related information not all websites gave reliable health related information. As a result, it was suggested that the consumers should always consult a healthcare professional in case they were not happy with the information shared on social media.

The main findings suggested that based on the information obtained from the social media and website, consumers buy over the counter drugs, non-prescription medicine from online

pharmacy, however, buying non-prescription medicines such as pain killers cough and cold and vitamins and protein supplements through the online pharmacy is considered to be safe. . Buying prescription drugs from online sources should be avoided. In addition, the study revealed that consumers between the ages of 30 and 40 purchased over the counter medicines from online pharmacy more and that there were more female users than men. It is recommended that in order to ensure that consumers use appropriate websites, GP surgeries should provide patients with the list of the authorised online pharmacies and health related websites. Although Contribution to the study is how to make online over the counter buying experience safer along with convenience.

Key words: Social media, online media, website, communication, online pharmacy, pharmaceutical, consumer, customer, digital marketing.

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1 CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

According to Jahdi and Acikdilli (2009), marketing has been in existence since ages, so it's not a new concept, but with the evolution of information technology in the form of social media where everything is becoming online, even the way marketing was done is in the process of changing. Thus, with the involvement of information technology in the field of marketing, now, marketing is divided into "traditional marketing", "digital marketing", and "social media marketing", or "online marketing". Moreover prior to the internet marketing or the online the promotion or the advertisement of the product was done using channels such television and print media, interactive media, trade promotions, press releases, sponsorship and event marketing, this type of product promotion or advertising was in traditional marketing, however, with the advent of digital technology and various channels of digital media marketing, the product promotion and advertising which was done during the traditional marketing phase have become outdated and obsolete and is not very much appreciated by the target audience (Zavrsnik, 2013). In the era of digital technology the product promotion is done either by various channels of digital media such as "social media", "blogs", "microblogs", "company website" etc. Further, as per Ab Hamid, Akhir and Cheng (2013) information technology plays a very important role in social media marketing and are also of the opinion that digital marketing in the form of "social media", "blogs", "micro blogs", etc seems to alter the decision of consumers in the purchase of goods and services.

In the era of computer mediated media, social media is used as a tool for the brand retention by the organisation which is frequently accessed by the audience, thus makes social media an important platform for organisation and business houses to create brand awareness thereby helping in customer retention (Odhiambo, 2012). Thus, Downey (2012) social media has come out has a tool or a medium for easy connection to a larger audience through its wider application and reach, thus fostering the interests of the community. So, it can be said that, social media has wider application now, besides just being limited to entertainment, by finding its application in the business and organisations (Kapoor, 2018).

Thus, the researcher, through this research wants to identify and study how with advent of computer mediated media the changing face of marketing will impact the pharmaceutical consumer. That is, the researcher wants to study how social media is changing the face of

marketing in pharmaceutical industry and its impact on the consumer. This chapter presents the aim, objectives and also the expected outcome of the study. Last but not the least, this chapter also presents a brief review of the structure of the thesis along with contents of the chapters.

1.2 Background to the research

Communication is very important for social interaction in the life of the human beings and can be defined as an “exchange of ideas, information and feelings” (Hun and Yazdarnifard, 2014, p. 21). Moreover, there has been a drastic change in the way communication was done which is noticeable in last few decades, and this can be attributed to the technological advancement. For the communication to be effective it should be considered in two parts that is the first part is about understanding the message and second part should deal with reaction to the first part of the message (Melewar *et al.*, 2017). Further, Mihart (2012) is of the opinion that the objective of marketing communication is to see how customer understands or perceives the marketing communication under different circumstances, also represent the voice of a brand which can be used to establish relation between the company and its consumers by reminding them of companies offerings (Hun and Yazdarnifard, 2014; Keller, 2001). However, of late it has been observed, marketing is changing drastically from traditional marketing to online or marketing through the social media, in short it is be said that marketing is becoming computer mediated. Thus, as the computer mediated marketing in form of online marketing and social media marketing is gaining popularity and has gained momentum becoming one of the emerging types of marketing communication channel in almost all the industry, thus, making it a hot topic for research (Fortin and Uncles, 2011). Furthermore, despite being slow in the adopting social media marketing, pharmaceutical industry has eventually adopted social media marketing and digital marketing in later part of last decade (Yazdanifard *et al.*, 2011; Green and Kesselheim, 2010). Moreover, as per Masood *et al.* (2009), new methods to communicate such as blogs, social networks, etc are being acquired to being used independently and also as a support to traditional marketing by the pharmaceutical marketing. Thus, representing a new way for pharmaceutical companies to interact and communicate with consumers, customers and the physicians (Webb, 2010). As, the pharmaceutical industry is adopting the social media and digital media marketing, the old model where patients blithely accepted their doctors’ judgment is quickly dying. Accordingly, as per Enyinda *et al.* (2018) it is been estimated that every month nearly 19 million people search information related to health on various website and quarter of them suffer from chronic health issues and diseases prefer to visit the peer sites

to meet and discuss the various health issues with fellow sufferers. He has also reported that nowadays patients with lots of information about their disease and related symptoms were showing up doctors' room (Anscombe et al., 2015). Thus, it can be said that, it not just the patients but the medical community is digitalizing (Heilman and West, 2015) as approximately 50 percent of doctors in U.S. and UK search Wikipedia for medical information as Wikipedia is considered to be the world's most popular source for health related information (Heilman *et al.*, 2011). Healthcare system has started to recognize these trends, in the year 2013 itself and globally the digital health funding increased by 39 percent, which is equivalent to \$2 billion. Further, in the United Kingdom itself NHS has not only recommended but also publishes a list of healthcare apps, helping the doctors prescribe these apps for the patients to help manage health conditions such as diabetes or stress (Bellostas *et al.*, 2015). Thus, it is seen that digital media marketing in form social media has now occupied a place in pharmaceutical industry. Through this research the researcher is trying to study how the social media in the pharmaceutical industry is influencing the UK consumers.

1.3 Research problem statement

In the last few years innovation has become an important part in the business and organisations Greenhalgh *et al.* (2008). Further, as per Morone and Taylor (2010) wealth of information is also available on research and innovation in the pharmaceutical industry, but there is lack of literature and information on application of social media marketing in the pharmaceutical industry and pharmaceutical consumers (Shadlen and Guennif, 2011). Moreover, as a health related information, social media, social media marketing, internet pharmacies or the online pharmacies offering prescription drugs without a prescription are available on the internet and social media, it can be very risky such as “injury”, “overdose”, and “development of abuse” and dependence. As a result, this has attracted the attention of researchers to investigate the different factors and consumer's intention to use Internet and social media marketing as a place to purchase non-prescription medicine based on the information obtained from the internet. However there very few studies which have been carried out just to study the online marketing of over the counter and non-prescription medicine, as a result research on consumer buying behaviour towards online pharmacies is scarce (Buttner *et al.*, 2006). In this regard, this research will be based on the consumer buying behaviour of over the counter drugs and non-prescription medicines from online or internet pharmacies and impact or the influence of social media marketing in the pharmaceutical or the medicine making industry and pharmaceutical products to the consumer. This research will be based on the social media and pharmaceutical

industry and finally how will it impact the consumers' behaviour in purchasing the medicines from online pharmacies. This will be done using semi-structured and structured questionnaire which will be further analysed and discussed.

1.4 Research aim and objectives

The aim of the research is to study the “Influence of Social Media Marketing on UK Consumers of Pharmaceutical Products.”

The objective of this research was to study the changing face of marketing and how this will influence the consumer in pharma industry.

1. To identify how social media is changing the face of marketing in the pharmaceutical industry.
2. To determine the impact of social media in the pharmaceutical industry.
3. To identify how social media will influence pharmaceutical consumer.
4. To identify the age and gender of the consumer searching information related to pharmaceutical products from social media and factors leading them to medicines from online pharmacy based on the information obtained from social media.

1.5 Research question

What will be the impact of the social media on the consumers in Pharmaceutical industry?

The main research question will be further divided into sub questions as under:

1. How social media is changing the face of marketing especially in the pharmaceutical industry?
2. How is social media marketing impacting the pharmaceutical industry?
3. How social media will influence consumer in pharmaceutical Industry? What are the various factors that influence the consumers of pharmaceutical industry?
4. What are age and gender of the consumer searching information related to pharmaceutical products from social media/internet and factors, leading them to buy medicines from online pharmacy based on the information obtained from social media

1.6 Significance of the Study

The pharmaceutical field has always experimented and adopted technology to provide medical advancements, but has been much slower to adopt social media in its marketing efforts, and

was mostly relying on traditional channels (Niemi,2015). However, over last few years' pharmaceutical industry has also adopted social media marketing, thus the researcher through this research wants to study the impact social media, and social media marketing will have on the pharmaceutical consumers, as it is not much studied. It has been seen that there are studies on digital marketing and social media marketing in various industries and how it is influencing consumers of all age and gender, but there are very few researches relating to social media marketing in pharmaceutical industry (Syrkiewicz-Switlala *et al.*, 2016). Thus, this study will be based on UK consumer prospective on social media marketing in pharmaceutical industry.

1.7 Scope of the study

Pharmaceutical industry is vast and has different departments, however this research deals with the recent trends and advancements of social media marketing in the pharmaceutical industry and its influence on the UK consumer. It will also include the various challenges that are associated in and around the social media and social media marketing in Pharmaceutical Industry. Thus, this study will be based on the consumer prospective, of social media marketing in pharmaceutical industry in UK. The town selected will be Wolverhampton.

1.8 Brief discussion of the methodology

Mixed method was used for the study, sampling method used was probability sampling, and the participant chosen were any either male or female above the age of 18. Using a structured questionnaire data was collected and Likert scale was used as a scaling method for quantitative study. The data collected was analysed using SPSS the test used were Spearman's correlation, Chi square test, Ordinal regression. Respondents were provided with the consent form. Data collection was voluntary, there was no compulsion, and it is on the discretion of the respondents. Once the respondents had agreed to participate in the study through the questionnaire then the data was collected.

In case of Qualitative research sampling method used was non-probability sampling, respondent selected were healthcare professionals. Data was collected by using Semi structured questionnaire, which was further analysed using thematic analysis. Respondents were provided with the consent form, data collection was voluntary, there was no compulsion, and it was on the discretion of the respondents. Once the respondents agreed to participate in the study through the interview, then the data was collected by recording the interview.

1.9 Structure of the thesis

The structure of the thesis is in a logical sequence, starting with the chapter one dealing with the introduction of the research and chapter seven dealing with the conclusion (figure 1.1). accordingly, each chapter will deal with different aspect of the study. Accordingly, chapter 1 will consist of aim and objectives and the background study of the research, chapter 2 will contain reviews of different literature related to the topic of study which will be critically analysed. Further, chapter 3 is all about research context, chapter Four is based on research methodology that is “research method”, and “research approach”, adopted in the study, it also give information related to data collection methods, that is use of semi-structured questionnaire which was used to interviews professionals from healthcare backgrounds such as Doctors and pharmacist who provided qualitative data for the study, besides structured questionnaire was used to collect data from the general public to provide quantitative data, and analysis of the data. Chapter five is findings and analysis; chapter six is on discussion followed with chapter seven which contains conclusion recommendation and limitation, and finally end with the references and appendix.

Chapter one: Chapter one is based on the introduction which gives an understanding to the reader about the research. This chapter consists of aim, objectives and research questions background study, rationale and significance of the research.

Chapter Two: Chapter Two focuses on literature review dealing with definitions of communication, marketing, digital media, social media, besides this it also deals with social media marketing in the pharmaceutical industry, advantages and disadvantages of pharmaceutical industry in social media. Besides this, the chapter also consists of the concepts and issues related to theory of consumer behaviour, consumer etc.

Chapter three: Chapter three focuses on research context pharmaceutical industry in general and in the context of the UK. This chapter will also throw some light on the UK Pharmaceutical market, its growth, UK market analysis. Further it will also be dealing with UK pharmaceutical Market volume forecast for next 2 years that till the year 2021 and also how the pharmaceutical industry is impacting the UK economy.

Chapter four: Chapter four is all about the research methodology, and also details the selection and justification of research approaches and the sample frames adopted for the pilot and main

study. The challenges encountered and the various research instruments used in mitigating such challenges also receive attention.

Chapter five: Chapter five focuses on the findings and analysis qualitative and quantitative studies with the help of graphs and descriptive statistics and the findings of the interviews using thematic analysis.

Chapter six: Chapter six deals with the overall discussion and answering the research question. This chapter is deals with discussing the findings of qualitative and quantitative studies. That is the research findings are discussed and presented based on quantitative survey questionnaire and face-to-face interviews.

Chapter seven: Chapter seven is all about conclusion along with the contribution, limitations and recommendations for future research.

1.10 Keywords

Digital marketing; online marketing; online pharmacy, internet marketing; non-prescription medicine, over the counter drugs, search engine; user generated content; omni-channel marketing; pharmaceutical industry.

1.11 Structure of the thesis

Figure 1.1 Structure of the thesis (developed by the researcher)

1.12 Chapter summary

This chapter is a summary for the entire research, starting with a brief review of social media and social media marketing in Pharmaceutical Industry. This chapter also discussed the aim, objectives and the questions of the research, along with the significance of study, methodology, brief information about the research context and assumptions and also at the end the brief summary of the thesis.

2 CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This section is based on literature review and will be focusing mainly on marketing and social media, consumer behaviour, digital media marketing in form of online marketing or social media marketing in the pharmaceutical industry, and marketing communications. Moreover, the purpose of this section is to study the various literature with an objective to explore different opinion related to the topic of research.

2.2 Background study

According to Mihart (2012) communication plays a very important for the human activities' and social interaction, although in the last few decades there has been a dramatic change in marketing communication due technological advancement. As a result, social network sites (SNSs) and social media marketing has attracted the attention of academics and industry researchers for their reach (Boyd and Ellison, 2010). Thus, this research will mainly focus on understanding the influence of social media marketing on the UK Pharmaceutical consumer.

In the present scenario it has been noted that computer mediated communication in the form of social media and marketing on the internet through various channels of social media is playing a very a vital role. Moreover, more and more people have increasingly been using social media and various digital media through the use of information technology. The main reason for exposing themselves to this social media and digital media is their roles as consumers to search for information about products, for purchasing and consuming them, and then communicating with others about their experiences. Marketers are responding to this fundamental shift of whereby people are using various channels on the social media and other digital and online marketing channels. According to Pew Research Centre (2015) almost 87% adults American were internet users, and this is closer to 100% of the demographic group which include people such as college-educated and higher-income adults and spend lot more of their time online. Further, in the same year that is 2015 Ofcom also reported that weekly, an UK adults were spending on an average 20.5 hours on the internet (Ofcom. 2015). Similarly, even Appel et al., (2019) reported that worldwide billions of people use social media and it is considered to be the fastest growing technology, examples of social media are Facebook, My Space etc. Further, as of March 31, 2019 Facebook (2019) reported that on an average its active users every month are 2.38 billion and daily active users 1.56 billion. Moreover, it is estimated

that by 2022 the active users of Facebook will grow to 3.29 billion, which is almost 50% world's population (eMarketer 2018). Thus, it can be said that in future the consumer marketing will be mostly carried out on digital setup or a digital platform, that too on social media and mobile. Seeing such a massive potential for target audience across the various platforms of social media, it is not surprising that marketers and business are embracing social media as a marketing channel.

Further, it is not just in business organisation but academically also, social media and related topic such as social media marketing, online word of mouth and online networks have become a topic of research (Appel *et al.*, 2020; Huete-Alcocer, 2017). Thus, it can be seen that traditional medium of marketing is getting more and more digitalised, the major reason being convenience, connectivity, interactivity etc making it easily accessible to everyone (Syrkiewicz and Switala, 2012). Besides the people and the companies, even the medical practitioners have also started using social media to get information related to drugs. Thus, the internet has become a global platform by the use of various social media channels and other communication channel. This impact is also seen in highly regulated pharmaceutical industry to sell and promote their products and services on social media, thereby adopting e-pharma marketing, although it's not yet been accepted as a image building tool for the company and its products (Syrkiewicz-*et al.*, 2016). Further, E-pharma marketing is basically an activity of promote and sell its products and services to the potential customers and thus build a relationship with them via the internet or over the social media (Armstrong and Kotler, 2012).

Further, it was reported by Limaye and Saraogi, (2018), that worldwide of the 80% of the total internet users look for health related information, out of which 90% of tech-savvy, in the age group 18-to-24 year use more than the senior citizen or the elderly population (von Muhlen and Ohno-Machado, 2012; Childs and Martin, 2012). It has also been noted that people of all age group and from all profession and background including pharmacist participants actively on social media for health related information (Bernhardt *et al.*, 2014; Ventola, 2014).

Diverse topics related to healthcare such as how to cope up with a long term disease and chronic condition, diet exercise fitness etc are being discussed and shared. It was also noted that in order to develop a professional network and to motivate patients, health care professionals HCPs use social media for health related information (Rolls *et al.*, 2016). Although initially, healthcare professionals were not very quick or rather slow in accepting or

adopting the social media for the health related purpose, but over a period they have adopted it, which is very evident by having 90 pages related to the pharmacy on Facebook (Costa *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, WebMD (56%) and Wikipedia (31%) are the most accessed online health-related information resources (Benetoli *et al.*, 2017), proving that 60% patients claim that they trusted the information on social media, so it's important that the doctors should be very actively sharing updates on the various health related and disease related topics. Thus, making social media a source of accurate and trustworthy information with the patient community (Grajales III *et al.*, 2014) as, it is not only watched by the patients, but also 60% of health care professionals (HCPs) watch what is happening on health-related issues on the social media (Limaye and Saraogi, 2018). Thus, as per Huh and Shin (2015) social media and internet has become a primarily a major source of information for consumer for health related information, and is one of the most popular online activities, in spite of it is having a lots of drawbacks related to privacy and security issues (Fox and Duggan, 2013). Thus, Mackey and Liang, (2013) is also of the opinion that as more and more consumers are going online to get information related to health so also the pharmaceutical companies are increasing their advertisement of prescription drugs through direct-to-consumer (DTC) over the internet and on different social media channels which refers the users or consumers to the prescription drug and medicine brands' websites as an alternative sources of information (DeLorme *et al.*, 2011).

2.3 Marketing

The term marketing has been defined differently by different authors accordingly, marketing as per American Marketing Association, (2008, p. 1) is *“the activity, set of institutions, and processes for creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings that have value for customers, clients, partners, and society at large”*. Thus, marketing can be called as an activity which consists of exchange of product or services, it can also be called as a process of creating, communicating, delivering a product with the purpose of earning profits. Moreover, marketing as per the Charter Institute of Marketing UK is a management function or a process which aims towards identifying, anticipating, and satisfying customer requirements with an objective of making a profit.

Similarly, Kotler & Keller (2008, p. 5) defines marketing as a *“meeting needs profitably”*, which means marketing has a sole objective of earning profits by satisfying the needs of consumers. However, as per Gronroos (2004), marketing is a process of developing the business, further Keegan (2010); Layton (2007) says marketing as a concept to meet

organisational goals by effectively communicating the message with an objectives to create an impact on customer. Thus, based on different definitions marketing is a profit-making process by meeting the needs and wants of the customers.

2.4 Digital marketing

According to Kannan (2017) the term “digital marketing” has evolved over a period from terms which use digital channels for marketing of products and services. As per Abou Nabout *et al.* (2012), digital marketing is a technology driven process enabling companies to collaborate with customers and partners in order to communicate, deliver, and sustain value. Moreover, digital or online marketing is considered to an umbrella term used for marketing of products or services using different channels of digital media with the use of Internet. Thus, Michael (2010), is of the opinion that digital marketing can also be referred to as “online marketing”, “internet marketing” or “web marketing” in different countries. As a result, Michael, (2010) says that in most of the countries, digital marketing has become very popular and is estimated to be growing at the rate of 4.5 trillion online advertisements very year. Thus, it can be noted that different authors have defined and explained the term digital marketing in a different way. As per Kannan (2017), it is basically the application of different digital media with an objective to advertise and sell the product.

2.4.1 Marketing communications in the era of digital technologies:

According to Winner (2008) in the initial years 21st century, the marketers had various platforms and media such as internet or online web pages to communicate with the customers, thereby increasing the number of ways in which the marketers could promote their products and services. As a results the consumers could connect directly with companies and marketers through various channels without any mediator or middle person. Thus, it can be said that digital technology in form of various channels such as internet marketing or social media marketing has changed the way in which the products are promoted and businesses work, as Owens (2009) opines that with the online marketing there is higher interaction between consumers and the marketers which was not possible in the traditional marketing. Seeing this popularity and features of internet marketing the business has started accepting it and thereby digital marketing in form of online communication is gaining more importance and also impacting the consumer buying behaviour (Ford and Freeman, 2009). Further, there are lots of advantages and benefits of digital marketing has over the traditional marketing, there benefits

are “around the clock Online”, “multimedia”, “worldwide web”, “interactive”, “One-To-One and micromarketing integration” thus making it a vital tool for the businesses (Hoffman, 1995 in Timmer,2000). Thus, as per Kitchen and Burgmann (2010) it can be seen that digital marketing is changing the way marketing is being carried out worldwide and with the internet and online marketing channels the marketing process has changed completely. Further, different channels of digital media have become wonderful and a common platform to market the product and service. Thus, it can be noted that Wind (2002), with the mechanisms of virtual shopping digital technology has not only changed the way in which marketing is done but also behaviour of the online consumer is growing fast virtual marketplace. Besides, because of tremendous growth potential of the digital marketing academic and researchers are getting interested which can be seen by the numbers of journal articles and academic papers published in just one year (Cheung *et al.*, 2003). Thus, this can be proved by the research carried out by the Taylor Nelson that 20% of internet users purchase products and services from the internet shops, similarly even in US 50 % people internet users normally purchased products from online shops (Forrester Research, 2003), indicating that digital marketing channels is changing the face marketing. Further seeing the popularity of digital media marketing, it can also be said that e-commerce will gradually become the main business activity. Thus, seeing the online consumers maturing the virtual vendors have to realize the importance and urgency for a professional approach towards the online consumers (Finne and Gronroos, 2009).

Internet marketing and social media marketing is changing the way in which business is done, moreover, it enhances the organisational communication because of its the interactivity and connectivity with their customers and business partners, thus it can be said that it is one of the important strategic marketing tools (Hamid, 2007). Thus, it can be said technology and innovation in form of information technology, internet marketing is drastically changing the manner in which the marketing was done (Kitchen and Burgmann, 2010). Therefore, as per Hoffman and Fodor, (2010) keeping connectivity along with interactivity in mind, social media marketing can be used to create direct contact not only with the consumers and the customers but also with the business partners. Thus, it can be said that social media has become one of the key ingredients or channels to the successful digital marketing. Also, in the opinion of Hoffman (2012) there are different social media applications that continue to proliferate the dynamics of online social interaction, as a result communication and marketing researchers are trying to understand different motivating factors of why and how people use social media. It is also said that social media introduces a potential re-connect with friends and

family over large distances. Moreover, Hoffman and Novak (2011) feels that higher-order goals of social media are connect, create, consume and control that is 4Cs are fundamental for the interactivity of social media, social media facilitates the to connect people, and when the people connect they create post, upload, blog which is consumed that is either read, watch, listen by the different people, which gives an individual a greater sense to manage and control the applications page such as layout, tagging, rating. Further, because of these capabilities of “4Cs” which social media has, people tend to spend so much of their time using social media and this is the reason why social media is so popular. Thus, the popularity of social media has stimulated researchers to examine social media and its usage. Furthermore, as per Novak (2008) researchers have identified many reasons or motivations of using social media including blogs, Twitter, virtual worlds, YouTube and many others, yet very little is found to guide the analysis of social media usage (Hoffman and Novak, 2012)

2.4.2 Digital marketing and healthcare /pharmaceutical industry

Digital media is changing the healthcare industry (Champagne *et al.*, 2015), new technologies and innovations have enabled pharmaceutical companies to not only improve drug discovery and development but also patient care, as with digitalisation, pharmaceutical business has not only become more patient centric but cost-effective (Das, 2019). Moreover, with digital collaborative services there will be higher transparency leading to a better health care, which in turn will results in better patient engagement (Kemppainen, and Liikkanen, 2017).

Thus, Parekh *et al.* (2016) is of the opinion that, this will lead to an increased the interaction with end users leading to quick and cost-effectiveness healthcare. For this study social media marketing will be used as mode of digital marketing. Moreover, even with the highly regulated pharmaceutical market it is social media which can develop a good relationship with the client, further, it also can help to communicate all the necessary information about pharmaceutical products (Akhtar *et al.*, 2015). As a there is growth potential in social media marketing in pharmaceutical industry, promoting the products, patient education programme can be carried out which can be an opportunity for the pharmaceutical industry. As a result, customer and consumers will acquires knowledge about health, diseases, and treatment. Although there are various social media network channels, which gives information on any drug and disease.

2.4.3 Challenges in digital marketing

Internet usage across the world is increasingly becoming a very significant source of competitive advantage in business to consumer and business to business marketing, by giving huge amount of attention on opportunities of digital marketing but no attention being given to its challenges. Companies have huge amount of data called big data, social media (Leeflang *et al.*, 2014) corresponding to developments the digital marketing, making internet as important marketplaces for the digital transactions of goods and services as a result it has created a tremendous challenges for firms.

2.4.4 Impacts of Digital marketing on consumer

According to Stephen (2016) and Goldstein *et al.* (2014), digital /social media environments/ marketing and its impact on consumer behaviour is still an emerging field. It is exciting to know different informational and social characteristics of digital/social platform impacts the consumers' opinions e.g., through the reviews or choices e.g., for this bids in online auctions, or friends' through social media, is impacting the behaviours. Adopting a distinct perspective, Wilcox and Stephen (2013) found that people using Facebook had no self-control, or lower self-control that when exposed to closer friends.

2.4.5 Digital marketing consumer experience

Cho and Park (2001) is of the opinion that the online customer are not just shoppers but information technology user, and the online experience is a more complex than just the physical shopping experience. Thus, it can be concluded that anyone who is online customer is also an information technology user. However, as per Constantinides, (2002, p. 60) "*web experience can be defined as the consumer's total impression about the online company which is because of his/her exposure to a combination marketing tools, and these can influence the buying behaviour of the online consumer to some extent*". Thus, as per Fortin, (2015), the web experience includes factors such as "searching", "browsing", "finding", "selecting", "comparing", and "evaluating" the information. Digital marketing also helps the consumer to interact and transact directly with the company . Thus, it can be said that digital marketing more than the consumers is important and beneficial for the company for targeting interested customers.

2.4.6 Factors affecting the digital/online consumer behaviour

As per Mustakim, Rahman and Aziz, (2020) online consumer purchasing behaviour has many dimensions, and consumers behave differently in different situations. Moreover, they are of the opinion that there are various factors affecting consumer purchasing behaviour through online shopping.

Figure 2.1: Factors affecting the online consumer behaviour (Constantinides, 2004)

Further, Constantinides (2004) is of the opinion that digital media marketing has created an impact over the virtual customers, however Kotler (2003), feels that frameworks of web experience is in itself a very new experience and is an additional input in the traditional buying behaviour (Kotler, 2003). Moreover, (figure 2.1) explains the different factors such as personal and environmental factors, marketing stimuli and the web experience which affect the consumer behaviour or buyer's decision during their online purchase.

Figure 2.2 External and internal factors consumer online purchasing behaviour (Mustakim, Rahman and Aziz, 2020)

Besides Constantine (2004) even Mustakim, Rahman and Aziz, (2020) in fig 2.2 have identified different external and internal factors effecting the consumer online purchasing behaviour. Accordingly, on analysing these factors, Mustakim, Rahman and Aziz, (2020) came to the conclusion that eventually there was a change in the manner in which people purchased products and services from online shops.

Figure 2.3 Factors that affect consumer purchasing behaviour ((Bucko, Kakalejčik and Ferencová, 2018)

Further, Bucko, Kakalejčík and Ferencová, (2018) in the fig 2.3 has studied various factors such as availability, social proof, scarcity, product details, conditions, social media activity which effects the buying behaviour of online shoppers.

Further as per Pandey and Parmar (2019) perceived ease of use, perceived risk, perceived usefulness, effect of website design, economic factor, availability of products, and customer satisfaction are the different factors effecting the online consumer behaviour. Thus, it can be seen that right from 2004 to 2020 there are various factors such as price, availability, scarcity, perceived value etc that has motivated online customers to purchase products from online sources.

2.5 Social Media

In the year 2000, social media witnessed a great boost of having many social networking sites, as these networking sites boosted the interaction between the individual customers, consumers and the organizations who were sharing common interest. Further, as per Rabinowitz (2013) Web 2.0 is the key element of consumer-generated media (CGM) which is using a latest level of online technology, in the forms include text, images, audio and video including blogs and micro-blogs, vlogs, podcasts, and wikis and. it is defined as an “online applications, platforms and media which aim to facilitate interactions, collaborations and the sharing of content” (Palmer and Koenig-Lewis, 2009, p. 165). As per a report from Forrester Research, it was seen that besides the teenagers even people in the age group of 35 to 44 years used social media, compelling the companies to operating in online space (Kietzmann *et al.*, 2011). Further, Kaplan (2010) says online and internet technology has transformed the interactivity and communication throughout the world, thereby influencing the purchase behaviour of consumers by the application of this integrated marketing communication strategy in form of Blogs, YouTube, My Space, Facebook and websites as they links up millions of users globally with similar interests, views and hobbies (Mangold, 2009). Moreover, social media in health care industry and pharmaceutical industry is not only used for promoting brands, but also improving the interaction across the different stakeholder involved in industry (Grajales *et al.*, 2014).

2.5.1 Social media marketing

Social media marketing is used to promote company and their products is basically a subset of online marketing, made up of social media channels (Barefoot and Szabo, 2010). Kaplan and Heinlein (2010, p.61) goes to define social media marketing is “*a group of internet-based applications that builds on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and it allows the creation and exchange of user-generated content*”. Moreover, as per Akar & Topçu (2011) the consumers who are using social media marketing can, not only generate, but edit and share company related information available on the online portals, thereby making the businesses loss its control. This information is perceived reliable by the consumer than the direct communication from the company. Hence, peer feedback or opinion and the reviews have become a major influencer on buying behaviour of the online customers (Constantinides *et al.*, 2010; Akar and Topçu, 2011). Thus, connection, communication and sharing has become easy (Derham *et al.*, 2011) with the use of social media and this has made it a popular platform for most of the business-related activities ranging from marketing, customer relations management within and out of the company (Kim *et al.*, 2010).

2.5.2 Social media and Pharmaceutical Industry

In last few years, social media has finally become one of the major sources of health information and has gained importance in pharmaceutical and health related industry (Evans, 2006; Bernhardt *et al.*, 2014; Syrkiewicz and Switala, 2015). Moreover, Facebook has gain popularity in last decade, and also Facebook has become a major sources of information on health related topic in the UK, making it one of the most popular social media site for health related information (Collier, 2014; Syrkiewicz, 2015). Moreover, digital and modern technology in the pharmaceutical and healthcare industry is not only limited to the implementation of production and research techniques but also in supplying consumers with innovative medicinal products, by interactive method of selling and building brand of the companies (Syrkiewicz-Świtała, Romaniuk and Ptak, 2016). Digital media such as social media internet big data, etc has become an important part of the life. As almost all the sectors have already has adapted at a faster rate baring a few such as pharmaceutical industry, which was not quick to adopt digital media marketing, but recently, Parekh *et al.* (2016) pharmaceutical industry has utilized digital marketing platform, thereby enabling online purchase of products by the customers and consumers. However, only non- prescription drugs or non- prescription medicines can only be sold online, as a result all the pharmaceutical

companies cannot sell them online as they manufacture prescription drugs, but certain pharmaceutical companies like Pfizer etc have been active, responsive and communicating with customers via social networking platforms, moreover Johnson and Johnson was the first company to launch a YouTube channel. Thus, Pharmaphorum (2018) opines that social media is no longer a fashionable word as it has moved to one of the most technical sector that is pharmaceuticals and healthcare industries. Although healthcare practitioners' and healthcare public institutions are reluctance about using social media, but social media is useful for patients and healthcare consumers in health-related information (Mukherjee *et al.*, 2013). However, Mackey and Liang (2013) has reported that because of social media marketing, online marketing, electronic direct-to-consumer (eDTCA) has become very easy in the pharmaceutical industry worldwide.

Table 2.1 Healthcare informational on the Social Media

Tool	Definition	Example
Weblogs	Online journals written by an author on any topic of interest, and can receive comments and can be shared	www2.mdanderson.org/cancerwise/ Health.com,
Content syndication/ RSS feeds	enables the subscriber to receive online text, video, and other updates	Health.com, mayoclinic.com, cancer.org
e-Games	Interactive games played through the Internet.	CDC.gov, healthgamesresearch.org
Microblogs	Length of the content is restricted	Eg. Twitter
Social networking sites:	Can add friends, send messages create and online communities	Facebook, LinkedIn

health related social networking sites	Allow users to share health related information	dLife.com, stickK.com Youtube.com,
Widgets	web applications that can display featured content from users site to another website	Cdc.gov, widgetbox.com
Wikis	multiple users can create and post content	Wikihealth, wikiph.org

**Compiled by the researcher*

2.5.3 Direct-to-consumer advertising in pharmaceutical industry

Direct-to-consumer-advertising is a common term used by marketing researchers and health related communicators, but Bradley and Zito (1997) in Mukherjee *et al.*, (2013) coined the term direct-to-consumer advertising of prescription drugs and defined it as a promotion or an advertisement by a pharmaceutical company of prescription drug and its information to the common man common public who is not much aware of prescription drug in the lay media (Mukherjee, Limbu and Wanasika, 2013). Furthermore, there are many studies where the term “direct-to-consumer advertising”(DTCA) is used but they have not specified whether it’s a prescription drug or non-prescription drug. As a result, it is confusing direct-to-consumer advertising involves advertisement of over-the-counter medications or prescription medications. Thus, to finish this ambiguity Cordoş *et al.* (2017) carried out a research, accordingly he could prove that direct-to-consumer advertising is basically a promotion or advertisement of prescription drug by pharmaceutical companies through website and social media. Thus, the highly participative and innovative Web 2.0 has influenced the people to search for health-related information on the web.

2.6 Consumer and Consumer behaviour

As per Sundaram (2008) ‘*consumer*’ is someone who buys a product or services not with an objective of reselling, but for his personal consumption. Similarly, Kotler (1994) says that

consumer behaviour is basically a subcategory of marketing, involving a study of different factors such as psychology, sociology, anthropology, economics etc which effects the buying behaviour of the consumers.

According to Font-i-Furnols (2014), consumers are the last step in the chain, and having their expectations met is important. As a result, the companies should know the various factors which go to affect the consumer buying behaviour. Further, consumer behaviour considers a wide variety of factors which go to influence the consumer and wide range of activities which are beyond just purchasing, such as recognising the need, searching for information, and evaluating the alternatives sources for information, next step is building the purchase intention, and finally the act of actually purchase, consuming and lastly or the final stage is the act of disposal. This understanding of consumer behaviour has evolved not only through many noticeable but discernible stages over the past many decades, but through the use of new research methodologies and paradigmatic approaches that's being adopted (Blackwell *et al.*, 2001).

Thus, consumer behaviour is been described differently by different authors. Accordingly, Solomon defines consumer behaviour as *“consumer behaviour is the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, purchase, use or dispose of products, services, ideas or experiences to satisfy needs and desires.”* (Solomon *et al.*, 2006, p 6). Furthermore, Schiffman and Kanuk (2007, p.3) is of the opinion that the consumer behaviour can also be defined as *“the behaviour that consumers display while he is searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating, and disposing of products and services that they expect will satisfy their needs”*.

Moreover, Kotler (1994) is of the view that consumer behaviour is basically a subcategory of marketing which involves “psychology”, “sociology”, “socio-psychology”, “anthropology” and “economics” aspect to understand how why and what customers buy. Thus, consumer behaviour is a study to understand various factors including demographics psychographics etc influencing the consumer purchase decision. Moreover, as per Blythe (2008) the concept of consumer behaviour is gradually changing to consumer purchase behaviour as the consumers within the segment have similar taste of products and services, and this can be the important aspects of consumer behaviour (Lantos, 2011). Besides this, as per Solomon (2010), market segmentation consists of “demographics”, “age”, “gender”, “social-class”, “geographic”, “psychographic” and “behavioural” etc. (Solomon *et al.*, 2010) and consumers environment has significant impact on consumers’ purchase decision which can affect or can change his

desire and motives for product to be purchased (Blythe, 2008). Further, as per Solomon *et al.*, (2010, p.68-69) there some very vital dimensions in consumer behaviour is said to social time, that it, “*The time in relation to social processes and rhythms and schedules in society such as working hours, opening hours, eating hours, and other institutionalized schedules*”. Thus, different authors have expressed consumer behaviour in a different way.

As per Solomon (2006), consumer behaviour is where a person buys, uses or disposes anything with basic intention of getting satisfaction; however, Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) says consumer behaviour is the process whereby a person is searching a product, buys a product with the intentions of getting satisfied. Thus, as per both the author the main objective of consumer behaviour is getting their needs and desire satisfied.

Consumer-buying behaviour as per Kotler (2004, p.601) is defined as “*The buying behaviour of consumers that is the individuals and households who buy goods and services for personal consumption*”. Besides, consumer buying behaviour as per Jerman *et al.*, (2013), is a behavioural study of people in terms of their consumption of products and services. Thus, consumer behaviour as per Mihart (2012) is analysis of the influence of various components of integrated marketing communication (IMC). The important steps in consumer behaviour is “consumers decision making”, moreover as per the (figure 2.4) the decision-making process involves various steps such as “problem recognition”, “information search”, “evaluation of alternatives” followed by “purchase decision”, and last but not the least is the “post purchase evaluation”.

Figure 2.4 Consumer decision-making processes (Kardes *et al.*, 2011)

Besides this, according to Font-i-Furnols (2014), there are three factors that should be considered while explaining consumer behaviour and they are psychological, sensory and marketing. This is being depicted by figure (2.5) is a multidisciplinary model of affecting consumer behaviour. The various interrelated factors of the model that affects the consumers' buying decision-making, the important components being consumer, context, culture.

Figure 2.5 Multidisciplinary model of the main factors affecting consumer behaviour (Font-I-Furnols, 2014)

It is a well-known fact that consumers are rational beings, so can easily be affected by many external factors such as cognitive, emotional, volitional and even automatic actions. According to Font-i-Furnols (2014) various psychological factors have been analysed and described in the scientific literature to have an influence on the buying behaviour of the consumers, and purchase of various products, services or experiences. These factors can motivate an individual's conduct in different ways such as socially, economically, culturally or psychologically.

Table 2.2 History of consumer behaviour theory as defined by different authors (Baxi, 2011)

Researcher	Year	Contribution area
“Katz and Lazarsfeld at Columbia university”	1955	“Information dissemination and interpersonal influence”
“Katona and his colleagues ay University of Michigan”	1960	“Consumer Expectation and consumer attitude”
“Bauer at Harvard”	1960	“consumer response & communication”
“Kuehen Howard”	1962, 1963	“Learning theory”
“Evan Kassarjan”	199, 1965	“Personality and social character”
“Engal Kassarjan and, Cohen”	1963, 1965	“Cognitive dissonance”
“Bourne and Stafford”	1957, 1966	“Reference Group”
“King Zaitman”	1963, 1965	Interpersonal communication
“Levy”	1966	Social class
“Wells”	1966	Lifestyle
“Baurer Sturdivant”	1964, 1969	Sub – Culture
“Kuehen Frank”, “Nicosia”, “Howard and Sheth”	1962, 1966 1969	consumer behaviour
“David laibson”	1997	overspending attitude and behavioural economist, will, power, and money
“Sendhill Mullainathan”		Integrated and economic behavioural into mainstream theory.

2.6.1 Theoretical approaches to the study of consumer behaviour

Baxi (2011) consumer behaviour is a multi-disciplinary study involving different parameter such as organisations, consumer and government authorities. It finds its application in consumer buying behaviour as it provides an insight to the marketers with regards various elements of marketing mix. There are many approaches of consumer behaviour theory, accordingly, five major approaches have emerged, and they were Economic Man, Psychodynamic, Behaviourist, Cognitive, and Humanistic approach. Moreover, the term 'economic man' was first used in the late 19th century (Persky 1995). As per this approach a consumer should be aware of all the available options and he should be capable of correctly rating each of them (Schiffman and Kanuk, 2007). However, Sigmund Freud (1856-1939) has widely contributed to the psychodynamic work (Stewart, 1994), according to him Id, the Ego and the Superego are the three main facets of the psyche (Freud 1923). So, it can be said that the psychodynamic approach should be determined by individual cognition, or environmental stimuli rather than by biological drives. Thus, consumer behaviour can be said as a subject of biological influence (Arnold *et al.*, 1991; Arnold *et al.*, 2005).

2.6.2 Consumer culture theory (CCT)

Consumer culture is a social arrangement relating culture and social issues. Moreover, consumer culture theory (CCT) as per Arnould and Thompson (2005) is about choices and behaviours which can either be related socially and culturally as opposed to an economic or psychological. Moreover, it's also about the relationships which relates consumer action in the marketplace (Arnould and Thompson, 2005). Further, it can be said as a study involving cultural complexity which can link the researcher's efforts (Bajde and Canniford, 2015). Thus, in short Arnould and Thompson (2005) are of the opinion that consumer culture theory basically takes into consideration culture as the basis of experience, meaning, and action (Geertz, 1983).

2.7 Marketing Communications (MC)

Marketing communication is a two-way process, where the company emits the information towards its clients, suppliers, competitors, opinion leaders, etc. and then the information is collected the by the company (Pilarczyk, 2004). Moreover, Goi (2009) expressed

McCarthy(1964) refined Borden's idea of marketing mix and is of the opinion that marketing communication consisting of 4Ps "price", "place", "promotion" and "product" and forms a very important part of marketing management to influence customers and their buying behaviour. Moreover, as 4Ps framework has been subjected to much criticism for being too simplistic and misleading so the 4Ps framework was extended to 7Ps, and it has found its place specially for the service marketing. As rightly pointed out by Ravangard, Khodadad and Bastani, (2020) in most of the industry other than the service industry the marketing mix is better known as 4Ps that is "product", "price", "place", and "promotion", however in service industry, there are other factors as well, they are "delivery", "customer engagement", "physical environment", "time", and "processes" are also very important or vital factors. Thus, Abedi and Abedini (2017) in Ravangard, Khodadad and Bastani, (2020) have identified 7Ps of the marketing mix, influencing the choice of the consumers. These 7ps are "price", "products", "physical assets", "place", "process", "people", and "promotion", which add to service marketing.

Thus, as per Enache, (2011) with the increase in the competition and different perspective offered, marketing mix has become a tools to reach their end goals. Moreover, depending on industries, a marketing framework is provided to understand, analyse or to alter or change the marketing forces present in the environment. Thus, as per Enache, (2011) by using the 7 Ps framework a company can create a coherent marketing mix to address its objectives and attract the customer. Thus, the framework of 7Ps of marketing mix has helped to not only understand the market forces or analyse them but also to change or alter them.

Further, as per Kotler (2012), marketing communication is a result oriented process of informing, reminding and persuading the different customers or audience, about the product or services which the company sells (Kotler *et al.*, 2012; Završnik, 2013). As per Kiang *et al.* (2000) in the last decade online marketing has gained lot of importance, as it helps the company to interact and exchange information between sellers and buyers with an expectation of getting customer/consumer detail or information which can be later used during the product launches and product promotion (Shimp, 2003).

2.7.1 Influence of marketing communication on consumer behaviour

As per Keller, (2001) marketing communication theory, marketing communication should create an impact on the consumers purchase behaviour by informing, persuading inciting, and reminding him of a product or service different situations and circumstances. There are various things such as market research and market segmentation which influence the consumer

behaviour. Thus, marketers influence the buying behaviour of their target audience. Furthermore, as per Hun (2014) besides many other factors, “products characteristic” is a very important factor, which can easily influence the consumers buying behaviour. As per one of the surveys, product packaging price can also influence the consumer behaviour and consumer perception (Hun, 2014). Moreover, company should be aware of 3 key major external factors cultural, social, personal and psychological factors which can impact on the consumer behaviour (Hun, 2014). As per PIMT (2014) buyers purchase decision is not a very straightforward process, and may differ from person to person and in different situation (Hun, 2014). Thus Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2009) says consumer behaviour can be changed or altered by marketing communication, thus it can be said that marketing communication can influence the buying behaviour of the consumers, but Howell (2012) is of the opinion that different people have different view and this can also differ if they are from different generation. Furthermore, it is noted that online communication impacts both men and women equally, but higher preferences for online marketing communication was seen with young adults as against to people who were in late age or middle age (Thayer, 2006)

2.7.2 Influence of social media on the behaviour of consumers

According to Forbes (2013) it is noted that social media has influenced consumer behaviour to purchase all kind of product ranging from expensive to cheap products based on the online feedback. As a result, Hamid (2007) feels that consumers just want information and feedback from social media before making any purchases, as Xu, feels that consumers regard social media feedback as a very important and they believe on these feedbacks and information. Similarly, it was found in a survey that 62% of consumers in USA read online reviews generated by consumer, moreover 98% found these reviews very useful and 80% of them were influenced by it (Ioanas,2014). Furthermore, Schlosser (2005) and Ioanas *et al.* (2014) also found that even a minutest of negative comments changed the perception of the consumers towards a product or service. Thus, this shows that social media can influence the behaviour of consumer.

2.7.3 Influence of social media on consumer behaviour in Pharmaceutical industry:

According to Jawaid and Ahmed, (2018) it was found that majority of UK population were using Facebook, LinkedIn etc to seek health related information. Further, use of social media was affected by several factor such as value, trust, attitude, and gender (Kim *et al.*, 2016).

Furthermore, as per Moorhead *et al* (2013) most of the people in United states used websites particularly related to health which were interactive and informative, moreover, it is gaining more importance.

2.8 Relationship between pharmaceutical industry and its major stakeholders

There are different category of stakeholders such as primary and the secondary stakeholder, but according to Daft (2011), in case of pharmaceutical organizations stakeholders can be a single person or more than one person, having a common or a mutual interest towards the activities of the organization, these people can be either a suppliers, or a consumers who is using the organisation's pharmaceutical product, it can also be a the medical research centre or an institute carrying out medical research, or the employees working for the organization or the shareholders who form the foundation of the company's success or failure as they are directly involved in the direct economic situation. Secondary stakeholders are those who are not directly involved in the welfare of the organisation, and do not play any vital role in the economic development of the organisation, such as government, trade unions, the media, and political parties etc but are as important as the primary stakeholders (Hellriegel *et al.*, 2007). Furthermore, as per Herxheimer (2003) in case of the pharmaceutical companies' different groups of stakeholders have been working together constructively and they are patients and the pharmaceutical organisation, of which one usually rich, the other poor have developed over the years.

2.9 Online/internet Pharmacy

During the past two decades it is been noted that to purchase products and services internet has become one of the most accepted form route of transaction. Similarly, even for buying medications online sources or online shops are no exception. However, besides the benefits, there are several risks linked to the purchase of over the counter medicines outside the traditional community pharmacy. Moreover, as per Fung *et al.* (2004), an internet-based vendor that sells prescription and non-prescription medicines is called as an online or an internet based pharmacy and it can either be legitimate and illegitimate (Desai, 2016). There are thousands of accessible online and internet pharmacies on the web, but the actual size of the market is currently unknown, as a very minimal or less information or data on the use of internet pharmacies for procuring medications and other health products is available. Moreover, use of illegal or illicit online pharmacies are of greater risk to life and health of the patient and also dangerous for the public health as these websites are not legal or are unregulated, and lack

required license, these online pharmacies markets pharmaceutical products such as “vaccines”, “non-communicable disease”, “medicines”, “essential medicines”, and also focus on “no prescription” required (Mackey, 2013). It has been seen that consumers who are engaged in self-diagnosing their health conditions are the one who procure medicines from such online pharmacies. Furthermore, purchasing medications from these online pharmacies can be very dangerous to the life as there is no guarantee of quality or safety (Forman *et al.*, 2006). As the pharmaceutical industry is becoming more digitalized, it is very important that these companies implement changes in their value chains and prevent disruptive innovation. Besides this, Gurau (2005) says despite strict regulations, online sales of prescription and non-prescription medicines is growing, main reason being customer satisfaction, as internet is an attractive channel for the health-related information and for purchasing healthcare related products (Kanungo, 2004). As per Spain *et al.*, (2001) the main reasons of using internet for health related products is because of deficiencies in medical system such as long waiting list to get an appointment, shortage of medical doctors or health care profession and very low quality of the service, have forced people to find different ways to treat their diseases. Moreover as per Gurau (2005) for the elderly, people who are ill, handicapped, and those who are isolated getting health related information from social media and home delivery from online pharmacies of prescription and non-prescription medicine can be lifesavers, besides these reasons, customers are also attracted to convenience, low prices, anonymity, home delivery promised (Gurau,2005). Despite this, there are very few academic studies that have taken place to study or analyse the online pharmacies, or the profile of customers who use online pharmacies to purchase over the counter medicines.

2.10 Changing face of marketing with social media marketing/Digital marketing

As per Dwivedi *et al.*, (2020) computer mediated communications in form of information technology such as “internet”, “social media”, “mobile apps”, and other “digital communications technologies”, have become not only an important part of life but an integral part of life for the people all around the globe. As per a recent survey Statista, (2020) 4.54 billion people which accounts for 59 % of the global population are active users of internet, thus, it can be noted that computer mediated communication in form of internet and social media usage has become one of most important and an integral part of life for most of the people across the world (Clement, 2020a). Moreover, in the year 2019, it was that almost 2.95 billion people globally were active social media and internet users, which was forecasted to increase to almost 3.43 billion by 2023 (Statistica, 2020), but it has already become 4.54 billion

in the 2020. Thus based on the literatures it has been concluded that social media and digital media has become an imminent and an important part of the people as it provides an important platform for receiving information, and also a very important platform for the businesses to promote its product and services that too a very low cost. Thus Ajina (2019), says marketing through the different digital medias and channels has increased the reach of the companies at a much lower price thereby are able to achieve their marketing objectives easily.

Further, as per Lister (2017) it was also noted that social media channels not only provide platform for business, but platforms such Facebook has more than 50 million businesses registered out of which 88 % of businesses also use Twitter to fulfil their marketing needs and objectives. Besides providing a platform for business needs these platforms also provides political promotion services. As it is noted that people have started spending an increased time on social media searching for products and information and communicating with other consumers, as a result companies have also responded to this change in consumer behaviour by making digital and social media an important part of their business and product promotion (Stephen, 2016). In order to aid to this they have started their marketing communication and branding goals through the different channels of social media marketing (Chaubey et al. 2016), thereby enabling companies to influence consumer's attitudes by connecting with them and receive their feedback, which will help them improve their products and current services. Moreover, this will also help in creating a awareness of the brands through the different digital channels (Lal et al., 2020) which has led to a substantial decline in the traditional communication channels (Kaur et al., 2018)

Thus, as per Schultz & Peltier, (2013) this has required the businesses to use different digital channels and social media marketing strategies to retain and increase market share by developing their social media plans by giving increased power to consumers (Naylor et al., 2012); . As a result, social media digital marketing has positively influenced the attitudes of consumer toward online shops thereby increasing eCommerce centric business (Hossain et al., 2019, 2020). Further, as per Shukla and Nigam, (2018) digital channels are very normal today for the consumers to carry out daily lives shopping by the use of mobile phone, different shopping apps, thereby impacting the consumer experience.

According to Chaubey *et al.* (2016) various social media marketing channels have been hot for marketing communication and branding goals, and is increasing its horizon and motivating consumers, marketers by making it one of the main channel of information. As a result, this has led to a significant change in the consumer behaviour due to technological advancement

and innovation which has directly contributed to the interaction and decisions making and online shopping. It is also changing the way the marketers communicate with their customer and prospective customer and has become an alternative channel media of communication for organizations to liaison with the online customer (Baker, 2009).

Further, as per Arnold (2018), even healthcare professionals are not far away from social media and digital media marketing, as 60% of doctors search social media for delivering better healthcare to patients, thus social media finds its place in healthcare. Besides 41% of consumers have also confirmed that the health-related information from social media impacts their decisions. Thus, it can be noted that even pharmaceutical industry is not far behind and is replacing traditional marketing to digital and online including social media marketing as it offers the ease of interaction in limited time with end users through the informative and interactive sites, and this concept is very prominent in the United States (Parekh *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 2.6 Digital consumer/patient (Mannan and Mubeen, 2018)

Moreover, as per Mannan and Mubeen, (2018) online healthcare professional and patient have increasingly adapted mobile app and social media networks which provides online health related information, thus instigating pharmaceutical companies to explore and invest in digital technologies, although companies like Johnson and Johnson was first to start a YouTube channel for the healthcare professional and patients. Further, Mendoza-Herrera *et al.*, (2020) has also commented that social media platforms have become a least expensive tools for addressing public health related issues in those countries where there is a limitations of health-related institutions. Moreover, globally for health promotion even, “WHO, the World Bank, and the United Nations Children’s Fund” use social media regularly and have millions

of followers globally, further, there are commercial social media platforms as well having healthcare related tools for the public health implications, such as Facebook who has partnered with the American Blood Centres and the American Red Cross for blood donation awareness and tools to notify people where they can donate blood in case of short supply in their local areas (Budaraju,2019). Thus, Moorhead et al. (2013) says that social media and online media has added a new dimension to health care system by communicating to public, patients, and health professionals about health issues over the internet (Moorhead et al., 2013), but this has also facilitated social media consumers to buy over the counter medicines and healthcare related products from the online pharmacy (Fittler et al., 2018).

2.11 Hypothesis Development

Following the literature review on social media marketing in pharmaceutical Industry and its influence on the consumers, it was very much evident that consumers did search health related information on the internet and also searched for over the counter drugs on the social media and internet. From the literature review it was seen that convenience, security, price, were the factors that lead consumers to buy over the counter medicine from the online pharmacies. Thus, to study the influence of social media marketing on the consumers the following hypothesis were formulated:

- Age and purchase of over the counter medicine online pharmacy
- Age and convenience related for buying online sources.
- Age and price related for buying over the counter medicine from online sources
- Age and choice related for buying over the counter medicine from online sources.
- Age and combined scores of different variables related for buying over the counter medicine medicines from online pharmacy.
- Age and information security a risk for buying over the counter medicine online.
- Ages on healthcare information related for buy over the counter medicine from the internet
- Age and extra charges spend when buying over the counter medicine from online or internet pharmacy.
- Age and searching healthcare related information on the social media.
- Gender and cumulative scores of different various factors for buying over the counter medicine from online pharmacy.

2.12 Conceptual framework:

Figure 2.7 Developed by the researcher

2.13 A thematic table to summarize the literature review chapter

AUTHOR(S)	THEMES
Jahdi and Acikdilli (2009)	Concept of marketing
Završnik (2013)	Comparison between traditional marketing and digital marketing
Ab Hamid <i>et al.</i> (2013)	Various channels of digital marketing such social media, blogs, micro blogs can change the consumer behaviour
Downey (2012)	Social media is emerging as well equipped and easy to connect to a larger audience for interaction and communication.
Kapoor (2018)	social media has a wider application in the business and organisations
Hun and Yazdarnifard (2014)	Communication is very important for social interaction
Melewar <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Effective communication
Mihart (2012)	Understanding and perceiving the communication
Hun and Yazdarnifard (2014); Keller (2001)	Marketing communication should remind the consumers of the offerings of the company.
Fortin and Uncles (2011)	computer mediated marketing in form of social media is gaining momentum
Yazdanifard <i>et al.</i> (2011); Green and Kesselheim (2010)	Pharmaceutical industry being an information-intensive industry was slow in the adopting social media marketing

Masood <i>et al.</i> (2009)	pharmaceutical marketing communicates such as blogs, social networks, independently and also as a support
Webb (2010)	Social media a new way for pharmaceutical companies to interact with consumers and physicians
Anscombe <i>et al.</i> (2015); Enyinda <i>et al.</i> (2018)	health related information on different website every month.
Anscombe <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Patients search lot health related information on internet.
Heilman and West (2015)	Not just the patients but the medical community is also digitalizing
Heilman <i>et al.</i> (2011)	Wikipedia is considered to be the world's most popular source among healthcare professionals
Buttner <i>et al.</i> (2006)	few studies on online marketing of over the counter medicine.
Syrkiewicz-Switlala <i>et al.</i> (2016)	very few researches relating to social media marketing in pharmaceutical industry
Appel <i>et al.</i> (2019)	worldwide billions of people use social media, considered to be the fastest growing technology
Syrkiewicz <i>et al.</i> (2012)	“convenience”, “interactivity” and “two-way flow of information” over the internet.
Armstrong and Kotler (2012)	pharmaceutical company building a relationship with the customer over the social media

Limaye and Saraogi (2018)	worldwide out of the 74% of Internet users on social media, 80% of them mostly look for health related information
von Muhlen and Ohno-Machado (2012); Childs and Martin (2012)	senior population relied more on health information on social media,
Bernhardt <i>et al.</i> , (2014); Ventola (2014)	active participants on social media for health related information comprised of all age and all profession
Benetoli <i>et al.</i> (2017)	Most of the people relied on WebMD (56%) and Wikipedia (31%) for health-related information.
DeLorme <i>et al.</i> (2011)	increasing number of consumers going online for health information leading to drug advertising online, and online pharmacies
Fox and Duggan (2013)	Searching health related information has become is a popular activities on the internet.
Kotler and Keller (2008)	marketing as a “ <i>meeting needs profitably</i> ”
Gronroos (2004)	marketing is a process of developing the business
Layton (2007)	marketing as a concept to meet organisational goals
Abou Nabout <i>et al.</i> (2012)	digital marketing is a technology-enabled process enabling companies to collaborate with customers and partners in order to communicate, deliver, and sustain value
Michael (2010)	digital marketing “online marketing”, “internet marketing” or “web marketing”

Ford and Freeman (2009)	digital marketing in form of online communication
Owens (2009)	In online marketing the interaction between consumers and the marketers is much better and higher.
Kitchen and Burgmann (2010)	Digital technologies are altering the way marketing is done
Wind (2002)	digital technology is altering consumers behaviour towards products and markets
Champagne <i>et al.</i> (2015)	Digital media is changing the healthcare industry
Parekh <i>et al.</i> (2016)	Social media will lead to an increased the interaction with end users leading to quick and cost-effectiveness healthcare
Leeflang <i>et al.</i> (2014)	Challenges in digital marketing
Stephen (2016; Goldstein <i>et al.</i> , 2014)	digital /social media environments/ marketing has impacted consumer behaviour
Wilcox and Stephen (2013)	Facebook affected self-control
Cho and Park (2001)	online customer is not just a shopper but can also be an information technology expert.
Constantinides (2004)	digital marketing has influenced the virtual customers
Rabinowitz (2013)	social media, is consumer-generated media
Baker (2009); Thevenot (2007); Tulgan (2007)	Social media includes blogs and micro-blogs, vlogs, podcasts, and wikis

Palmer and Koenig-Lewis (2009)	Social media online applications, platforms and media which aim to facilitate interactions, collaborations and the sharing of content
Kaplan (2010)	Social media influencing the buying behaviour of consumers
Grajales <i>et al.</i> (2014)	in health care industry social media is used for improving peer-to-peer and clinician-to-patient communication,
Barefoot and Szabo (2010)	Companies use Social media marketing to promote their products, are also used as a subset of online marketing activities
Constantinides <i>et al.</i> (2010); Akar and Topçu (2011)	Social media marketing has an influence on buying behaviour
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2010)	social media a popular platform for most of the business-related activities
Parekh <i>et al.</i> (2016)	pharmaceutical industry has utilized social media sites or ecommerce sites as digital marketing platform, thus enabling online purchase of products by the customers
Pharmaphorum (2018)	social media is no longer a fashionable word it's moved beyond it.
Mackey and Liang (2013)	social media marketing and online marketing in pharmaceutical industry
Sundaram (2008)	“ <i>Consumer</i> ’ is someone who buys a product or services not with an objective of reselling
Kotler (2004)	Consumer-buying behaviour

Solomon <i>et al.</i> (2006)	Consumer behaviour
Schiffman and Kanuk (2007)	Consumer behaviour
Kotler (1994)	consumer behaviour is basically a subcategory of marketing
Blythe (2008)	consumer buying behaviour is gradually changing into consumer purchase behaviour
Solomon (2010)	market segmentation is made up of “demographics”, “age”, “gender”, “social class”, “geographic”, “psychographic” and “behavioural”
Baxi (2011)	consumer behaviour is a multi-disciplinary study involving marketing organisations, consumer groups and governmental authorities
Arnould and Thompson (2005)	Consumer culture theory (CCT) is all about choices and behaviours
Goi (2009)	Concept of 4Ps price, place, promotion and product
Kiang <i>et al.</i> (2000)	online marketing communication helps company by interacting and exchanging information between sellers and buyers, with an objective to gets the full detail of the customer/ consumer
Hawkins and Mothersbaugh (2009)	consumer behaviour across the globe can be influenced by marketing communication
Kim <i>et al.</i> (2016)	In the United Kingdom, public use Facebook to seek healthcare information

Arnold (2018)	social media is being used by physicians, pharmaceutical companies etc for health related activities.
Moorhead <i>et al.</i> (2013)	social media brings a new dimension to health care
Evans (2006); Bernhardt <i>et al.</i> (2014); Syrkiewicz-Switlala and Switala (2015)	Social media gained importance in pharmaceutical and health related industry
Gurau (2005)	Online pharmacies
Kanungo (2004)	internet in an attractive channel for health related information and also for purchasing healthcare related products such as medicines.

Source: Compiled by the researcher

2.14 Summary

Thus, this section of the report was based on the social media, impact of social media, communication, how social media is changing the communication pattern in the healthcare industry, online pharmacy, besides how it is impacting the social media online consumers to purchase healthcare related product from the online pharmacy, however these products are normally over the counter product. The next chapter presents discussions on the research context which will discuss the overall the pharmaceutical market in the UK.

3 CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH CONTEXT

3.1 UK pharmaceutical market analysis:

According to ABPI (2021) the pharmaceutical industry is an important sector in the UK the most dynamic industries in the UK and also the major contributor to the country's economy. As per research and consulting firm Global Data's (2016), there are 5,000 life sciences companies that develop, produce and market products and services in the pharmaceutical, medical device and biotechnology markets.

On analysing the UK pharmaceutical generics market, it was noted that the UK market value has been growing very strongly in recent years despite the maturity of the market. Growth in the forecast period is expected to decelerate. Moreover, growth has been slower since 2013 by 10.9%, share of generics declined by 7.1% in 2015, however in 2016 there was a growth of 4.1% and 3.9% in the year 2017; in the year 2018 UK generics market had total revenues of \$12.8bn. The, representing a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 12.7% between 2014 and 2018. Moreover, market consumption volume increased with a CAGR of 0.3% between 2014 and 2018, to reach 85% of total pharma volume. The market's volume is expected to rise to 88.5% by the end of 2023, representing a CAGR of 0.8% for the 2018-2023 period. Besides, market consumption is already high at 85% of the total pharmaceutical volume, is increasing slowly each year with more emphasis being put on generics by the NHS and private companies. The performance of the market is forecast to decelerate, with an anticipated CAGR of 4.5% for the five-year period 2018 - 2023, which is expected to drive the market to a value of \$15.9bn by the end of 2023. (MarketLine, 2019)

For pharmaceutical companies in the UK market, Brexit continues to cause major uncertainty, primarily in regard to the regulatory process, human resource and compliance legislation, and can also have negative implications such as the relocation of the European Medicines Agency and essentially isolating the UK from the European pharmaceutical community. Alternatively, it could be an opportunity for the pharmaceutical market to gain greater regulatory freedom, which could in turn make the market more competitive. However, the outcome is yet to be seen. More market saturation is expected, which will raise the market's performance, and with many important patents expiring, it is expected that the generics market will benefit. The aging population will also drive demand for more medication as the levels of chronic disease rises

higher. The performance of the market is forecast to decline, with an anticipated CARC of -0.4% for the five-year period 2019-2024, which is expected to drive the market to a value of \$26,023.8m by the end of 2024 (MarketLine, 2019).

3.2 Pharma Market Data

Market value

As per Market line it was reported that the United Kingdom generics pharmaceutical market grew by 6.7% in 2018 to reach a value of \$12792.7 million. The compound annual growth rate of the market in the period 2014–18 was 12.7% (Market line, 2019).

Table 3.1: United Kingdom generic market value: \$million, 2014-2018 (Source: MarketLine)

Year	\$ million	£ million	€ million	% Growth
2014	7,939.8	5,956.0	6,730.1	
2015	9,731.9	7,300.4	8,249.2	22.6%
2016	10,745.1	8,060.4	9,108.0	10.4%
2017	11,984.7	8,990.3	10,158.8	11.5%
2018	12,792.7	9,596.4	10,843.6	6.7%
CAGR: 2014–18				12.7%

Source: MarketLine (2019)

Figure 3.1 United Kingdom generic market value: \$million, 2012-2016 (source: Market Line)

3.3 UK Pharma Market volume

The United Kingdom generics market grew by 3.7% in 2018 to reach a volume of 85 % of total pharma volume. The compound annual growth rate of the market in the period 2014–18 was 0.3% (Market line, 2019).

Table 3.2 United Kingdom generic market volume : % of total Pharma Volume, 2014-2018

Year	% of total pharma	% Growth
2014	84.0	
2015	78.0	(7.1%)
2016	80.1	2.6%
2017	82.0	2.4%
2018	85.0	3.7%
CAGR: 2014–18		0.3%

Source: MarketLine (2019)

Figure 3.2 United Kingdom generic market volume : % of total Pharma Volume, 2014-2018
(Source: Market Line, 2019)

3.4 Market segmentation:

The United Kingdom accounts for 17.5% of the European generics market value. (MarketLine, 2019).

Table 3.3: United Kingdom generic market geographical segmentation: million 2018 (MarketLine, 2019)

Geography	2018	%
Germany	23,012.3	31.5
United Kingdom	12,792.7	17.5
France	4,162.4	5.7
Spain	3,818.1	5.2
Italy	1,371.6	1.9
Rest of Europe	27,890.0	38.2
Total	73,047.1	100%

Figure 3.3: United Kingdom generic market geography segmentation(MarketLine, 2019)

3.5 Market outlook

As per the Market value forecast in 2023, the United Kingdom generics market is estimated to have a value of \$15,916.8 million, thus increase by 24.4% since 2018. Thus 4.5% growth is predicted during the period 2018–23 in the UK pharmaceutical market (Market line, 2019).

Table 3.4: United Kingdom generic market value forecast: \$million, 2018-2023

Year	\$ million	£ million	€ million	% Growth
2018	12,792.7	9,596.4	10,843.6	6.7%
2019	13,587.6	10,192.7	11,517.4	6.2%
2020	14,272.0	10,706.1	12,097.6	5.0%
2021	14,890.6	11,170.2	12,621.9	4.3%
2022	15,404.8	11,555.9	13,057.8	3.5%
2023	15,916.8	11,939.9	13,491.7	3.3%
CAGR: 2018–23				4.5%

Source: MarketLine (2019)

Figure 3.4: United Kingdom generics market value forecast: \$million 2018-2023 (Source: MarketLine 2019)

3.6 Market volume forecast

In 2023, the United Kingdom generics market is forecast to have a volume of 88.5 % of total pharma volume, an increase of 4.1% since 2018, thus 0.8% compound annual growth rate is predicted in the period 2018–23 (Market line, 2019).

Table 3.5: United Kingdom generic market volume forecast% of total pharma, 2018–23

Year	% of total pharma	% Growth
2018	85.0	3.7%
2019	83.6	(1.6%)
2020	86.6	3.6%
2021	87.8	1.5%
2022	88.1	0.3%
2023	88.5	0.4%
CAGR: 2018–23		0.8%

Source: MarketLine(2019)

Figure 3.5: United Kingdom generic market volume forecast. Source: (MarketLine, 2019)

3.7 Government policies relating to pharmaceutical industry in UK

The pharmaceutical industry in UK is regulated by the Association of British Pharmaceutical Industry (ABPI). The ABPI is recognised by the government as the industry body negotiating on behalf of the branded pharmaceutical industry for statutory consultation requirements including the pricing scheme for medicines in the UK. On 27 November 2017, the Government launched its Industrial Strategy white paper. The ABPI have welcomed the government's roadmap for business (Market line, 2017).

3.8 The pharmaceutical sector's contribution to the UK economy

According to a new report published by PwC on Monday 6 March 2017, which deals with the economic contribution of the UK Life Science industry, to determine the value added to the UK economy by the life sciences sector. Thus, it was noted that the pharmaceutical industry is one of the major contributors to the economy of the UK, besides bringing lifesaving and life-enhancing medicines to patients and ABPI represents companies in supplying 80 per cent of branded medicines used by the NHS and who are researching and developing the majority of the current medicines pipeline, ensuring the UK remains at the forefront of helping patients prevent, manage and overcome disease. Moreover, the UK biopharmaceutical industry has strong clusters across the country which includes South East, North West and Scotland and over 62,000 employees, thereby giving the highest productivity over £330,000 GVA per employee. This sector also has an exports worth £30bn (PWC, 2017).

3.9 Post-Brexit and UK pharma industry

According to News by Press Office in ABPA(2020) in a joint statement Richard Torbett, the Chief Executive of the “Association of the British Pharmaceutical Industry” (ABPI) and Nathalie Moll, Director General, “European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations” (EFPIA), together representing the EU and UK pharmaceutical industry, said:

"We have always said that a deal is in the best interest of patients in the UK and the EU. This means ongoing collaboration in key areas including scientific research and cooperation in areas like medicines safety. We will now take the time to look at the detail to understand what it means for our members and the future of the pharmaceutical industry".

“Regardless of a deal, the end of the transition means there will be a significant change in how border and customs arrangements work come Jan 1st and companies have been working on

contingency plans to mitigate any disruption. We will continue to do everything in our power to maintain the flow of medicines to all parts of the UK and the EU."

3.10 Summary

This chapter discusses with overall pharmaceutical healthcare market of UK, in terms of growth, contribution to the economy, overall Government policy in this sector, which is highly regulated, and how will the Brexit and post-Brexit impact this market and. The next section will be dealing on the research methodology.

4 CHAPTER FOUR: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

Methodology is defined and described by many author , but as per Brown (2006) methodology is a framework or the foundation for conducting the research. Similarly, O’Leary (2004, p.85) described methodology as the “framework used to conduct the research which is associated with a sets of paradigmatic assumptions”. Moreover, methodology is a combination of two important factors and it to achieve its objectives of the research, the researcher should replicate the methodology used in similar researches (Allan and Randy, 2005)

According to Wilson (2013), the main purpose of business research is basically to gather information to aid in business-related decision-making. Moreover, business research is a systematic process with an specific objective, where the data is collected, recorded, analysed and interpreted for solving managerial problem. This chapter will deal with methodology that will be used in this research. The methodology includes type of research, research population, and sampling frame, proposed implementation of sampling plan, sampling size, sampling method, respondent selection, data measurement and data collection. To understand the key concepts of research and how they fit into your methodology, Honeycomb of Research Methodology will be considered. Accordingly honeycomb model of research methodology is shown below:

Figure 4.1: The honeycomb of research mythology (Wilson, 2013)

According to Wilson (2013), research methodology consists of 6 main elements that is “research philosophy”; “research approach”; “research strategy”; “research design”; “data collection” and “data analysis techniques”. Thus, Samekh and Lewin (2005, P.346) defines methodology as “the collection of methods or rules by which a particular piece of research is undertaken’ and the ‘principles, theories and values that underpin a particular approach to research”. This study is based on abductive philosophy and mixed methods research design, data was conducted through the structured questionnaire for quantitative study and semi-structured questionnaire was used to collect the data by interviews. Furthermore, this chapter consist of important parts of the research methodology such as research methods, research approaches and methodology, with a main intention to develop a suitable research methodology to address the aim and the objectives of the study. Besides, it also discussed the research process, and various aspects of the data collection methods and the statistical techniques which was applied to analyse the data collected. The importance of choosing a research design is emphasised by Thomas (2004), as research design is a foundation for conducting a research (Bryman and Bell, 2007). In studies relating to social and behavioural sciences mixed method of research design is considered as the best approach to address the research questions. Moreover, research approach should always be considered while designing the research (Patel, 2006). As per Tashakkori and Teddlie (1998) pragmatism is a paradigm which is different from constructivism and it deals with qualitative approach and positivism deals in quantitative approach, but the paradigm advises on the use of mixed method in problems and research related to behavioural and social study. Further, mixed-method approach is a combination of qualitative and quantitative method, and can be used as data collection techniques and analysis. Thus, in this research mixed method approach is adopted as the researcher feels that one single method was not sufficient to explore the given problem (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; Creswell *et al.*, 2004).

An overview of the research methodology applied in this research:

Table 4.1: An overview of the research methodology

Research Method Used in the Study	Mixed research methods
Research Paradigm	Pragmatic paradigm
Research Approach	Abductive approach
Primary Data Collection Method	For Quantitative data collection survey was done using the structured questionnaire. For Qualitative data collection In-depth semi-structured interviews were conducted
Secondary Data Collection Method	Books and journal articles
Data Analysis Technique	For Quantitative Analysis Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used For Qualitative Analysis Thematic analysis was adopted.

Figure 4.2 Overview of the research process (developed by the researcher)

4.2 Theoretical Paradigm and Assumptions

In Chapter 1 it is indicated that the purpose of this study is to establish the influence of social media marketing among the consumers of the pharmaceutical industry. So as per Berg (2004) in his opinion the choice of philosophy should be very accurate as it influences the research data collection and data analysis and also the result of the research. Accordingly, philosophies are interconnected like epistemology, ontology and methodology (Guba and Lincoln, 1985) and ontology is connected to methodology frameworks and epistemological assumptions. Thus, according to Burrell and Morgan (1979), at every step of research there are assumptions, assumptions regarding human knowledge called epistemological assumptions, about the realities in research called as ontological assumptions and the way an individual's values influenced the research process called as axiological assumptions. These assumptions precisely shape the understanding of the research questions, the methods and the interpretations of findings (Crotty, 1998). Further, epistemology is assumptions about acceptable, valid and legitimate knowledge, and how to communicate this knowledge to others (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). Ontology is all about assumptions about the nature of reality, and it shapes the way in which the research objects are seen. Thus, in business and management organisations, management, individuals' organisational events etc. are the objects. So, ontology is the all about business and management and the choice for the research project. Axiology is all about ethics, values in the research process. Furthermore, research philosophy consists of Positivist, interpretive, pragmatic and ideological (Miller and Crewell, 1997), but this section will deal only on with positivism, interpretivist, and pragmatism.

4.3 Positivism

Positivism is a philosophical stance based on observable social reality which is consist of unambiguous and accurate knowledge, it would be organisations and other social entities as real in the same way as physical objects and natural phenomena are real. As per Crotty, (1998) epistemologically is based on observable and measurable facts and phenomena etc that can be observed, or measured leading to a meaningful data . That it can be said that there is a causal relationship between the data and scientists who creates law-like generalisations (Gill and Johnson 2010). Thus, positivism can be defined as "*positivism is an epistemology position that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond*" (Bryman and Bell 2003 p.14). In positivism research knowledge is

derived by mathematical and statistical process which is derived by the application of quantitative research approach.

4.4 Interpretivism

Interpretivist philosophy deals with observations and relationships between a situation and variable (Bryman and Bell, 2003). Further, Anderson (2005) is of the opinion that interpretive approach, leads to losing the direction of the study and study can be explored rather than tested for the hypothesis that are predetermined.

4.5 Pragmatic /mixed method approach

Pragmatic method or mixed method approach is basically a combination of positivism and interpretivism method and can also be called as Hybrid method. Pragmatic or mixed method approach helps to maximize the research advantage, moreover Bryman and Bell (2011) is of the opinion that this method is normally used in the social research. as a result, this study will adopt pragmatic method approach to achieve the overall objectives and aim of the study.

4.6 Research design

For the collecting the data and analysing data research design is chosen, that is research design is basically a framework, which means that it deals with plan of the research consisting of structure and its strategy and the method in which the how the research will be carried out (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Moreover, Anderson (2005) is of the opinion that research design can fine tune the research ideas into a research project. The research strategy employed, and the implementation strategy can be formulated later. “Explorative”, “experimental”, “longitudinal”, “cross sectional” and “descriptive” are the different research designs. This research is based on mixed method research strategy, as the quantitative research is usefull in determining the relationship between two different variables, one variable being an independent variable and another variable being a dependent or outcome variable within a population. And in this study, the researcher aims to study relationship between the social media digital marketing and its impact on consumers in the pharmaceutical industry. As there are two variables and its relationship are being studied. Qualitative research helped to understand how the social media impacts pharmaceutical consumers according the healthcare professionals such as doctors and pharmacist.

4.6.1 Exploratory

Exploratory research is used when the research questions do not give a conclusive or a final solution to the existing problems. Exploratory research is normally conducted when the research problem is not defined and it does not provide conclusive results, but definitely helps to understand research problem in a better way. Besides, it also helps the exploratory researcher, to change the direction of research based on new revelation or information (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Besides, exploratory research design does not provide a answers to the research questions, that is it does not provides conclusive results to the research questions but just explores the topic of research with varying levels of depth. It has been noted that “exploratory research is the initial research, which forms the basis of more conclusive research. It can even help in determining the research design, sampling methodology and data collection method” (Singh, 2007, p.64). Exploratory research “tends to tackle new problems on which little or no previous research has been done” (Brown, 2006, p.64). Exploratory studies are considered as the most common and popular method for collecting primary data for unstructured interviews.

4.6.2 Descriptive

Descriptive research is basically described to various functions and characteristics of phenomenon which are further divided into series of case studies, case series, cross-sectional study, longitudinal study, etc.

4.6.3 Causal

Causal research is normally used for the cause and affect relationships, experimental and quasi-experimental studies are popular research methods employed for causal studies.

4.6.4 Why the selected research design was chosen?

The research design chosen is confirmatory sequence design as the quantitative study unfolds first. Subsequently the qualitative study is performed to better understand the quantitative results obtained. So, the researcher has adopted mixed research strategy and the research approach will be abductive and research design will be confirmatory sequence design.

4.7 Research Approach

Research approaches are of three types that is inductive, deductive and abductive or mixed method research approach.

4.7.1 Deductive

In deductive approach based on a theory that is already existing a hypothesis is developed, and then a research strategy is designed to test the hypothesis, and this is called quantitative research (Ghauri and Grohaug, 2005). A deductive design normally is used to see if there is a relationship between the variables (Gulati, 2009).

Figure 4.3 Deductive approach (Trochim, 2006).

Thus, Babbie (2010) deductive approach begins with some expected patterns which is tested against observations, whereas inductive approach begins with observations and seeks to find a pattern within them

4.7.2 Inductive

As per Hyde (2000, p.83) inductive approach is *“a theory-building process, starting with observations of specific instances, and seeking to establish generalization about the phenomenon under investigation”*. Moreover, in inductive approach, observations are made which later contributes to a theory, but in deductive approach it is opposite, that is it begins with a theory and applies a well-known theory.

Figure 4.4 Inductive Approach (Trochim, 2006).

In Inductive approach the researcher after collecting the data develops a theory which is based on the result. This happens in qualitative type of research.

Moreover, in this research the researcher has adopted the abductive research approach as in this study the research strategy is of mixed method that is the researcher has used both qualitative and quantitative method to collect data.

4.7.3 Mixed method

As per Bazeley,(2010) in mixed method more than one methodological or paradigmatic approach such as qualitative, quantitative, a combination of the two. Researchers are therefore encouraged, to take different approaches which complement each other. The main reasons behind using the mixed method approach are to increase the reach and get maximum information possible.

Figure 4.5 Multiple-Study Mixed Methods Research (Creswell, 2003)

By combining qualitative and quantitative methods and techniques, it is possible to study a wider phenomenon (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003; 2010). Besides this, when the researcher uses both the approach that is quantitative and qualitative to collect data, it allows the

researcher to validate and compare the results of the study, this was noted in some previous studies on similar topic, where both qualitative (Campaniaris, *et al.*, 2011) and quantitative (Singh, *et al.*, (2010) approaches were used for the data collection. Creswell, (2003) has justified the mixed method approach is better as it gives deep and better understanding and of the research problem, but it can be commented that mixed methods research is not easy as it is time consuming to collect and analyse both quantitative and qualitative data using different statistical software. Moreover, in this research the researcher is using the Multiple-Study Mixed Methods Research (Creswell, 2003).

4.8 Data Collection Methods

Data collection method means the method in which the data will be collected, accordingly in this research, the data will be primary data or primary research. As per Walliman (2005) in primary research the primary data is collected by either recording, or observation, with an objective to reach very close to the truth. In this researcher used quantitative data as well qualitative data which was collected using questionnaires which included structured closed ended questions for quantitative and semi-structured questions for qualitative interview. Primary research was preferred over secondary research (Walliman, 2005). Thus, the data collection methods used for this research was through a well-structured questionnaire for quantitative study and semi-structured questionnaire for qualitative study as the data needed for this research is primary data. Moreover, the researcher had also explored various research papers, journals articles, to get secondary data.

For the quantitative research questionnaires were distributed to both male and female who are above 18 years of age, as questionnaires are quick and cheaper and easier and quicker (Kumar, 2005; Veal, 2005) in comparison to interview. The distributed questionnaire took approximate 10-15 minutes to complete. Most of the questionnaire were completed by the participant where both the researcher and the participants were in the same location to avoid any difficulties or confusion, but few participants had asked to email the questionnaire and that they will complete it and send it back. Moreover, completing the questionnaire face to face was done to get high response and to overcome any problems which the respondents may face (William, 2001). Moreover, for the qualitative research the data was collected by the use of semi structured questionnaire and interview was conducted.

Besides, collecting the data for quantitative study through the use of structured questionnaire, the researcher also used semi-structured questionnaire to collect the qualitative data by the way of interview. The doctors and the pharmacist were contacted who were for the interviewed to study their opinion on what impact social media has on the consumer health in the pharmaceutical industry. Accordingly, the doctors and pharmacist were contacted over the phone and emails were sent out to them, besides they were also contacted in their surgery and time was booked interview. Respondents were provided with the consent form and information sheet. Data collection was voluntary, there was no compulsion, and it was entirely on the discretion of the respondents to take part in the research. Once the respondents agree to participate in the study, they were provided the questionnaire, where they gave their opinion by the way of interview. Thus, the primary data was collected.

Secondary data analysis is basically the use of the already existing data which might have been collected for some earlier study (Hinds *et al.*, 1997; Szabo and Strang 1997). Moreover, secondary data analysis is different from systematic reviews and meta-analyses of qualitative studies (Popay *et al.*, 1998). To find the literatures and journal articles various search engines were used such as “EBSCO host, Web of Science and Science Direct, ProQuest” etc. The academic literature and the journal articles were based on “consumer marketing”, “pharmaceutical marketing”, “digital media marketing”, “social media marketing” etc. in an attempt to study the consumers behaviour using social media, social media marketing for pharmaceutical product. Hypothesis was developed based on the secondary data obtained from office of national statistics (ONS). The secondary data from the year 2008 to 2016 was obtained from ONS was based on demography of the UK. This demographic data was analysed using SPSS. The statistical tools used was Pearson correlation.

The second part of the research deals with primary research using data, which was collected using structured questionnaire from the 380 adult consumers above the age of 18 by completing the structured questionnaire. However only 200 observations were valid as some of the participants did not complete the questionnaire fully, and some did not return the completed questionnaire. Moreover, on comparing with the similar research it was found that 200 sample size was adequate to carry on the quantitative analysis. After collecting the data, it was coded, compiled and entered in SPSS which is a statistical software. Further the data was tested for the different test such as descriptive statistics, Spearman’s correlation and Chi Square test, and ordinal regression. After the data was tested for these tests, then it was analysed for the hypothesis.

The next stage was on qualitative studies, wherein the semi-structured questionnaire was drafted, and the data was collected by conducting interviews of the healthcare professionals mainly GPs and pharmacist who expressed their views on how the social media in pharmaceutical industry is impacting the current customers and how will it affect the future customers. The in-depth interview approach was conducted using semi structured questionnaire which contained a set of predetermined questions, and these questionnaire were sent to the doctors and pharmacist who were ready to take part in the study prior to the date of the interview. The interview process took an average of 30 to 45 minutes each. All the interviews were recorded on a digital recorder such as a phone or on Dictaphone and also the contents were written down manually. The next step was to transcribe the interview, which was transcribed manually. After the transcribing the interview the data was analysed using thematic analysis. Moreover, as per McAuley (1999) is of opinion that, handwritten notes help to detect any discrepancies, although the recording was played again and again to understand and transcribe. The handwritten notes do helps in clarifying the any issues and confusion in the recordings. Thus, the qualitative interview had helped the researcher to understand the importance of social media in healthcare and pharmaceutical industry from the prospective of the healthcare professionals. All the interviews were conducted in the English language.

4.8.1 Proposed implementation of sampling plan

The sampling plan is a plan which gives in detail on how the sampling will be carried out. Once the questionnaire is approved the next step will be to get in touch with the people (sample), they can be contacted over the phone and then who can be met in person, besides this they can be met by visiting public library, university library, shopping mall, and super market such as Asda, Tesco etc, then taking an appointment from then as per most suitable time, and then going and meeting them, and giving them the invitation letter consent form and information sheet, if they are happy to take part in the research then hand over to them the questionnaire and ask them to fill it up, and also inform them it will not take more than 10-15 minutes. In case if some people cannot meet face to face in that case take their email add and email them the consent form, information sheet, and the invitation letter. Once they had consented to take part in the research, the questionnaire was emailed, also informing than it will not take more 10-15 minutes. Similarly, for the qualitative research the doctors and pharmacist were contacted over the phone and emails were sent out to them, besides they were

also contacted in their surgery and time was booked interview. Respondents were provided with the consent form and information sheet. Data collection was voluntary, there was no compulsion, and it was entirely on the discretion of the respondents to take part in the research. Once the respondents agree to participate in the study, they were provided the questionnaire, where they give their opinion. Thus, the data was collected.

4.9 Target population

A research population is the total of all the individuals who have certain characteristics that are needed for the research and are of interest to a researcher. As per Barnsbee et al., (2018) target population can be defined as “the target population is the group of individuals that the intervention intends to conduct research in and draw conclusions from”. That is, it’s a big collection of an objects or individuals that are focused by the scientific query, but because it’s a huge or large size the researchers cannot often test each and every individual, as it will be not only very expensive but also time-consuming and. As a result, sampling techniques are normally considered. A research population is basically a well-defined collection of individuals having similar taste and characteristics. The researcher has selected city of Wolverhampton for quantitative study and England for qualitative studies. Wolverhampton has a population of 254,406, out of the population of children is 20%, so the total adult population is 203,525. (Wolverhampton.gov.uk, 2017). The reason for choosing Wolverhampton for the study was There are 49.4% males and 50.6% females in Wolverhampton, which is very similar to the gender distribution in England (49.3% males and 50.7% females), thereby it can be related to the population of England.

4.9.1 Sampling frame

A sampling frame is the group of people from which the researcher will draw the sample. Before a sample is considered, members of study population have to be identified, by making a list called a sampling frame, and each member of sampling frame is called sampling unit. The sampling fraction is the ratio of sample size to study population size. (Etikan, 2016). For this study the sampling frame will be population of Wolverhampton who are the registered citizens with electorate as the sample will be drawn from the population of Wolverhampton. Sampling frame = sample size/ study population.

4.9.2 Sample size

The sample size is the total number of observations that were carried out in the research, moreover there is no exact sample size and can be different in different research settings, but it is said that large sized sample can lead to increased precision in the results (Banerjee, 2010).

4.9.3 Determination of sample size using statistical techniques

Population size:	203525
Confidence level (%):	95
Margin of error (%):	5%
Calculate:	Sample size:384

So, the researcher has calculated the sample size which is 384 respondents having the confidence level of 95% and margin of error is kept as 5%.

4.9.4 How to calculate sample size (SurveyMonkey, 2021)

Sample size can be calculated by use the following formula:

$$\text{Sample Size} = \frac{\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N}\right)}$$

Population Size = N, Margin of error = e . z-score = z Sample size is = 384 participants.

4.9.5 Probability sampling

As per Kothari (2004) probability sampling can also be called as ‘random sampling’ or a ‘chance sampling’, that is in probability sampling every item of the universe has an equal chance of being included in the sample, thus in this method the sample the participants are picked up from the whole group randomly. Thus, it can be said that it is blind chance that determines which item is selected. Moreover, the results or the outcome which is obtained from probability or random sampling can be assured in terms of probability. The researcher can measure the errors of estimation or the significance of results obtained from a random sample. Thus, bringing out the superiority of random sampling design. This is the reason why

random sampling is often considered as the best technique for selecting a representative sample. Thus, probability sampling method is said to be the most reliable method as it eliminates sampling bias as it gives every individual of the population an equal chance of being selected in the research as a participant. It is more accurate as it is representative of the entire population (Banerjee, 2010).

Thus, Probability sampling was used in the quantitative part of the data collection individual were selected randomly from the whole population.

4.9.6 Non-probability sampling

In non-probability sampling, all the individuals or all the members or objects of the population may not be selected for the study, as there is no equal chance of every member of the population to get selected. Moreover, non-probability sampling method is normally useful for only certain types of studies such as “pilot studies”, “case studies”, “qualitative research”, or for the hypothesis development etc, this sampling method does not give the real picture of the problem as it does not consider the entire population. However, this sampling technique is preferred as it is quick cheap and easy (Martínez-Mesa, 2016).

However, in the present study the researcher had used non-probability sampling only for the qualitative study were only certain member of the population were selected that only those people who were associated with pharmaceutical related sector.

4.9.7 Why the chosen sampling technique was chosen?

The researcher used non-probability, convenience sampling for the qualitative studies where all the members of society do not have the equal chance of being selected as the participants were only people from healthcare background, so it was unfeasible or impractical to conduct probability sampling for qualitative studies however for the quantitative studies probability random sampling was used as all the members of the society had equal chances of being selected

4.10 Ethical Considerations

The confidentiality was very important. The participants were informed that this is an academic study and the data will not be supplied to third party. Information sheet and consent form was given to the participant and their consent was taken before asking them to fill the

questionnaire. Besides this, their involvement will be totally voluntary. The participant data (questionnaire in paper form) will be kept very safely. Once the participant data was collected which was in physical form (paper form), it was converted into electronic form, and the paper form was destroyed using a paper shredding machine. This was personally done by me. When the data is converted into electronic form, it will be saved on my laptop which is password protected. Besides this the folder where the data was saved in my laptop was password protected and the password is only known to me as no one else uses my laptop. Moreover, the data collected was used only by me and my research supervisor, which will be passed to my supervisor either by emailing him or using a USB drive. Once the data is transferred to my supervisor, the data will the data from the USB drive will be deleted. After the data is analyzed and presented in a form of results, the electronic data which is saved in my laptop will be deleted by me and also from the recycle bin of my laptop.

4.11 Data Analysis and Interpretation

According to Cassell and Symon (1994, p.24) "*there is no single set of rules for the analysis of data from qualitative research*", only the important thing one needs to be familiar with is to develop a correct analysis. Moreover, while analysing a research problem, it is very important that all the details are considered as analysis is an important component for the research for it to make sense and to achieve the aim and objective of the research and for this all the feedback from the questionnaire should be thoroughly analysed (Jones, 2008). In this case, the analysis was done by the use of statistical software package called SPSS for quantitative study and thematic analysis for qualitative study. The reason for choosing this SPSS software package for the analysing the quantitative data was that it can analysis large volume of data and produces a robust result. Once the data is collected analyzing it is the normally the next step so as to get the answers or the results of the research question. Interpreting and analyzing the data is also equally and very important (Gratton and Jones 2010). The researcher will carry out a quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis, whereby the researcher will be testing the hypothesis. The statistics that will be used are descriptive statistics ordinal regression, spearman's correlation. Furthermore, it also provides the researcher with graphs and tables and descriptive statistics Scott and Mazhindu (2005), which can be easily and quickly interpreted. Analysis of the data will help to find out the consumer perception of digital media marketing in pharmaceutical industry, furthermore it also helps to analyze whether digital media marketing is a suitable marketing in pharmaceutical industry.

The proposed technique for data analysis for the research will be quantitative analysis and qualitative analysis that is mixed method by the use of SPSS software, followed by regression correlation., and also, qualitative analysis by way of thematic analysis. Once the data was collected, it was coded, compiled and analysed using SPSS, so the coded and the compiled data was entered in statistical software for analysis. The primary data which was collected was ordinal data and is more precise form of categorical data. In case of ordinal data, a respondent rates on the Likert scale of 1 to 5 (Blumberg *et al.*, 2008). Further the ordinal data which was collected was tested for “Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient”, “Chi Square Test”, and “ordinal Regression analysis”. For the qualitative data, which was obtained by the interview, the themes were generated and identified and then the thematic analysis was performed. Moreover, before performing the actual analysis, data was checked several times soon after entering the it into SPSS.

4.11.1 Spearman Correlation

According to Kothari (2004) in the early 1900s Spearman’s Correlation coefficient was developed by the statistician Charles Spearman and is denoted by r . Moreover, Spearman’s Correlation is used when the information or data is not in numerical form but in a form, which can just be ranked as first, second, third, and so forth. The value of Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient falls is in between ± 1 , where $+1$ indicates a perfect positive correlation and -1 is perfect negative correlation and all other values of correlation coefficient will show different degrees of correlation. Spearman correlation is used for non-parametric ordinal data.

Accordingly, in this research as non- parametric ordinal data was used, so spearman correlation was used to study the relation between the two variables.

4.11.2 Pearson Correlation

According to Allen (2017), Pearson correlation coefficient also known as Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient denoted by the symbol r is the most common measure of correlation which is been widely used to a study the relationship between two quantitative variables. The coefficient of correlation lies between -1 and +1, which indicates the strength of the relationship between variables. the correlation or the relation between the variables will be weaker if the correlation coefficient is equal to zero and *vice versa*. These two variables can be either interval or ratio and the data has to be parametric data. Pearson correlation was performed to identify the relationship between the variables of the secondary data that was obtained from office national statistics (ONS). The data was parametric, so Pearson's correlation has been employed as the data analysed.

4.11.3 Chi Square test

According to McHugh (2013), Chi-square test is a non-parametric statistical tool which is designed for analysing the differences in the group for measuring the dependent variable is at a nominal level. Moreover, for analysing and comparing the non-parametric data, the Chi-square test is the most robust for studying distribution of the data, besides there is no need of equality of variances in the data. Further it can also be used for evaluating dichotomous and independent variables and multiple group studies. Besides other non-parametric tools and some parametric tools available in statistics, the calculations which are needed to compute the Chi-square test itself provides large amount of information about the performance of the groups in the study. Moreover, one of the important point to be noted of Pearson's Chi-square distribution is that in this statistical methods there was no need of the normal distribution to for interpreting the findings and arriving at the result (Singhal and Rana, 2015). Furthermore, Chi-square test is one of the most significant statistical test, which can be used with a strength statistic. Cramer's V test obtained in the Chi Square test is considered to be the strength test which is used to test the strength of the data when Chi-square test result has been obtained. Chi-square has various advantages such as it is robust and its ease of computation with the distribution of the data, what's more it can be used in studies where parametric assumptions are not met, besides its flexible and its flexibility can be seen as it can handles data from two or more group. As it has advantage it also has certain limitations, the limitation includes

specific sample size, its difficulty in interpreting 20 or more independent or dependent variables, and also its tendency to produce relative low Cramer's V correlation measures, even there is highly significant results (McHugh, 2013). Thus, Chi-square test not only informs about the probability of independence of a distribution of data, if said in simple terms it only tests whether there is any association or relation between the two variables or not, closeness of association or relation between the two variable is informed by Chi Square test (Singhal and Rana, 2015).

As the data was an ordinal data so non-parametric statistical test Chi Square test was used to study the relation between the variables. Moreover, the sampling was random sampling.

4.11.4 Ordinal regression

'Ordinal regression' (OR) or Ordinal logistic regression are two names for the statistical technique they can be called by the names, and is used to predict behaviour of ordinal level of dependent variables with a set of independent variables. The dependent variable is the order response category variable and the independent variable may be categorical or continuous. (Statistics Solutions, 2019). 'ordinal regression' is basically used for predicting an ordinal dependent variable with one two or more independent variables (Statistics.laerd.com, 2018). As per Hassad, (2000) ordinal logistic regression or ordinal regression is robust, flexible, and an interpretable multivariate approach.

Ordinal regression problems are very common in many research areas and have been used as a standard nominal problem leading to non-optimal solutions. These problems pertaining to ordinal regression problems are in mostly between classification and regression, thereby similarities and differences can be presented. In ordinal regression the problems are rated with the values on an ordinal scale. Further it has been noted that in recent years there has been an increased demand of ordinal Regression in the information retrieval community for various reason, one of it can be ordinal Regression is an important approach for ranking, other reason is that ordinal Regression become a natural choice for rating reviews of products and problem thereby receiving an increased attention and interest (Baccianella *et al.*, 2009). Besides being a natural choice there are different ways of using logistic regression, they can be used for predicting group membership and information relating to the strengths and relationships between the various variables, although it also has various advantages and disadvantages. Prank a perceptron approach that generalizes the binary perceptron algorithm to the ordinal multi-class situation, is a fast-online algorithm (Crammer and Singerm, 2002)

4.11.5 Qualitative studies

According to Pathak *et al* (2013) qualitative research is more about understanding a piece of research in a humanistic manner or in an idealistic approach, as in this the researcher tries to understand people's "beliefs", "experiences", "attitudes", "behaviour", and "interactions". Although in qualitative research, non-numerical data generated yet it is recognized to have ability to give voice to the participants by permitting them to share their experiences and enhance their involvement. Thus, it adds a new dimension to interventional studies (Gibson *et al*, 2004). Moreover, qualitative research is divided into three broad categories, they are "Observational studies", "interview studies" and "documentary/textual analyses" of written records. In addition, in qualitative methods, the relationship between the researcher and the participant becomes more closer that is, it's often less formal than in quantitative research (Kalra, Pathak and Jena, 2013). What's more, qualitative research is multimethod approach as the researcher studies things in their natural settings, attempting to make sense of, or interpret. Further, qualitative research can be used in various types of study such as "case study life story", "interview", "observational", "historical", "interactional", and "visual texts", where ever the data available is not in numerical form, this can be used to analyse it (Aspers and Corte, 2019).

Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is used to analysis qualitative data. As per Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, (2016) thematic analysis is a systematic, flexible orderly and logical method to study qualitative data, by coding qualitative data to identify themes. Thus, researcher has used thematic analyses to study the research problem and analyse the data which was collected by carrying out the interview of the healthcare professionals such as doctors and pharmacist. The objective of using thematic analysis was that is helped the researcher to identify the various concepts in the data collected. This section will be all about analysing the findings and discussing the qualitative phase of this research. This step was considered as a very important and crucial step in understanding the viewpoint of the participants in this case the healthcare profession and social media is impacting the customers. In Qualitative approach the interview was carried out than this interview was transcribed manually, and then thematic analysis was carried out. In the qualitative study, the data is broken into pieces so as to get them into categories, and in the thematic analysis the transcribed data is coded, as the coding permits the condensation of the data into categories (Maxwell, 2005). Data analysis is a

process which involves “reading” and “re-reading”, “assessing”, and “re-assessing”, the transcripts many times so to ensure that correct transcriptions was done. The transcription was done manually by hearing the recording many times. The next step was to work on identifying codes and categories, so as to get the themes. Coding is defined as “*assigning tags or labels to the data, based on the concept of the study*” (Coffey and Atkinson 1996, p. 26). Thus, to ensure reliability each interview transcripts were coded manually (Dariau *et al.*, 2007). Once the data was coded, themes were prepared. Once the data was transcribed, it was organised into sections so as in order to identify the interviews.

As per Braun and Clarke (2006) model, there are six steps for thematic analysis, these six stages are explained below:

Stage I: Data familiarisation: During the process of transcription the researcher get familiar to the data and this is called data familiarisation. The process involves careful reading of the transcribed data again and again to understand the information identify and form patterns (Bazeley, 2009). Besides this data familiarisation can be also done by carefully listening the recordings.

stage II: Initial code generation: after the data familiarisation stage, the stage is initial codes generation, which is based on the key elements of the research questions. Moreover, Williams *et al.* (1990) feels that in order to add more themes and sub-themes the researchers should get it from literature review and as they reach the analysis stage.

Stage III: Searching themes: the next stage is based on searching for the themes. This involves identifying and examining each and every case individually so as to identify patterns in each transcript so as to discover relevant themes.

Stage IV: Reviewing the themes: Initial codes were identified and reviewed, to form new sets of codes, which was then carefully checked for its applicability to the entire data set.

Stage V: defining and labelling the theme: this stage deals with the process of developing sub-themes, which have to be well-defined and labelled, have to be reported from this stage.

Stage VI: Writing the Report: next stage deals with report writing, which is based on the thematic analysis protocol. Besides in this stage sentences or words phrases which the interviewees used have been quoted verbatim.

Diagrammatic representation of data coding process:

Figure 4.6 Diagrammatic representation of data coding process (developed by the researcher)

4.12 Validity and Reliability

Reliability of the study can be referred to the extent or to degree to which the same answers are obtained using the same instruments when used multiple time. Thus, in other words, if the research is highly reliability, its only then other researchers will be able to generate the same results under similar conditions and using the same research methods. According to Babbie,(2010, p.158)“reliability problems crop up in many forms. Moreover, reliability is a concern every time a single observer is the source of data because there is no certain guard against the impact of that observer’s subjectivity”. Furthermore, reliability issues can also be related to subjectivity, so it can be said that subjective approach should not be adopted otherwise it can be said that the reliability can be compromised, but validity of research can be found or calculated using scientific research method and can be found during the generation of research findings (Wilson, 2010). Besides this Oliver (2010) is of the view that validity is mandatory for all types of studies. As per Cohen et al (2007) “content validity”, “criterion-related validity”, “construct validity”, “internal validity”, “external validity”, “concurrent validity” and “face validity” are the different forms of research validity. Furthermore, validity of a research should include time scale but it’s not mandatory. Although threats to research reliability and validity can never be eliminated, but the researchers try to minimize it as much as possible.

4.13 Limitations and how they have been overcome

It is for sure that the research does have some limitations. However, it is critically important to minimize the limitations throughout the research process. The limitations can be range from research aims and objectives that are too broadly, or method of data collection. Limitation can

also be because of too small sample size, as the statistical tests cannot identify significant relationships within data set. Besides this there are not much lack of previous studies in the chosen research area. So, getting the information from the literature was very difficult. Getting an appointment from the healthcare professional to carry out the interview for the qualitative interview was very difficult, however with the help of the contacts of friends and through social media got in touch with the healthcare professionals took their appointment and emailed them the questionnaire and depending upon their convenience either took a face to face interview or on skype.

4.14 Research Process in diagrammatic representation

Figure 4.7 Research Process (developed by the researcher)

4.15 Chapter summary

This chapter was on the research methodology, providing a blueprint on how to conduct a research by following an appropriate methodology, so as to resolve the research questions formulated in the chapter one. This chapter also gives the information on what research philosophy is, research design, research approach, sample size, sampling frame, limitation of the research, validity, ethical approval, data analysis, data collection etc. As a mixed method, it will focus on collecting, analysing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in a multiple study. The study will use the combination of quantitative and qualitative approaches for understand research problems properly. This research will be carried out in a systematic manner so as to resolve the research problems which will lead to the contribution of the research and implications of the research to the managers.

5 CHAPTER FIVE: FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter describes the findings of research. The findings relate are based on the research questions, data was analysed to identify, describe and explore the relationship between the variables. Primary data was collected by using the self-administered questionnaires and interviews in a mixed method. The study included the analysis of “descriptive statistics” which was later presented in table and in graphical format representing measurements of “percentages”, “frequencies”, “mean”, “standard deviation”. Moreover, this chapter is divided into two sub-sections that is quantitative studies and qualitative studies, quantitative studies is further divided into two sections secondary data analysis and primary data analysis. Secondary data was obtained from journals and government website whereas the primary data was collected by the way of interview and using structured and semi-structured questionnaire for the qualitative quantitative studies. The quantitative data collected was analysed using SPSS that is the statistical software for descriptive statistics, (mean, standard deviation, graphs, charts and tables) spearman’s correlation, ordinal regression and Chi square. The results were presented in tables and graphs. The descriptive statistics used in the study were frequency distribution and cross-tabulation. The objective of the frequency statistics was to find out the frequency the regularity or at what interval a variable occurred. To present the information tables and bar charts were used, besides all questions in the questionnaire were examined. Correlation relationship testing between two variables was performed using Spearman’s correlation to test the relationship between two different variables. The data was collected t by using a simple random sampling method. The structured and semi- structured questionnaire was prepared, with various types of questions in it. Semi-structured questionnaire was used for qualitative studies and structured questionnaire was used for quantitative studies. The questionnaire which was being used for the quantitative studies had five-point Likert scale question type wherein 1 was “strongly disagree” and 5 was “strongly agree” for measuring the variables.

After quantitative analysis qualitative analysis was also performed in the study as mixed method was adopted in the study. The data was collected by interviewing the healthcare professionals by the way of the semi-structured questionnaire and later the data was analysed.

5.2 Secondary Data Analysis

5.2.1 Pearson correlation

1. Hypothesis-1 Relation between of income and internet user

If income impacts the respondent to use internet user, that means income and internet usage are related. Thus, the hypothesis will be:

H1- Relation between income and internet use.

Table 5.1: Pearson correlation: Relation between income and internet user.

Correlations			
income	Pearson Correlation	income	Internet user
	Sig. (2-tailed)	1	.904**
	N	10	10
Internet user	Pearson Correlation	.904**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	10	10

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.1: Simple Scatter Fit of Internet User and Income

The Pearson Value as per Table 5.1 is .904 which is lesser than, showing that income and internet use is relate, moreover, as seen from the scatter chart (Fig 5.1) the relation is positive and a linear.

2. Hypothesis-2 Relations between Impact of income on internet shopping

If internet shopping depends on the income of the user, then internet shopping is related to income. The hypothesis will be:

H1- Relation between internet shopping and income.

Table 5.2: Pearson correlation of internet shopping and income

Correlations			
		income	Internet shopping
income	Pearson Correlation	1	.880**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	10	10
Internet shopping	Pearson Correlation	.880**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	10	10

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.2: simple scatter with fit line of income and internet shopping

The Pearson Value as per Table 5.2 is 0.88 which is lesser than, showing that income and internet use is relate, moreover, as seen from the scatter chart (Fig 5.2) the relation is positive and a linear.

3. Hypothesis3: Relation between internet shopping and internet user

H1- Impact of Internet user on internet shopping

Table 5.3: Pearson correlation between internet shopping and internet user

Correlations			
		internet shopping	internet user
internet shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.995**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	10	10
internet user	Pearson Correlation	.995**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	10	10

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.3: Simple scatter with line of fit between internet user and internet shopping

The Pearson Value as per Table 5.3 is .995 which is lesser than, showing that income and internet use is relate, moreover, as seen from the scatter chart (Fig 5.3) the relation is positive and a linear.

4. Hypothesis4: Relationship between social media users and internet shopping

H1- Impact of social media user on internet shopping

Table 5.4: Pearson Correlations: Relationship internet shopping and social media user

Correlations			
		internet shopping	Social media user
internet shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.969**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	10	10
Social media user	Pearson Correlation	.969**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	10	10

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.4: Simple scatter with line of fit between internet shopping and social media user

The Pearson Value as per Table 5.4 is .969 which is lesser than, showing that income and internet use is relate, moreover, as seen from the scatter chart (Fig 5.4) the relation is positive and a linear.

5. Hypothesis-5: Relation between internet shopper and purchase of over the counter medicine on the internet

The hypothesis is:

H1- impact on internet shopper and purchase of over the counter medicine on the internet

Table 5.5: Pearson correlation: Internet shopper and purchase of over the counter medicine on the internet

Correlations			
		Internet shopping	Online med purch
Internet shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.987**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.002
	N	5	5
Online med purchase	Pearson Correlation	.987**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	
	N	5	5

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5.5: Simple scatter fit of online medicine purchase by internet shopping

The Pearson Value as per Table 5.5 is .987 which is lesser than, showing that income and internet use is relate, moreover, as seen from the scatter chart (Fig 5.5) the relation is positive and a linear.

5.2.2 Findings from secondary data

On analysing the demographic data (secondary data) of UK obtained from Office of National Statistics (ONS), it was found that people who use internet are high income, social media users, also do online shopping. furthermore, it was found that online shoppers also purchased medicine through the online pharmacy. This study showed that social media can makes shopping easy, retrieving information easy, but in pharmaceutical industry using information from social media is risky and should be used with precaution. Furthermore, secondary data was obtained from UK ONS was tested for Pearson correlation using statistical software package (SPSS), the findings were that internet shoppers also purchase medicines from internet shops and online pharmacy. According to the secondary data the people who used internet regularly also be using the social media, also purchased products and services online including medicine and pharmaceutical over the counter products. The study has shown various that purchasing medicine from online source is potentially risky. The researcher had retrieved secondary data on internet users, online pharmacies users from (ONS) Office of National Statistic, using SPSS Pearson Correlation test was performed. Accordingly, there was a linear relationship between online shoppers and purchasers of over the counter medicine online. Besides this the hypothesis were developed and the findings are below.

5.3 Primary data analysis

5.3.1 Primary data: Quantitative Study

In order to understand why the customers purchased over the counter medicines based on the information obtained from in social media from online pharmacy, questionnaires were prepared and distributed to 384 people above the age of 18 and to both the gender. But only 200 people have responded and completed the questionnaires.

5.3.2 Descriptive statistics:

Table 5.1: Age of the respondents

AGE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-29 years old	99	49.5	49.5	49.5
	30-39 years old	63	31.5	31.5	81.0
	40-49 years old	30	15.0	15.0	96.0
	50 years and above	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.1: Age of the respondents

Figure 5.1 is all about the age of the respondents. That's is there were 200 respondents out of which about 50% of the respondents were in the age bracket of 18 to 29 years old, and 31% the respondents were in the age group of 30 to 39, however 15% of the respondents were in between 40 to 49 years of age. Furthermore, the respondents who were about 50 years of age were only 4%. Thus, this study demographically is of the young people who are the major users of the internet and social media. And this age group will reflect on what they think

Table 5.2: Gender of the respondents

GENDER					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	115	57.5	57.5	57.5
	Female	85	42.5	42.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.2: Gender of the respondents

Figure 5.2 is a pie chart which gives the gender of the respondents who had taken part in the survey. Accordingly, 42.5% of the respondents were female, and 57.5% were male. Thus, the major respondents were male.

Table 5.3: Weekly disposable income

DISPOSABLE INCOME					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	29	14.5	14.5	14.5
	2	46	23.0	23.0	37.5
	3	55	27.5	27.5	65.0
	4	35	17.5	17.5	82.5
	5	35	17.5	17.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.3: Weekly disposable income

Figure 5.3 is all about the weekly disposable income of the respondents. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 17% of the respondents had weekly disposable income above £200 so it can be judged that these people must be the one who might be full time employed. However, the next 17.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income was in between £155-199. Further 27.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income was in between £100-149, besides, 23% of the respondents had weekly disposable income was in between £50-199, last but not the least last 14.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income was less than £49. This shows that the major respondent of the survey were the people who had weekly disposable income less than £200.

Figure 5.4: Employment status of the respondent

Table 5.4: Employment status of the respondent

EMPLOYMENT STATUS					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Employed Full time	74	37.0	37.0	37.0
	Employed Part time	38	19.0	19.0	56.0
	Self-employed	12	6.0	6.0	62.0
	unemployed	6	3.0	3.0	65.0
	Student	70	35.0	35.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.4 is all about the employment status of the respondents. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 37% of the respondents were full time employed, and 35% of the respondents were students. Besides this 19% of the respondents were part time employed. So, it can be judged that these people must be the one who might be full time employed. However, the next 17.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income been in between £155-199. Further 27.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income been in between £100-149, besides, 23% of the respondents had weekly disposable income been in between £50-199, last but not the least last 14.5% of the respondents had weekly disposable income was less than £49. This shows that the major respondent of the survey were the people who had weekly disposable income less than £200.

Figure 5.5: Does the respondent use Internet

Table 5.5: Does the respondent use Internet

USE INTERNET					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Sometimes	10	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Often uses internet	61	30.5	30.5	35.5
	Always	129	64.5	64.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.5 is all about respondents who use internet. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 65% of the respondents always use internet, however 30% of the respondents use it often, besides this 5% of the respondents used internet sometimes. Thus, it can be judged that the majority of the respondents always use internet. Thus, this shows that the major respondent of the survey were the people who used internet very regularly.

Figure 5.6: Number of respondents using social media

Table 5.6: Number of respondents using social media

USE SOCIAL MEDIA					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Occasionally	51	25.5	25.5	29.0
	Sometimes	72	36.0	36.0	65.0
	Often	51	25.5	25.5	90.5
	Always	19	9.5	9.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.6 is all about the number of respondents using social media. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 9.5% of the respondents always use social media; however, 25.5% of the respondents were using it often. Besides this 36% of the respondents stated that they used social media sometimes. Besides it was also noted that almost 25.5% used it occasionally, last but not the least it was seen that there were 3.5% of the respondents who did never used social media. Thus, it was noted that almost 25% of the respondents were either occasionally using the social media and the next 25% were often users of the social media.

Figure 5.7: Number of respondents using Internet marketing

Table 5.7: Number of respondents using Internet marketing

USES INTERNET MARKETING					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	8	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Occasionally	48	24.0	24.0	28.0
	Sometimes	66	33.0	33.0	61.0
	Often	54	27.0	27.0	88.0
	Always	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.7 is based on the respondents who were using internet marketing. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 33% of the respondents used internet marketing sometimes, whereas 27% of the respondents often used the internet marketing. Besides this 37% of the respondents were using internet marketing sometimes. So, it can be judged that these 37% form the group of people who are using the internet marketing maximum. However, the next 12.5% of the respondents always use internet marketing so it can be concluded that only one fifth of the respondents are the regular users of internet marketing. Further 27.5% of the respondents use internet marketing often, besides, 24% of the respondents were using the internet marketing on and off, however there were about 4% of the respondents who never used internet marketing. This shows that the major respondent of the survey was using the internet marketing sometimes.

Figure 5.8: Number of respondents using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users

Table 5.8: Number of respondents using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	14	7.0	7.0	7.0
	Occasionally	59	29.5	29.5	36.5
	Sometimes	59	29.5	29.5	66.0
	Often	40	20.0	20.0	86.0
	Always	28	14.0	14.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.8 is all about the number of respondents using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 30% of the respondents were sometimes using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users, and 20% of the respondents were sometimes using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users. Besides this 14% of the respondents were always using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users. Whereas it was also found that about 7% of the respondents never used social media to get the feedback about a product from other users, and almost 30% of the respondents were occasionally using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users. Thus, it was concluded that 14% of the respondents were very regular user of social media to get the feedback about a product from other users, whereas 7% of the respondents were not at all using social media to get the feedback about a product from other users

Figure 5.9: Respondents using social media for product information

Table 5.9: Respondents using social media for product information

USE SOCIAL MEDIA FOR PROUCT INFORMATION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	31	15.5	15.5	15.5
	Occasionally	61	30.5	30.5	46.0
	Sometimes	64	32.0	32.0	78.0
	Often	31	15.5	15.5	93.5
	Always	13	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.9 is all about the employment Respondents using social media for product information. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 32% of the respondents were sometimes using social media for product information, whereas 15% of the respondents often were using social media for product information. Besides this 9% of the respondents always using social media for product information. However, the next 30.5% of the respondents were occasionally using social media for product information. Whereas 15.5% of the respondents never were using social media for product information.

Figure 5.10: Do the respondents search for the healthcare relating information on the company website?

Table 5.10: Do the respondents search for the healthcare relating information on the company website?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	4	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Occasionally	23	11.5	11.5	13.5
	Sometimes	101	50.5	50.5	64.0
	Often	48	24.0	24.0	88.0
	Always	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.10 is all about the respondents search the company website for the healthcare relating information. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 50% of the respondents sometimes used and searched the company website for the healthcare relating information. However, 24% of the respondents were often searched the company website for the healthcare relating information. Whereas 12% of the respondents said they always searched the company website for the healthcare relating information. Besides there was one class of respondents which never searched the company website for the healthcare relating information they were about 2%. Last but not the least 11.5% occasionally searched the company website for the healthcare relating information

Figure 5.11: Do the respondents search information relate to the healthcare product on the Wikipedia?

Table 5.11: Figure11 Respondent Search Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia

SEARCH WIKIPEDIA TO FIND OUT HEALTHCARE PRODUCT INFORMATION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never use	2	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Occasionally	34	17.0	17.0	18.0
	Sometimes	122	61.0	61.0	79.0
	Often	39	19.5	19.5	98.5
	Always	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.11 is all about Respondent Search Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 61% of the respondents Respondent Search Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia, however 19.5% of the respondents often searched on Wikipedia whereas 1.5% of the respondents always searched Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia. Whereas 1% of the Respondent never Search Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia and 17% of the respondent sometimes search Information Relating to the Healthcare Product on the Wikipedia

Figure 5.12: Do the respondents search information about the medicine on the social media?

Table 5.12: Respondents search information about the medicine on the social media

SEARCH INFORMATION ABOUT MEDICINE ON THE SOCIAL MEDIA					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Occasionally	26	13.0	13.0	16.5
	Sometimes	93	46.5	46.5	63.0
	Often	61	30.5	30.5	93.5
	Always	13	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.12 is all about the respondent searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 46.5% of the respondents were searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media a, however 30.5% of respondent often searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media whereas 6.5% of the respondents always respondent searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media. Whereas 3.5% of the respondent was never searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media however, 13% of the respondents sometimes were searching information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media

Figure 5.13: Does the respondent search information on the internet about the adverse drug reaction?

Table 5.13: Respondent search information on the internet about the adverse drug reaction

SEARCH FOR INFORMATION ON MEDICINE SUCH AS ADVERSE DRUG REACTION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	occasionally	57	28.5	28.5	32.0
	Often	132	66.0	66.0	98.0
	sometimes	4	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.13 is all about the respondents' search information on the internet about the adverse drug reaction. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 66% of the respondents often search information on the internet about the adverse drug on the social media; however, 2% of respondent sometimes search information on the internet about the adverse drug on social media, whereas 28.5% of the respondents often search information on the internet about the adverse drug on the social media, whereas 3.5% of the respondent were never searching information about the adverse drug on the social media.

Figure 5.14: Does the respondent search about the disease online?

Table 5.14: Does the respondent search about the disease online?

SEARCH INFORMATION ABOUT DISEASE ONLINE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Occasionally	34	17.0	17.0	20.5
	Often	112	56.0	56.0	76.5
	Sometimes	42	21.0	21.0	97.5
	Always	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.14 is all about the respondents who searched about the disease internet or online. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 56% of the respondents were often searching information disease on internet or online or on the social media; however, 21% of respondent sometimes were searching information relating to disease on the social media whereas 2% of the respondents were always searching information disease on the social media. Whereas 3.5% of the respondent were never searching information relating to disease on the social media however, 17% of the respondent sometimes were sometimes searching information relating to disease on the social media.

Figure 5.15: Do the respondent search information on disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor.

Table 5.15: Do the respondent search information on disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor.

SEARCH INFORMATION ON DISEASE OR PROBABLE MEDICINE BEFORE VISITING THE GP					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	2	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Occasionally	28	14.0	14.0	15.0
	Sometimes	80	40.0	40.0	55.0
	Often	45	22.5	22.5	77.5
	Always	45	22.5	22.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.15 is all about the respondents who search information on disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 40% of the respondents were sometimes searching information disease on internet or online or on the social media before visiting the doctors; however, 22% of respondent were often searching information relating to disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor on the social media whereas 22% of the respondents were always searching information disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor on the social media. Whereas 14% of the respondent were occasionally searching information relating to disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor on the social media however, 1% of the respondent sometimes were never searching information relating to disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor on the social media.

Figure 5.16: Respondent’s perception of the safety of information given on the social media relating to the healthcare related product

Table 5.16: Respondent’s perception of the safety of information given on the social media relating to the healthcare related product

SAFETY OF INFORMATION GIVEN ON THE SOCIAL MEDIA					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not very safe	28	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Not safe	72	36.0	36.0	50.0
	Neither safe nor not safe	80	40.0	40.0	90.0
	Safe	20	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.16 is all about the Respondent’s perception of the safety of information given on the social media relating to the healthcare related product. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 36% of the respondents believed that information relating disease, or medicine given on the social media was not safe; however, 40% of respondent were of no specific opinion whereas 10% of the respondents believed the information given on the social media relating to disease of medicine was very safe. Whereas 14% of the respondent believed the information relating to disease based on symptoms or probable medicine is not very safe.

Figure 5.17: Do the respondent purchase healthcare related product or medicine from online pharmacy

Table 5.17: Do the respondent purchase healthcare related product or medicine from online pharmacy

PURCHASE THE MEDICINE THROUGH THE ONLINE PHARMACY					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	48	24.0	24.0	32.0
	neither Agree nor disagree	101	50.5	50.5	82.5
	Agree	32	16.0	16.0	98.5
	Strongly Agree	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total		200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.17 is all about the respondents who purchase healthcare related product or medicine from online pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 50% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media; however, 16% of respondent agreed about product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media whereas 1.5% of the respondents strongly about product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media, whereas 6% of the respondent were strongly disagreed about product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media.

Figure 5.18: Is price the reason for buying the medicines or healthcare product from online pharmacy

Table 5.18: Is price the reason for buying the medicines or healthcare product from online pharmacy

REASONFOR BUYING ONLINE- PRICE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	88	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Disagree	80	40.0	40.0	84.0
	neither agree nor Disagree	24	12.0	12.0	96.0
	Agree	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.18 is all about the respondents who felt price the reason for buying the over the counter drugs or medicines from online or internet pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 12% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about price for buying pharmaceutical products from social media; however, 4% of respondent agreed that price can be a main reason for buying over the counter medicine from social media or internet pharmacy, whereas 40% of the respondents disagreed that price can product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media. Whereas 40% of the respondent was strongly disagreed that price can be main reason for buying over the counter drugs from internet or online pharmacy or social media.

Table 5.19: Is convenience the major reason for buying the medicine or healthcare related product from online pharmacy?

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -CONVENIENCE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	33	16.5	16.5	24.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	83	41.5	41.5	66.0
	Agree	44	22.0	22.0	88.0
	Strongly agree	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.19: Is convenience the major reason for buying the medicine or healthcare related product from online pharmacy?

Figure 5.19 is all about the respondents who feel convenience the major reason for buying the over the counter non-prescription drugs from the online or internet pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 41% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about convenience for buying medical products from / online / internet pharmacy or social media, however 22% of respondent agreed that convenience for buying about over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or social media, whereas 12% of respondent strongly agreed that convenience can be a main reason for buying over the counter medical products from internet pharmacy or social media, whereas 16% of the respondents disagreed that convenience can reason for buying pharmaceutical related product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media. Whereas 8% of the respondent was strongly disagreed that convenience to be the reason for buying medical product or from online / internet pharmacy or social media.

Table 5.20: Do the respondents by choice buy the medicine or related products from online pharmacy?

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -CHOICE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	15	7.5	7.5	7.5
	Disagree	76	38.0	38.0	45.5
	neither agree nor disagree	88	44.0	44.0	89.5
	Agree	18	9.0	9.0	98.5
	Strongly agree	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.20: Do the respondents by choice buy the medicine or related products from online pharmacy?

Figure 5.20 is all about those respondents who feel that it's an individual's choice buy the over the counter non-prescription drugs from the online or internet pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 44% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about choice to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy, however 9% of respondent agreed that choice was the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy, whereas 1.5% of respondent strongly agreed that choice can be a main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy, whereas 30% of the respondents disagreed that choice can reason for buying pharmaceutical related product or medicine buying from online pharmacy or social media. Whereas 8% of the respondents were strongly disagreed that choice can be main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from internet or online pharmacy.

Table 5.21: Does being anonymous the main reason for buying from online pharmacy

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -ANONYMITY					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	6.0	6.0	6.0
	disagree	57	28.5	28.5	34.5
	neither agree nor disagree	85	42.5	42.5	77.0
	Agree	41	20.5	20.5	97.5
	Strongly agree	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.21: Does being anonymous the main reason for buying from online pharmacy

Figure 5.21 is all about those respondents who feel that being anonymous the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs from internet pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 43% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about anonymity being the reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from internet pharmacy; however, 20% of respondent agreed that anonymity can be a main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media, whereas 2.5% of respondent strongly agreed that anonymity can be a main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media, whereas 28% of the respondents disagreed that anonymity can be the reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media. Whereas 6% of the respondents were strongly disagreed that

anonymity can be main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media.

Table 5.22: Is the information given by the patient’s online pharmacy or social media secured?

IS THE INFORMATION SECURED					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	67	33.5	33.5	33.5
	Disagree	67	33.5	33.5	67.0
	neither agree nor disagree	52	26.0	26.0	93.0
	Agree	14	7.0	7.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.22: Is the information given by the patient’s online pharmacy or social media secured?

Figure 5.22 is all about information given by the patients’ online pharmacy or social media secured. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 26% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed that the information given by the patients’ on the online pharmacy or social media secured online pharmacy or social media; however, 7% of respondent agreed that the information given by the patients’ on the online pharmacy or social media is secured, whereas 33% of respondent disagreed that the information given by the patients’ on the online pharmacy or social media secured, whereas 33% of the respondents strongly disagreed that the information given by the patients on the online pharmacy or social media is secured.

Table 5.23: Is the respondent aware of the risk associated with buying healthcare products from online pharmacy?

AWARE OF THE RISK WHICH ARE ASSOCAITED WITH ONLINE PURCHASE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	37	18.5	18.5	18.5
	Disagree	70	35.0	35.0	53.5
	neither agree nor disagree	77	38.5	38.5	92.0
	Agree	16	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.23: Is the respondent aware of the risk associated with buying healthcare products from online pharmacy?

Figure 5.23 is all about those respondents who feel one must be aware of the risk associated with buying over the counter healthcare products such as medicines from online or internet pharmacy. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 38.5% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about risk associated with the risk that can be associate with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media; however, 8% of respondent agreed about risk associated with the risk that can be associate with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media, whereas 35% of respondent disagreed that about risk associated with the risk that can be associate with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media. whereas 18% of the respondents strongly disagreed that about risk associated with the risk that can be associate with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media.

Table 5.24: There might be additional charges when buying from online pharmacy

ADDITIONAL CHARGES					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	100	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Disagree	24	12.0	12.0	62.0
	neither agree nor disagree	76	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.24: There might be additional charges when buying from online pharmacy

Figure 5.24 is all about the employment status of the respondents. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 38.5% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed about additional charges as risk factor that can be associate with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media; however, 12% of respondent disagreed about additional charges as a risk factor associated with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media, whereas 50% of respondent strongly disagreed that about additional charges as a risk factor associated with buying the pharmaceutical products from online pharmacy or social media.

Figure 5.25: Is the respondent aware that the person giving information or prescription on the online pharmacy may or may not be genuine?

Table 5.25: Is the respondent aware that the person giving information or prescription on the online pharmacy may or may not be genuine?

PERSON GIVING THE INFORMATION AND PRESCRIPTION GENUINE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Disagree	15	7.5	7.5	11.0
	neither agree nor disagree	138	69.0	69.0	80.0
	Agree	19	9.5	9.5	89.5
	Strongly agree	21	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.25 is all about the employment status of the respondents. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 69% of the respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed that the people giving a prescription or information on the social media is genuine or not, however 10% of respondent agreed that the people giving a prescription or information on the social media is genuine or not, whereas 10.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that the people giving a prescription or information on the social media is genuine or not, whereas 7% of respondent disagreed that the person who is giving the information or prescription social media is genuine or not. 3.5% of the respondents strongly disagreed about the person who is giving the information or prescription social media is genuine or not.

Figure 5.26: Does the respondent use the healthcare app?

Table 5.26: Does the respondent use the healthcare app?

RESPONDENT USES THE HEALTHCARE APP					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	9	4.5	4.5	4.5
	Occasionally	68	34.0	34.0	38.5
	Sometimes	86	43.0	43.0	81.5
	Often	31	15.5	15.5	97.0
	Always	6	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.26 is all about the employment status of the respondents. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 43% of the respondents were sometimes using the using healthcare app. Besides this 15% of the respondents were often using healthcare app, whereas 3% were always using healthcare app. However, there were a class of respondents that is 34% of the respondents' occasionally using healthcare app. Last but not the least 4.5% of the respondents never used the healthcare app.

Figure 5.27: Is the respondent satisfied with social media in healthcare related product?

Table 5.27: Is the respondent satisfied with social media in healthcare related product?

SATISFIED WITH DIGITAL MEDIA IN HEALTHCARE RELATED PRODUCT					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	44	22.0	22.0	30.0
	neither agree nor disagree	79	39.5	39.5	69.5
	Agree	45	22.5	22.5	92.0
	Strongly agree	16	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5.27 is all about the level of satisfaction derived by using social media / digital media in healthcare related product. Accordingly, it can be noted that about 40% of the respondents, respondents were neither agreed nor disagreed whether they were satisfied with the social media / digital media in healthcare related product. Besides this 22% of the respondents were satisfied by using social media / digital media in healthcare related product, whereas 8% were highly satisfied by using social media / digital media in healthcare related product. However, there were a class of respondents that is 22% of the respondents disagreed level of satisfaction derived by using social media / digital media in healthcare related product. Last but not the least 8% of the respondents strongly disagree level of satisfaction derived by using social media /digital media in healthcare related product. Thus, it can be inferred that everyone has an individual choice and taste.

5.3.3 NON-PARAMETRIC CORRELATION: SPEARMAN’S CORRELATION

The primary data collected was ordinal in nature so was tested for Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient, which is a non-parametric test.

Hypothesis 1: Relation between age and purchase of medicine /related product internet or online pharmacy

The hypothesis will be:

H1- Age is related to purchase of medicine from online/ internet pharmacy.

Table 5.28: Spearman’s Correlation: relation between age and purchaser of over the counter medicine from online pharmacy

Correlations			Age	Purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation coefficient	1.00	.603**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy	Correlation coefficient	.603**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As the value of Spearman correlation is less than 1 that is it is .603, this result shows that age and searching healthcare information from the internet related. Besides this it can be observed that the relation between the two is positive significant and strong.

Hypothesis 2: Relation between age and convenience for buying over the counter medicine from online or internet pharmacy.

Is age and convenience related for buying over the counter medicine from online or internet pharmacy. That means that if age has an impact on convenience, then the hypothesis will be: H1- age is related to convenience.

Table 5.29: Spearman's correlation: Association between age and convenience for buying over the counter medicine from online pharmacy.

Correlations				
			Age	Reason for buying online convenience
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.304**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Reason for buying online - convenience	Correlation coefficient	.304**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Spearman correlation is 0.304 (table 5.29) which is less than 1, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected which says there is no relation between age and convenience, thus the result shows that age and convenience have positive and strong relationship.

Hypothesis 3: Relation between age and price.

The hypothesis is:

H1- age has an impact on price.

Table 5.30: Spearman's correlation: relationship between age and price for buy over the counter medicine from online pharmacy

Correlations				
			Age	Reason for buying online-price
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.162*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.022
		N	200	200
	Reason for buying online-price	Correlation coefficient	.162*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.022	.
		N	200	200

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Spearman correlation is 0.162 (table 5.30) which is less than 1, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected which says there is no relation between age and price, thus the result shows that age and price have positive and strong relationship.

Hypothesis 4: Relation between age and choice.

The hypothesis is:

H1- age has impact on choice of the buyer

Table 5.31: Spearman’s correlation: relationship between age and choice for buying over the counter medicine from online pharmacy

Correlations				
			Age	Reason for buying online - choice
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.208**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.003
		N	200	200
	Reason for buying online - choice	Correlation coefficient	.208**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.003	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Spearman correlation is 0.208 (table 5.31) which is less than 1, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected which says there is no relation between age and choice, thus the result shows that age and choice have positive and strong relationship.

Hypothesis 5: relationship between age and scores of various factors for purchasing from online/internet pharmacy.

The hypothesis is:

H1- age has an impact on scores of various factors for purchasing from online/internet pharmacy

Table 5.32: Spearman’s correlation: Relation between age and cumulative scores for buying over the counter medicines from online / internet store..

Correlations				
			Age	cumulative scores of reasons of buying online
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.00	.277**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	cumulative scores of reasons of buying online	Correlation Coefficient	.277**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Spearman correlation is 0.277 (table 5.32) which is less than 1, indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected which says there is no relation between age and scores of various cumulative factors for buying over the counter medicines from online / internet store, also the result shows a positive and strong relationship.

Hypothesis 6: Relation between age and information security

The hypothesis is:

H1- relation age and Information security.

Table 5.33: Spearman’s correlation: Relation between age and information

security of the patient who is buying over the counter medicine from online pharmacy

Correlations				
			Age	Information Security
Spearman's Rho	Age	Correlation	1.000	-.173*
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-Tailed)	.	.015
	Information Security	Correlation	-.173*	1.000
		Coefficient		
		Sig. (2-Tailed)	.015	.
		N	200	200

*. Correlation Is Significant At The 0.05 Level (2-Tailed).

Spearman correlation in this case is -.173 (table 5.33) which is less than 1, indicating age has impact on information security as a risk factor, there is a significant negative but a strong relationship between the age and information security.

Hypothesis-7

Relation between ages on healthcare information from the internet

Does age have an Impact from getting healthcare information from the internet? If age has significant impact on healthcare information from the internet, then it can be said that age, is responsible for the healthcare information from the internet. To find out the impact of age and healthcare information from the internet

The hypothesis will be:

H1 – age has impact on searching healthcare related information from the internet

Table 5.34: age has impact on searching healthcare related information from the internet

Correlations				
			Age	Search healthcare information on the internet
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.503**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Search healthcare information on the internet	Correlation Coefficient	.503**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As the value of Spearman correlation is less than 1 that is it is .503 indicating the null hypothesis can be rejected, thus age has no relation on searching healthcare information from the internet, this result shows that age and searching healthcare information from the internet related. Besides this it can be observed that the relation between the two is positive significant and strong.

Hypothesis 8

Relation between age and their healthcare app usage

Does age have an Impact from using healthcare app?

If age has significant impact on using the healthcare app, then it can be said that age, is responsible for the using the healthcare app. To find out the relationship between the age of the respondent and does he use healthcare app. The hypothesis will be:

H1 – Age has impact on using healthcare app.

Table 5.35: Age has impact on using healthcare app.

Correlations				
			Age	Respondent uses the healthcare app
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.178*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.012
		N	200	200
	Respondent uses the healthcare app	Correlation Coefficient	.178*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	.
		N	200	200

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

As per the Spearman correlation is less than 1 and is position the value of the Spearman is .178 which indicates that age has impact on using healthcare app. Moreover, the relationship is positive, strong and significant.

Hypothesis 9

Relationship between age and additional charges.

The hypothesis is:

H1 - Age has impact on additional charges

Table 5.36: Age has an impact on additional charges

		Correlations	
			Age Additional
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation	1.000
		Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	
	N	200	
Additional charges	Age	Correlation	.170*
		Coefficient	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.016	
	N	200	

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Spearman correlation value is 0.170 (table 5.36) which is less than 1, indicating that different age people considered that additional charges incurred when buying over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media moreover, there is positive and strong relationship between the age and additional charges.

Hypothesis 10

Association between age and social media usage among the respondent

Does age of the respondent and social media usage among the respondent are related. If age has significant impact on social media usage among the respondent are related, then it can be said that age and social media usage among the respondent are related. To find out the impact of age and social media usage among the respondent are related.

The hypothesis will be:

H1 - Age has an impact on social media usage among the respondent are related.

Table 5.37: Age has an impact on social media usage

			Age	Use social media
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation	1.000	-.245**
		Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	
	N	200	200	
Use social media	Age	Correlation	-.245**	1.000
		Coefficient		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	
	N	200	200	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As value of the Spearman correlation is $-.245$ indicating age has impact on social media users among the respondent and are related. This shows there is a significant relationship between the age and social media usage among the respondent are related; however, the relationship is strong but negative.

Hypothesis 11

Association between age and search health related information on the company website.

Does the age and searching information related to healthcare on the company website for product information are related. If age has significant impact on respondent who search healthcare information on the company website for product information, then it can be said that age and healthcare information search on the company website for product information are related. To find out the impact of age and respondent who search healthcare information on the company website for product information

The hypothesis will be:

H1 – Age and search healthcare information on the company website for product information.

Table 5.38: Age of respondent who search healthcare information on the company website for product information

			Age	Search health information company website
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.503**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Search healthcare company website for product information	Correlation Coefficient	.503*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As value of the Spearman correlation is $.503$, indicating age and searching healthcare information on the company website is related. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the age and searching healthcare information on the company website; furthermore, the relationship is found to be positive and strong.

Hypothesis 12

Relation between age and searching health or medicines related information related to on the social media.

Does age of the respondent and searching medicines related information on the social media are related. If age has significant impact on respondent who search healthcare information on the social media, then it can be said that age and respondent who search healthcare information on the social media are related. To find out the impact of age and respondent who search healthcare information on the social media

The hypothesis will be:

H1 – Relation between age and search health related information on the social media.

Table 5.39: Relation between age and search health related information on the social media

			Age	Search information about medicine on the social media
Spearman's rho	Age	Correlation coefficient	1.000	.299**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	200	200
	Search information about medicine on the social media	Correlation coefficient	.299**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The value of the Spearman correlation is 0.299, which is less than 1, indicating age does not have an impact on searching medicines related information on the social media. Thus, this indicates, a significant relationship between the age and respondent who search health and medicine related information on the social media; further, the relationship is positive and strong.

Table 5.40: Summary of Hypotheses Test Results as per Spearman's correlation:

H	Hypothesis	RESULT
H1	Relation between age and of the purchaser who purchases from online pharmacy	Accepted Relation is positive
H2	Relations between age and convenience for buying online.	Accepted, relation is positive
H3	Relation between age and price for buying from online pharmacy	Accepted, Relation is positive
H4	Relation between age and choice for buying from online	Accepted, Relation is positive
H5	Relation between age and cumulative scores.	Accepted, Relation is positive
H6	Relation between age and information security as a risk factor of buying medicine online.	Accepted, Relation is negative
H7	Relation between ages on healthcare information from the internet	Accepted, Relation is positive
H8	Relation between age and their healthcare app usage	Accepted, Relation is positive
H9	Relationship between age and additional charges	Accepted, Relation is positive
H10	Relation between age of the person who search health and medicine related information on the social media.	Accepted, Relation is positive
H11	Relation between gender and cumulative scores of different reasons which makes the buyer purchase medicines or any healthcare related products from online pharmacy.	Rejected
H12	Relation between age and searching the information related to disease medicine before visiting the GP	Rejected

5.3.4 CHI SQUARE

Hypothesis 1

Association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

H1: there is association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

Table 5.41: Association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.998 ^a	3	.573
Likelihood Ratio	2.013	3	.570
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.306	1	.253
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.95.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.100	.573
	Cramer's V	.100	.573
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and information security as the P value should have been less than 0.05 but in this case the p value is 0.573 which is higher than 0.05 $\chi^2(3, N=200) = 1.998, p = 0.573$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.1 so the effect is very small in this study. Thus, there is association gender the have the similar views on the information security of the patients on the online pharmacy and social media.

Hypothesis 2:

Association between gender and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media.

H1: There is association between gender and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media

Table 5.42: Association between gender and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.896 ^a	2	.050
Likelihood Ratio	6.066	2	.048
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.743	1	.098
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.			
Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.172	.052
	Cramer's V	.172	.052
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is an evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.05 χ^2 (2, N =200) = 5.89, p = 0 .05. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.172 equivalent to 0.2 so the effect is very small in this study. Thus, there is association both genders and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media, both the genders are aware that there can be additional charges

Hypothesis 3:

Association between Gender and Anonymity for buying over the counter pharmaceutical products from the social media or the internet pharmacy.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Anonymity for buying over the counter pharmaceutical products from the social media or the internet pharmacy.

Table 5.43: Association between Gender and Anonymity for buying over the counter pharmaceutical products from the social media or the internet pharmacy

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.534 ^a	4	.821
Likelihood Ratio	1.530	4	.821
Linear-by-Linear Association	.266	1	.606
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.13.			
Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.088	.821
	Cramer's V	.088	.821
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and Anonymity being the Reason for buying pharmaceutical products through the social media as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.821 $\chi^2(4, N = 200) = 1.534$, $p = 0.821$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.088 equivalent to 0.1 so the effect is very small in this study. Thus, there is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and Anonymity being the Reason for buying pharmaceutical products through the social media.

Hypothesis 4:

Association between Gender and convenience for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and convenience for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy

Table 5.44: Association between Gender and convenience for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.010 ^a	4	.734
Likelihood Ratio	2.033	4	.730
Linear-by-Linear Association	.287	1	.592
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.80.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.100	.734
	Cramer's V	.100	.734
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and convenience being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.734 $\chi^2(4, N = 200) = 2.010, p = 0.734$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.10 equivalent to 0.1 so the effect is very small in this study.

Hypothesis 5:

Association between Gender and choice for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy

H1: There Is Association between Gender and choice for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy

Table 5.45: Association between Gender and choice for buying over the counter drugs / medicine from the internet pharmacy

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.775 ^a	4	.217
Likelihood Ratio	6.834	4	.145
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.425	1	.119
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.28.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.170	.217
	Cramer's V	.170	.217
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and choice being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.217 $\chi^2(4, N=200) = 5.775$, $p = 0.217$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.170 equivalent to 0.2 so the effect is very small in this study.

Hypothesis 6:

Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP

Table 5.46: Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.174 ^a	4	.270
Likelihood Ratio	5.924	4	.205
Linear-by-Linear Association	.899	1	.343
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .85.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.161	.270
	Cramer's V	.161	.270
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and searching information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.270 $\chi^2(4, N = 200) = 5.174$, $p = 0.27$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.16 equivalent to 0.2 so the effect is very small in this study.

Hypothesis 7:

Association between Gender and do they consult the /Online Doctors on social media.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and consult the Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors.

Table 5.47: Association between Gender and consult the Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-Sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.224 ^a	4	.521
Likelihood Ratio	3.270	4	.514
Linear-By-Linear Association	.037	1	.848
N Of Valid Cases	200		
A. 2 Cells (20.0%) Have Expected Count Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Count Is 1.28.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.127	.521
	Cramer's V	.127	.521
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender, and do they consult the Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors as for the variables to be significant the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.5 $\chi^2(4, N=200) = 3.22, p = 0.52$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.1 equivalent to 0.1 so the effect is very small in this study.

Hypothesis 8:

Associations between Gender and Using Social Media for healthcare related information.

H1: There is association between gender and use social media for product information.

Table 5.48: Association between gender and use social media for product information:

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.486 ^a	4	.014
Likelihood Ratio	13.217	4	.010
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.042	1	.044
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.98.			
Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by	Phi	.250	.014
Nominal	Cramer's V	.250	.014
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is gender and use social media for health information as for the variables to be significant the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.014 $\chi^2(4, N=200) = 12.486$, $p = 0.014$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.25 equivalent to 0.3 so the effect is medium in this study.

Hypothesis 9:

Associations between age and convenience to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media.

H1: There is association between age and convenience to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media.

Table 5.49: Association between age and convenience to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.385 ^a	1	.002		
Continuity Correction ^b	8.145	1	.004		
Likelihood Ratio	11.907	1	.001		
Fisher's Exact Test				.001	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.338	1	.002		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.31.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.217	.002
	Cramer's V	.217	.002
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and convenience is the main reasons for purchasing over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media.

as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0 which is lesser than 0.05 $\chi^2(1, N=200) = 9.38$, $p = 0$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.2 so the effect is medium in this study. Thus, age and convenience are related, and convenience is the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media.

being the reasons for purchasing medicine/related Health product through online sources is related, however the impact is medium in this study.

Hypothesis 10:

Associations between age and individual choice for purchasing over the counter medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources.

Table 5.50: Associations between age and individual choice for purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.963 ^a	1	.008		
Continuity Correction ^b	6.040	1	.014		
Likelihood Ratio	7.256	1	.007		
Fisher's Exact Test				.011	.006
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.928	1	.008		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.29.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.187	.008
	Cramer's V	.187	.008
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and choice being the reasons for purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources as the P value should be less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0 which is lesser than 0.05 $\chi^2(1, N = 200) = 6.96$, $p = 0$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.2 so the effect is medium in this study. Thus, there is a relationship between age and choice.

Hypothesis 11:

Associations between age and additional charges as a risk factor when purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources.

H1: There is association between age and additional charges being the risk factor while purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources.

Table 5.51: Association between age and additional charges being the risk factor while purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.867 ^a	1	.090		
Continuity Correction ^b	2.273	1	.132		
Likelihood Ratio	2.805	1	.094		
Fisher's Exact Test				.098	.067
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.853	1	.091		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 14.44.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.120	.090
	Cramer's V	.120	.090
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no significant relationship between the two variables that is age and additional charges being the risk factors for purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources as the P value should be less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.09 which is more than 0.05 $\chi^2(1, N = 200) = 2.867$, $p = 0.09$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.12 so the effect is low in this study. Thus, age and additional charges as a risk factor are not related.

Hypothesis 12:

Associations between age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP.

H1: Associations between age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP

Table 5.52: Associations between age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.582 ^a	4	.233
Likelihood Ratio	6.302	4	.178
Linear-by-Linear Association	.028	1	.867
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.70.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.167	.233
	Cramer's V	.118	.233
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is no significant relationship between the two variables that is age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP. As the p value should be less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.233 which is more than 0.05 $\chi^2(4, n=200) = 5.582$, $p = 0.233$. effect size: Cramer's $v = 0.118$ so the effect is low in this study. Thus, there no significant relationship between age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP are related.

Hypothesis 13:

H1: Association between age and purchase of over the counter drugs / medicines online and internet pharmacy

Table 5.53: Association between age and purchase of over the counter drugs / medicines online and internet pharmacy.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	121.416 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	110.475	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	86.288	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.13.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.779	.000
	Cramer's V	.551	.000
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is strong evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy, as the P value should be less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0 which is lesser than 0.05 $\chi^2(4, N =200) = 121, p = 0$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.551 so the effect is high in this study. Thus, there is strong relation between age and purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy

Hypothesis 14:

Associations between age and Price as one of the reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media.

H1: There is association between age and Price as one of the reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media

Table 5.54: Association between age and Price as one of reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online pharmacy or internet or social media

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.851 ^a	1	.016		
Continuity Correction ^b	4.723	1	.030		
Likelihood Ratio	5.179	1	.023		
Fisher's Exact Test				.025	.019
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.822	1	.016		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.08.
b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.171	.016
	Cramer's V	.171	.016
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is an evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and price being one of the reason while buying the healthcare related product on the social media as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is $0.01 \chi^2(1, N=200) = 5.85, p = 0.01$. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.171 equivalent to 0.2 so the effect is very small in this study. Thus, there is association both age and price while buying the healthcare related product on the social media.

Hypothesis 15:

Associations between age and Anonymity of the purchaser

H1: There is association between age and anonymity of the purchaser

Table 5.55: Association between age and anonymity for buying over the counter medicine from the online pharmacy

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.662 ^a	2	.001
Likelihood Ratio	12.696	2	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.052	1	.025
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.74.			
Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.261	.001
	Cramer's V	.261	.001
N of Valid Cases		200	

There is an evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and anonymity being one of the reason while buying the healthcare related product on the social media as the P value should have been less than 0.05 and in this case the p value is 0.001 χ^2 (2, N =200) = 13.662, p = 0 .001. Effect size: Cramer's V = 0.261 equivalent to 0.3 so the effect is medium in this study. Thus, there is association both age and anonymity while buying the healthcare related product on the social media.

Summary of Hypotheses Test Results as per Chi Square Test

Table 5.56: Summary of Hypotheses Test Results as per Chi Square Test:

H	Hypotheses	Results
H1	Association between gender and information security of the patients in social media	Rejected
H2	Association between gender and additional charges as a risk factor while buying the healthcare related product on the social media	Rejected
H3	Association between Gender and Anonymity being the Reason for buying pharmaceutical products through the social media	Rejected
H4	Association between Gender and convenience for buying the medical product on social media/ online	Rejected
H5	Association between Gender and choice being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online	Rejected
H6	Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP .	Rejected
H7	Association between Gender and do they consult the /Online Doctors on social media.	Rejected
H8	Associations between Gender and Using Social Media for healthcare related information.	Accepted
H9	Relationship between age and convenience incurred when buying medicine from online sources	Accepted
H10	Associations between age and choice being the reasons for purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources	Accepted
H11	Relationship between age and additional charges	Rejected
H12	Associations between age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP.	Rejected
H13	Associations between age and purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy	Accepted
H14	Associations between age and Price for purchasing from online pharmacy	Accepted
H15	Association between age and anonymity	Accepted

5.3.5 ORDINAL REGRESSION

The Logit Theoretical model

The theoretical model to be used in the study is modelled as follows:

$$\text{Logit}(p) = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + \dots + b_kX_k$$

Where p is the probability of the characteristic of interest

$$\text{Odds} = \frac{p}{1-p} = \frac{\text{Probability of presence of characteristic}}{\text{Probability of not presence of characteristic}}$$

$$\text{And} = \text{Logit}(p) \text{ is } \frac{\ln(p)}{1-p}$$

The analyses of the out of ordinal regression is based on model fitting information, goodness of fit, pseudo R square and test of parallel line and parameter estimates. According to Engelhardt (2017), model fitting information helps to improves the ability to predict the results or the outcome by comparing a model without any explanatory variables such as the baseline or Intercept Only model against all the explanatory variables. The model fitting information contains the 2log likelihood for the intercept only or null model and the full model. Moreover, as per Hoque (2017) there is also a “likelihood ratio”, “chi square test” to test whether there is a significant improvement in the fit of the final mode relative to the intercept only model. The significance of chi-square statistic that is $p < .0005$ indicates that the model gives a significant improvement over the baseline intercept-only model, indicating that the model gives better predictions than just a guesswork based on the marginal probabilities for the outcome categories. The goodness of fit table contains the deviance and Pearson chi square test, which determines whether a model exhibits good fit to the data, non-significant test results indicate the model fits well, they do not always agree (Field (2018); Petrucci (2009). Pseudo R square are rough analogue to the R square in OLS regression, but due to lack of information it cannot be interpreted (Pituch and Stevens, 206).

PLUM - Ordinal Regression

Ordinal logit Regression:

1. PLUM cumulative social media BY Gender Employment Income WITH Age

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	946.987			
Final	923.742	23.245	10	.010

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the $p=0.01$, so the model is highly significant.

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	2058.991	2460	1.000
Deviance	729.919	2460	1.000

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(2460) = 2058.991, P=1$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(2460) = 729.72, P=1$] were both non-significant. So, these results suggest good model fit.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.110
Nagelkerke	.110
McFadden	.018

Overall, the model accounted for approximately 11% of the variance in the outcome

	parameter estimates					
	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval
[Employment=se If - employed]	1.209	0.600	4.057	1	0.044	0.033 2.386

In the parameter estimates self-employed was significant model

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	923.742			
General	.000 ^b	923.742	370	.000

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. Statistically significant is taken as an indicator that the assumption is not satisfied. Moreover, in the result of the analysis, we interpret the result to mean the assumption is unsatisfied ($p=0$).

An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the gender, employment status, disposable income and age had any effect on the cumulative score of all the type social media used by people to search all type of medicine and disease related information (always, never, sometimes). Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(10) = 23.24$, $p < .05$, employment status, $b = 1.2$, $SE = 0.6$, $p < 0$, predicted for searching medicine on cumulative social media, that is all types of social media.

Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 11% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- R Square = .018.

2. PLUM cumulative scores of reasons of buying medicine from online pharmacy/social media BY Gender Employment Income WITH Age

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	577.356			
Final	541.789	35.567	10	.000

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the $p=0$, so the model is highly significant

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	725.533	835	.997
Deviance	393.432	835	1.000

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(835) = 725.533, P=1$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(835) = 393.43, P=1$] were both non-significant. So, these results suggest good model fit.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.163
Nagelkerke	.165
McFadden	.041

Overall, the model accounted for approximately 16.5% of the variance in the outcome

Parameter Estimates							
	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
weekly disposable Income (£49)	1.54	.679	5.177	1	.023	-2.876	-.214
(£50-100)	1.58	.630	6.290	1	.012	-2.816	-.345
(100-149)	1.25	.514	5.912	1	.015	-2.258	-.242

In the parameter estimates people with weekly disposable income in between (£49 to 150) was significant model.

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	541.789			
General	.000 ^b	541.789	120	.000

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. For the model to be statistically significant, p value should be greater than or equal to 0.05. however, in this case the P value is equal to 0 (P=0). So, the test of parallel line is not significant.

An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the gender, employment status, disposable income and age had any effect on the cumulative score of all the type social media used by people to search all type of medicine and disease related information (always, never, sometimes). Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(10) = 35.56$, $p < 0$, only gender, $b = 0.064$, $SE = 0.257$, employment status, $b = .84$, $SE = .78$, $p < 0$, and income is $b = -1.54$, $SE = 6.3$, $P < 0.05$ predicted for reasons for buying medicine from online pharmacy/ social media, that is all types of social media. Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 16.5% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- $R^2 = .041$.

Thus, as per the model fitting information the model is highly significant, however the Test of Parallel Lines is not significant.

3. PLUM Risk of buying online base on info from social media BY Gender Employment Income WITH Age

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	568.965			
Final	539.651	29.314	10	.001

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the $p=0$, so the model is highly significant

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	1170.835	705	.000
Deviance	395.957	705	1.000

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(705) = 1170.835$, $P=1$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(705) = 393.957$, $P=1$] were both non-significant. So, these results suggest good model fit.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.136
Nagelkerke	.138
McFadden	.034

Overall, the model accounted for approximately 14% of the variance in the outcome

		Parameter Estimates				
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.
Location	Age	-.475	.240	3.902	1	.048
	[Gender=female]	.457	.259	3.115	1	.078
	[Employment=full time]	-.949	.386	6.055	1	.014
	[Employment=part time]	-.926	.382	5.885	1	.015
	[Employment=self-employed]	-.928	.604	2.358	1	.125
	[Income=less than £49 weekly]	-2.183	.685	10.143	1	.001
	[Income=£50 to £100]	-2.077	.635	10.684	1	.001
	[Income=£101 to 149]	-1.415	.514	7.568	1	.006
	[Income=£150 to 200]	-1.329	.492	7.297	1	.007

In the parameter estimates disposable income 1, income 2 and income 3. income 4 that is the disable incomes ranging from £49 to £200 per week, age, gender 1 that is male and employment 1,2,3 that is full time employed, part time employed and self-employed was significant model. This is significant model

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	539.651			
General	241.254 ^b	298.397 ^c	100	.000

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. For the model to be statistically significant, p value should be greater than or equal to 0.05. however, in this case the P value is equal to 0 (P=0). So, the test of parallel line is not significant.

An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the gender, employment status, disposable income and age had any effect on the cumulative score of risk of buying medicines based on information obtained from online sources (always, never, sometimes). Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(10) = 29.3$, $p < 0$, only gender 1 that is male with $b = 0.45$, $SE = 0.259$

employment status that is self-employed $b = -0.92, SE = 0.6$, full time $B = -0.94 SE = 0.38$ and part Time employed $b = -0.924, SE = .38, p < 0$, and income is $b = -1.32, SE = 0.49, P < 0.05$ predicted for that it was risky to buying medicines from online pharmacy base on info from social media. Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 14% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- R Square = .034.

4. PLUM purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media WITH Age

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	243.773			
Final	116.222	127.551	5	.000

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the $p = 0$, so the model is highly significant

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	137.630	55	.000
Deviance	59.503	55	.315

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(55) = 137, P = 0$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(55) = 59.5, P < 1$] were both non-significant. So, these results suggest good model fit.

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.472
Nagelkerke	.509
McFadden	.244

Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 51% of the variance in the outcome.

		Parameter Estimates						
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Location	Age	2.214	.241	84.496	1	.000	1.742	2.685
	[searchmedicineinfo nsocialmedia=3]	.978	.592	2.728	1	.099	-.182	2.138

In the parameter estimates searching medicine related information on the social media 3 and age, was significant model. This is significant model

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	116.222			
General	93.144 ^b	23.078 ^c	15	.083

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. For the model to be statistically significant, p value should be greater than or equal to 0.05., in this case the P value is equal to 0.08 (P is greater than 0.05). So, the test of parallel line is significant.

An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the gender, employment status, disposable income and age had any effect on the cumulative score of risk of buying medicines based on information obtained from online sources (always, never, sometimes). Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(5) = 127$, $p < 0$, only age, $b = 2.2$, $SE = 0$, search medicine related information on the internet, $b=0.9$ $SE = 0.59$, $p < 0$, predicted for searching medicine on cumulative social media, that is all types of social media. Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 50.9% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- R Square = .24

5. PLUM purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media Gender Income Employment Use Internet Use social media WITH Age

Model Fitting Information				
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Model Intercept Only	495.598			
Final	342.351	153.247	20	.000

Link function: Logit.

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the p=0, so the model is highly significant

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	524.243	660	1.000
Deviance	320.039	660	1.000

Link function: Logit.

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(660) = 524.243, P=1$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(660) = 3920, P=1$] were both non-significant. So, these results suggest good model fit

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.535
Nagelkerke	.578
McFadden	.294

Overall, the model accounted for approximately 57.8% of the variance in the outcome

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Model Null Hypothesis	342.351			
General	285.623 ^b	56.727 ^c	60	.596

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. For the model to be statistically significant, p value should be greater than or equal to 0.05, moreover in this case the P value is equal to 0.596 (P=0.590). So, the test of parallel line is significant.

Parameter Estimates							
	Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
[Gender=male]	0 ^a	.	.	0	.	.	.
[Income=less than 49]	-1.655	.796	4.315	1	.038	-3.216	-.093
[Income=£49-100]	-1.650	.735	5.035	1	.025	-3.092	-.209
[Employment=full time]	-1.075	.462	5.409	1	.020	-1.980	-.169
[Use internet=sometimes]	.967	.355	7.421	1	.006	.271	1.663

In the parameter estimates weekly disposable income of £100 and full time employed, people who used internet often was significant model. This is significant model

An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the gender, employment status, disposable income and age had any effect on the searching information on the internet on medicine and actually buying medicines based on information obtained from online sources (always, never, sometimes).

Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(20) = 153.2, p < 0$, only gender, $b = 0.22, SE = 0.31$, employment status, $b = -1, SE = .462, p < 0$, and income 1 is $b = -1.655, SE = 0.78, P < 0$ predicted for searching medicine on cumulative social media, that is all types of social media. Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 57.8% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- R Square = .29

**6. PLUM convenience being the factor to purchase medicine from online sources
WITH Age**

Case Processing Summary			
		N	Marginal Percentage
CONVENIENCE	Strongly disagree	16	8.0%
	Disagree	33	16.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	84	42.0%
	Agree	43	21.5%
	Strongly agree	24	12.0%
Valid		200	100.0%
Missing		0	
Total		200	

Model Fitting Information				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	126.362			
Final	99.350	27.012	2	.000

Link function: Logit.

As per Model fitting information, the for the model to be significant P value should be less than 0.05, and in this case the p=0, so the model is highly significant

Goodness-of-Fit			
	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	29.309	26	.297
Deviance	34.866	26	.115

Link function: Logit.

So, in this model the interpretation Pearson Chi square test [$\chi^2(26) = 29.3, P < 0.05$] and the Deviance test [$\chi^2(26) = 34.8, P < 0.05$] were both significant. So, these results suggest good model fit

Pseudo R-Square	
Cox and Snell	.126
Nagelkerke	.134
McFadden	.047

Link function: Logit.

Thus, the overall value for the model accounted for approximately 13.4% of the variance in the outcome

		Parameter Estimates					95% Confidence Interval	
		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Thre	[convenience 1]	-1.184	.521	5.156	1	.023	-2.205	-.162
shol	[convenience 2]	.179	.488	.135	1	.713	-.777	1.136
d	[convenience 3]	2.131	.512	17.31	1	.000	1.127	3.135
	[convenience 4]	3.583	.558	41.27	1	.000	2.490	4.677
Loca	Age	.822	.161	26.04	1	.000	.506	1.137
tion	Gender	-.005	.262	.000	1	.986	-.518	.508

Link function: Logit.

In the parameter estimates age and convenience was the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media was significant model. This is significant model.

Test of Parallel Lines^a				
Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Null Hypothesis	99.350			
General	93.355	5.995	6	.424

The null hypothesis states that the location parameters (slope coefficients) are the same across response categories.

a. Link function: Logit.

As the test of parallel lines are non-significant, then we interpret it to mean that the assumptions are satisfied. For the model to be statistically significant, p value should be greater than or equal to 0.05, moreover in this case the P value is equal to 0.424 (P=0.424). So, the test of parallel line is significant. An ordered logit model was estimated to investigate the age and convenience as the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media (always, never, sometimes). Together, the predictors accounted for a significant amount of variance in the outcome, likelihood ratio $\chi^2(2) = 27, p < 0$, only age $b = 0.822$, $SE = 0.161$, predicted convenience as the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media. Overall, the model accounted for approximately 13% of the variance in the outcome, McFadden's pseudo- R Square = 0.04. Thus, the model convenience was considered the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media with the age is significant model.

5.3.6 Summary of Results of different Models as per Ordinal Regression

In the model cumulative social media BY Gender Employment Income with Age As per the regression analysis it was found that normally people who were self-employed searched health related information on different social media platform, and model fit was highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 11%.

In the model cumulative scores of reasons of buying medicine from online pharmacy/social media BY Gender Employment Income with Age model, the model fitting information the model is highly significant, however the Test of Parallel Lines is not significant, with Nagelkerke of 16%.

In the model In Risk of buying online base on info from social media BY Gender Employment Income WITH Age the model is highly significant, test of parallel line is not significant, with Nagelkerke of 13.5%

In the model Purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media WITH Age, as per the Model fitting information the model is highly significant, Nagelkerke was 50% and test of parallel line was significant

In the model Purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media Gender Income Employment Use Internet Use social media WITH Age, the model was highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 58%, test of parallel line was significant.

In the model convenience being the main factor to purchase medicine from online sources WITH Age, model is highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 13% and the test of parallel line is significant.

5.3.7 Reliability study

The reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's Alpha , accordingly the Cronbach's Alpha value for the test was 0.63.

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha		
Based on		
Cronbach's Alpha	Standardized Items	N of Items
.631	.627	11

Cronbach's alpha coefficient should have values between 0 and 1, as 1 denotes perfect internal reliability and 0 means no internal reliability. The figure 0.63 in this study is an acceptable level of internal reliability in most social science studies (Nunnally, 1978). Accordingly, in the table below, information security was considered to be the risk factor as Cronbach Alpha value is 0.67, and for the reason to buy convenience had the highest Cronbach Alpha of 0.61.

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha
Search Information About Medicine on The Social Media	3.24	.885	.61
Reason for Buying Online- Convenience	1.76	.816	.610
Reason for Buying Online - Price	3.13	1.081	.577
Reason for Buying Online -Choice	2.60	.827	.603
Reason for Buying Online -Anonymity	2.85	.901	.610
Age	1.74	.859	.572
Disposable Income	3.01	1.301	.568
Lack Off-licence	2.11	.760	.619
Quality of The Medicine Which Is Brought Online	2.01	.767	.608
Additional Charges	1.88	.933	.624
Information Security	2.07	.935	.657

5.4 Thematic analysis

The six steps for analysis for thematic analysis was proposed by Braun and Clarke (2006), accordingly, the data was analysed keeping the research questions in mind the data was coded, analysed to unearthed themes and categories (Saunders, et al., 2007). The categories found are in table 5.58 and figure 5.28, 5.29. Data for thematic analysis was collected by interviewing 14 healthcare professionals situated in different places in UK. Accordingly, their demographic details in are presented in the table below:

Table 5.57: Demographic details of the interviewees

Interviewee	Profession	Location
Interviewee 1-01	GP	Stoke on Trent
Interviewee 1-02	Psychiatrist	London
Interviewee 1-03	GP	Manchester
Interviewee 1-04	GP	Manchester
Interviewee 1-05	GP	Manchester
Interviewee 1-06	Pharmacist	Wolverhampton
Interviewee 1-07	Pharmacist	Wolverhampton
Interviewee 1-08	Pharmacist	Walsall
Interviewee 1-09	Pharmacist	London
Interviewee1-10	Pharmacist	London
Interviewee 1-11	Pharmacist	London
Interviewee 1-12	Nurse	Wolverhampton
Interviewee 1-13	GP	Manchester
Interviewee 1-14	GP	London

Table 5.58 Code Generation

Interview quotes	codes
In such case MHRA and NHS in UK play very important role, the same applies to the online pharmacies or websites who are selling medicine and websites dealing with healthcare related information.	ethical, regulatory Coded for Legal
it is good, but the online consultation website or if advertised on social media should be registered with the NHS, otherwise it is difficult to find out how legal it is.	ethical, regulatory Coded for Legal
Besides this I would say the drug companies, NHS or MHRA should provide guidelines such please do not use this if you don't feel relieved within 3 weeks which will help the people understand	ethical, regulatory Coded for Legal
I think the regulatory bodies such as MHRA should write and stated not suitable for long term use or use for x amount of days only	ethical, regulatory Coded for Legal
Healthcare related Information on Social media that is about any medicine or disease is helpfully but should not be relied upon as we don't know whether the information is right or wrong	informative, self-aware, educational Health related information ,.
However, if the patient or customer wants any information on any medicine or on any diseases they can come down to the pharmacy and get the information as the people in pharmacy are qualified and real person not virtual as it is in the social media	Educational purpose, Self-awareness
“the information related to healthcare on social media should only be used to educational purpose and to increase the Self-awareness not for diagnoses purpose”.	Educational purpose, unreliable
I would say in a way it good as the customer is ware of his symptoms and also is aware what can be the probable medicine which will be prescribe to him, but he should not buy any	self-aware, educational. Potentially unsafe Unreliable Dangerous

medicine without the consultation of the pharmacist or the doctors	informative,
People do look for medical information online and social media at times even to see how worthy the doctor is	self-aware, educational. informative,
it helps them to research their general medical condition, a lot of people use trusted website such as NHS.com, they're helpful they give specific symptoms etc however some people are not aware, and they use non-credible website then it can be misleading”	Misleading Potentially unsafe Unreliable Dangerous misinformative
using for diagnosing purpose then it will prove to be disastrous which can also lead to complications.	Unreliable Dangerous
having a healthcare related pages and information on social media is good for the consumers / patients so that they knowledge, however they should never go for self-medication, that is as long as they just use social media for information and educational purpose	self-aware, educational. information and educational purpose, informative,
social media is benefit for the customers as long as they just use social media for information and educational purpose, if they start using for diagnosing purpose then it will prove to be disastrous which can also lead to complications	self-aware, educational. informative,
Yes, people do buy non-prescription medicines as suggested on social media or on the internet or on any print media.	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines, Dangerous risky
on the basis of information obtained from social media people buy over the counter it is allowed but then if they do not get relieve, they should consult a doctor or a pharmacist,	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines Dangerous risky
I can recall incidents when people come to my pharmacy and say they saw on London tube it was advertised that “feeling tired”, “tired of being tired” take Floradix, so they used to come say	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines,

they feel very tired and can I get Floradix, well people don't understand that tiredness can be for many reason	Dangerous risky
Convenience is the main reason people buy on line as when people are busy they don't want to go to the pharmacy and prefer to order from online pharmacy, also being anonymous is a big issue, people who suffer from sexually transmitted infections etc want to remain anonymous so can prefer to buy from online pharmacy.	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non-prescription medicines, Dangerous risky
Besides convenience anonymity and price, moreover wide variety of things you can find online food, light, as quite a lot of people at times say I can get it online.	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines, Dangerous Risky price
They should not buy any medical product from online pharmacy as it is dangerous, but as it is It is all about convenience or be anonymous or can be cheaper	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines, Dangerous Risky price
people can buy over the counter medicines based on information from social media, but it should be used only for a limited period, if there is no symptomatic relieve	Dangerous Risky Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines,
lot of people come to my pharmacy and ask for a brand and if I don't have that brand, I say I don't have that brand but a different brand so the say ok. I don't want it I can get it online".	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non-prescription medicines, Dangerous risky
It's normal the non-prescription medicines which are bought from the internet or the online pharmacy	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non-prescription medicines, Dangerous Risky Online pharmacy
I feel buying from online pharmacy is potentially dangerous and unreliable	Data loss Dangerous

	Risky dangerous and unreliable Security issues
a patient cannot talk face to face; however, people do buy because of convenience. But online pharmacy potentially dangerous, store base pharmacy Is better.	Dangerous Risky unreliable
how secure the healthcare and personal information which are shared by the customers on the online pharmacies	Security issues
If they go to local pharmacy it can give face to face interaction , however Online pharmacy alone will only survive	Unsafe Security issues
if it also has store based as lot of people might be taking medicine from online pharmacy, but if there is any side effect they cannot contact online pharmacy, they will come to the local pharmacy, where they will have a face to face talk, so as per me I don't like the concept of online pharmacy	Risky Dangerous
Information on Social media about any medicine or disease is helpfully but should not be relied upon as we don't know whether the information is right or wrong however if the patient or customer wants any information on any medicine or on any diseases they can come down to the pharmacy and get the information as the people in pharmacy are qualified and real person not virtual as it is in the social media	informative, self-aware, educational.
But then they should not continuously use it if they don't feel any difference. I would suggest maximum 3 week beyond that if they do not feel relieved, they should consult a healthcare professional.	Risky Unreliable Dangerous
I don't agree with online pharmacy, or any medical product to be purchased online as it may be risky	Dangerous Risky unreliable

Besides getting information from pharmacist will be more reliable and person can be confident rather than when they get information on social media	Risky Unreliable Dangerous
Like for example lot of people come to my pharmacy and ask for a brand and if I don't have that brand, I say I don't have that brand but a different brand so they say ok. I don't want it I can get it online.”.	Convenience, choice, anonymity, non- prescription medicines price
So, in a way it is a false advertising and half knowledge is dangerous. Information on Social media can be good, but it gives half information and can mislead the consumer/patient as half knowledge is dangerous	half knowledge dangerous Misleading

The analysis of the interview data unearthed the different themes to become the categories. These categories are listed in the table below:

Table 5.59: Framework for codes and categories

Categories	Factors
Category 01	Social media
Category 02	Convenience
Category 03	Choice
Category 04	Regulatory
Category 05	Legal
Category 06	Ethical
Category 07	Reliability
Category 08	Security
Category 09	Healthcare
Category 10	Information and educational purpose
Category 11	Non-prescription
Category 12	Advertising
Category 13	Risk

Compiled by the researcher

Figure 5.28: Initial Thematic map showing the 5 different clusters: Based on the information obtained from the thematic analysis, (developed by the researcher)

After transcribing the interviews, various codes were identified from the transcribed data, Accordingly, from these codes, potential themes emergent themes were generated, firstly a thematic map was designed, then the derived themes were organised in the thematic analysis network. The themes give better understanding and interpretation of each other. To illustrate the five emerged themes, a thematic was designed (figure 5.28). As shown in (figure 5.29) the themes were organised in a coherent manner in the thematic analysis network (Braun and Clarke, 2006) Important 5 areas are the themes are shown in (figure 5.28). Thus, as per (Figure 5.29) (table 5.58) shows the various themes that were generated based on the interviews.

Figure 5.29: Thematic analysis network: categories grouped into clusters. developed by the researcher on the basis of information obtained from the thematic analysis

As per Rubin and Rubin, (2011) in the research, an analysis of the qualitative data basically focuses on presenting thorough, in depth and detailed information so as to address the research. This section of the report deals with the analysis of the interviews conducted with the healthcare care professionals such as Doctors and pharmacist. Accordingly, as per the findings of the interview, interviewee 1-06 who was a pharmacist believed that,

“Social media being important for healthcare professional, as social media breaks down and help to read the articles easily rather than reading pages and pages on the book, it also helps to read people perception and realistic approach, and how it is impacting people”

However as per him as the healthcare/ pharmaceutical industry being more technically sound, it needs more of the regulatory works, government approvals etc so basically this was one

of the main reason why Pharmaceutical/healthcare industry was very late in being into social media and social media marketing.

Further interviewee 1-07 who was also a pharmacist was of the opinion that *“having a healthcare related pages and information on social media is good for the consumers / patients so that they knowledge, however they should never go for self-medication, that is as long as they just use social media for information and educational purpose, if they start using for diagnosing purpose then it will prove to be disastrous which can also lead to complications. Besides he was also of opinion that on the basis of information obtained from social media people buy over the counter it is allowed but then if they do not get relieve, they should consult a doctor or a pharmacist”*.

Thus, according to him social media or the internet does have healthcare related pages and information for educational purpose or just for knowledge, but they should never go for self-medication, as it can be disastrous, moreover people do buy over the counter drugs from online pharmacy based on the information from social media.

Similarly, interviewee 1-08 who happens to be again a pharmacist remarked that *“ people can buy over the counter medicines based on information from social media, but it should be used only for a limited period, if there is no symptomatic relieve”*.

Thus, he says that even if people want to buy the over the counter non-prescription drugs from the online or offline pharmacy based on the information from social media but they should not use it for more than 3 weeks if they do not get relieve.

Further, interviewee 1-09 a pharmacist by profession remarked, *“it helps them to research their general medical condition, a lot of people use trusted website such as NHS.com, they’re helpful they give specific symptoms etc however some people are not aware, and they use non-credible website and online pharmacy then it can be misleading”*

Thus, here it is said that as there are many misleading websites and online pharmacy so the consumers should be very cautious and watchful while using for any health related information or buying as over the counter medicines. So, it is very important that people use only credible website or if they are using information from any social media pages then it should be credible page of NHS etc for healthcare related information otherwise it will be misleading.

Further interviewee 1-09 a pharmacist said that

“People do look for medical information online and social media at times even to see how worthy the doctor is”,

So even in such case the website or the social media page should be authentic and credible otherwise it will give wrong impression of the doctors as the patient will have misleading information.

Moreover, it was pointed out that by interviewee 1-01 a medical doctor who is a GP that

“The drug information obtained from social media or from blogs etc should be only for information and educational purpose and it should not be used for diagnosis purpose, as yes, it is correct sometimes, but people may not understand the technical terms”

Again, it is advisable that the drug information obtained from social media or from blogs should not be used for diagnosis purpose but just for knowledge.

In the opinion of interviewee 1-10 a pharmacist:

“Information on Social media about any medicine or disease is helpfully but should not be relied upon as we don't know whether the information is right or wrong however if the patient or customer wants any information on any medicine or on any diseases they can come down to the pharmacy and get the information as the people in pharmacy are qualified and real person not virtual as it is in the social media”.

It, been brought out time and again that information related to health and medicine obtained from social media should not be used for diagnosis purpose and they should purchase even the over the counter medicine from community pharmacy and not from the online pharmacy.

Yet another example of interviewee 1-11 a pharmacist said:

“Yes, people do buy non-prescription medicines as suggested on social media or on the internet or on any print media. I can recall incidents when people come to my pharmacy and say they saw on London tube it was advertised that “feeling tired”, “tired of being tired” take Floradix, so they used to come say they feel very tired and can I get Floradix, well people don't understand that tiredness can be for many reason.. Not just Iron deficiency, so yes people do buy medicines if they read on Social media or any print media. But then they should not continuously use it if they don't feel any difference. I would suggest maximum 3 week beyond that if they do not feel relieved, they should consult a healthcare professional. Besides this I would say the drug companies, NHS or MHRA should provide guidelines such please do not use this if you don't feel relieved within 3 weeks which will help the people understand”
“I think the regulatory bodies such as MHRA should write and stated not suitable for long term use or use for x amount of days only”

Here the interview again has brought out that people do buy over the counter medicine from the online and offline pharmacy just on the basis of information obtained on internet or social media.

Further even in the opinion of interviewee 1-02 who is a medical doctors (GP) by profession

“I don’t agree with online pharmacy, or any medical product to be purchased online as it may be risky. I think online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, it cannot survive, moreover a patient cannot talk face to face, however people do buy because of convenience”. “Besides getting information from pharmacist will be more reliable and person can be confident rather than when they get information on social media”.

As per the interviewee her Convenience is the reason people do buy from online pharmacy.

Again, a doctor that is interviewee 1-03 was also of the opinion that

“I would say in a way it good as the customer is ware of his symptoms and also is aware what can be the probable medicine which will be prescribe to him, but he should not buy any medicine without the consultation of the pharmacist or the doctors”

The online information or online pharmacy should not use, as far as possible people should buy from community pharmacy.

Similarly, a pharmacist that’s interviewee 1-07

“It depends which online pharmacy the person is buying, if it is registered with MHRA than it ok to buy otherwise it can harm Patient, as there will no proper service, no proper information, the drug can be low standard or not within the therapeutic windows, so buying even a non-prescription drug also from any online pharmacy is not a right decision as it can even lead a to complications”

One of the pharmacists that’s the interviewee 1-09 from London said,

“Like for example lot of people come to my pharmacy and ask for a brand and if I don’t have that brand, I say I don’t have that brand but a different brand so the say ok. I don’t want it I can get it online.”.

Similarly, one of the doctors (Interviewee 1-02) remarked that,

“So in a way it is a false advertising and half knowledge Is dangerous. Information on Social media can be good, but it gives half information and can mislead the consumer/patient as half knowledge is dangerous. In certain cases it is good, like for example in India a mass campaign where the pregnant ladies in first trimester where given information on social media that the they should take an iron supplement and they were aske d to go and physician about , thus it create an awareness”.

The healthcare professionals were also asked about online consultation with doctor, because at times people do not get appointments from GP, in this case one of the doctors (Interviewee 1-13) said,

“it is good, but the online consultation website or if advertised on social media should be registered with the NHS, otherwise it is difficult to find out how legal it is. Further he also remarked that online doctors are good for elderly patients who find it difficult to visit the GP and also for follow-up cases it a good initiative. Babylon is on the online doctor consultation website, which is also used in UK by many people. Besides the Babylon NHS should come out with online doctors which will help the elderly patients and patients who are busy and suffering from chronic conditions and can't wait for the appointment”.

Online doctors might be good, but like online pharmacy nothing can be said for the online doctors unless they are registered and informed to the people.

In these regards doctor (interviewee 1-14) also said that

“GP surgeries and pharmacist should inform about these online consultations to the patients, so that patients do not get trapped to the online doctors' consultations which are not approved by the NHS. In such cases MHRA and NHS in UK play very important role”, the same applies to the online pharmacies or websites who are selling medicine and websites dealing with healthcare related information”.

Besides, they also expressed their views on the advantages and disadvantages of social media in pharmaceutical industry and healthcare related industry. They also expressed their views on how the social media and digital media in healthcare and pharmaceuticals industry in long run can be useful in terms of getting information about the medical conditions, but based on the information obtained from internet people should not diagnose his disease.

Thus, based on these interviews code it was found that people do buy from online pharmacy based on the information obtained from the internet, it can be very risky and disastrous. they should use online health related information only for knowledge and not for diagnosing themselves.

5.5 Summary

This chapter deals with finding and analysis of outcomes the primary data and the secondary data using quantitative and qualitative methods. The analysis is done by highlighting and examining the main and the important findings of the study using Pearson's correlation, spearman's correlation, Chi square and ordinal regression using SPSS and the qualitative study was done by using the thematic analysis.

Based on the quantitative study it was found that the age did had significant impact the buying behaviour of healthcare related product visa vis gender, and as per spearman's correlation, Chi square and ordinal regression convivence, price, anonymity were the main reason why people were buying from the internet stores and as per Cochbach Alpha convenience, anonymity had the score of more 6 showing the validity of the data. Thus, it was the age and not the gender of the people that was associated or related to convivence, price, anonymity in buying healthcare related products from online sources.

Further as per the thematic analysis it was found that digital media and in particular social media and various website can be healthful only for educational and informational purpose, but the information gained from these websites should not be used for diagnosis purpose. The customers should not use these websites to diagnose their symptoms and disease. Besides as the thematic analysis and as per the interview with the healthcare professionals such as doctors and pharmacist it could be concluded that people normally use the online doctors and online pharmacy because they are convenient specially for the people who are busy and who cannot wait for GPs appointment they consult the online doctors, similarly online pharmacies are also used for people who find it convenient as convenience Is one of the major factor which has been brought out by most of the healthcare professional for using online pharmacy and online doctors. Besides as it is seen that next generation people are using online pharmacies and online doctors so the government and Medical agencies like MHRA ,NHS should see to it that they are safe and people should be informed that even over the counter medication should not be used for very long time, beside as one of pharmacist said that seeing the advertisements people buy the general over the counter medicine , however in the advertisements there should be warning that any medicines even over the counter medicine should not be used for prolonged period if the person is not cured.

6 CHAPTER SIX: DICUSSION

According to different authors it was found out that social media is playing an important role in healthcare marketing. As per Hackworth (2010) social media networking in the health care industry provides for implementation of social media applications successfully. Current applications on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube are quite popular. Furthermore, Shaw (2011) believes social media is not only used by the patients and care takers but even the doctors and nurses have embraced in the healthcare sector. Thus, based on the demographic data (secondary data) of UK obtained from ONS, it was found that high income people tend to use internet, social media users, online shoppers. These online shoppers were also purchasers of over the counter medicine from online pharmacy.

6.1 Discussion Quantitative study

Based on the quantitative studies, information related health on social media was only searched by people of specific age. Similarly, Bernhardt *et al.*, (2014) is of the opinion that says not all people who bought over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media resources basically looked for various factors such as choice, convenience, additional charges. However, respondents of all the age group considered information security very important. Thus, it showed people of all the age group did not search the internet for health related information.

On analysing the primary data using the quantitative methods using SPSS, the first approach used by descriptive statistics, accordingly in this approach the frequency of a task incurring again and again was found out. Accordingly, for quantitative studies the sample size was 384 samples, out of which only 200 samples were valid and out of which age of the majority participant were in the age group of 18 to 29 followed by 30 to 39, so the researcher cannot comment much on behaviour of the people who are beyond 40 in the social media in healthcare industry, besides the gender ratio of male to female was 58% : 42% , it can be said male to female ratio was almost equal, so the result obtained contain the habit of both the gender. Besides most of the respondents had weekly disposable income of £100 to £150, besides this most of the respondents were either students or full tie employed. Further it was also noted that most of the respondents were using social media and internet and also used social media for feedback on products, further most of the respondents also searched website and social media for healthcare related products of which 50% respondents said that they

sometimes did search, however 12% respondents said that they always searched healthcare related however 24% said they often searched, so it can be said that about 88% of the respondents did search for internet that is social media or website or even Wikipedia for healthcare related information either for adverse drug reaction, or for different symptoms of diseases, specific disease related medicines. Besides the respondent were also asked their views on whether they feel that the information on the healthcare given on the social media safe accordingly 80% felt that it was neither safe nor unsafe, that it is depends if a person used right source it is safe and if wrong source it can be unsafe, It was also found that about 44% of the respondents said that convenience as the reason to buy healthcare and pharmaceutical products from the online or internet related sources followed by price which were very few respondents, price and being anonymous. Besides this the respondents were also asked if they felt that their information was secured purchasing healthcare product from the online sources, accordingly, 7% felts it was safe however 26% did not had opinion. Further they were also asked their views on risk associated with the online doctors or online pharmacy accordingly 8% felt that it can be risky however 39% did not have any opinion. Further they were also asked if they used healthcare apps 3% to 43% were on the positive sides that is they use from always to sometimes. Besides the descriptive frequency the ordinal data set was also studied for spearman's correlation and ordinal regression.

Based on the Spearman's rho correlation it was found that people of only certain age search for the health related information on the social media, however (Bernhardt *et al.*, 2014) it was also found that there are various factors such as of the choice, convenience, additional charges, people of certain age group only purchased over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media. However, all the age respondents considered that the information security was one of the most important parameter on the online sources, further it was also found that people of specific age group only more interested in searching internet, or on social media for healthcare related information. Thus, it can be said that people of all the age did not search health related or pharmaceutical product related information on the internet.

Besides, it was also found that there was a significant strong and positive relationship between the age and price as the main reason to buy over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media; furthermore, the relationship is positive and strong, which means as the ages increase people purchased medicine from online

sources for the price, convenience being the reason to buy medicine from online pharmacy or online sources, beside it was also found some people did not bother about the price or convenience, but it was their choice to buy medicine or pharmaceutical related products from online sources. Thus, it was found that age and different factors such as convenience price and choice was directly related. People of all ages felt it was convenient to buy medicine from online sources because of price. It was also found that age of the respondent and searching internet for healthcare information are related and the relation is found to be strong and positive that is more the age people tend to search the healthcare related information on the internet and this was also discussed in the literature review of all the people who surf internet most of them search healthcare related information. Similarly, people of all the age search and use healthcare app, and also there was a significant relationship between the age of the person and purchase of over the counter non-prescription drugs or medicine from online or internet pharmacy or social media, also the association between the two was positive and strong. Further the association between age and respondent who search healthcare information on the social media was tested on spearman's co-relation, it was found that there was a significant positive and strong relationship.

Based on the results obtained from Chi square test, there was no association or relationship between the two variables that is gender and information security satisfied with social media in healthcare related product, genuineness about the information and prescription in social media, satisfaction with social media in healthcare related product, searching information related to medicine on the social media, purchase of over the counter drugs or non-prescription medicine from the internet pharmacy or consult the online pharmacy/online doctors, besides searching information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP, risk associated with purchase of medical products on the social media, even being anonymous or safety or convenience was any reason for buying from online source which means both the gender were equally concerned, however, it was seen that there was significant relationship between gender and extra charges or added charges incurred when purchasing the healthcare related product on the social media, use of social media for healthcare related product information. However, there is a strong relationship between age and purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy, convenience, choice, and cumulative scores of reasons of buying online pharmacy being the reasons for purchasing medicine/related HealthCare product through online sources, age and search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP. Additional charges being the risk factors for purchasing medicine/related

HealthCare product through online sources. Besides there is no evidence of significant relationship between the two variables that is age and cumulative score of risk of buying online.

Thus, based on Chi Square the age is an important factor, when people search for healthcare related information over the social media and on the internet, however gender do not have any association with the other variables. Different models were studied using ordinal regression; however, convenience and age was found to be major reason for purchasing the nonprescription medicine from social media and from online pharmacies.

Based on ordinal regression the In the model cumulative social media BY Gender Employment Income with Age it was found that normally people who were self-employed searched health related information on different social media platform, and model fit was highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 11%, besides cumulative scores of reasons of buying medicine from online pharmacy/social media BY Gender Employment Income with Age model, the model fitting information the model is highly significant, however the Test of Parallel Lines is not significant, with Nagelkerke of 16%. Further purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media WITH Age, as per the Model fitting information the model is highly significant, Nagelkerke was 50% and test of parallel line was significant. Besides Purchase medicine from online sources BY search medicine info on social media Gender Income Employment Use Internet Use social media WITH Age, the model was highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 58%, test of parallel line was significant. Last and not the least the model convenience being the factor to purchase medicine from online sources WITH Age, model is highly significant, with Nagelkerke of 13% and the test of parallel line is significant.

6.2 Discussion of the Qualitative study

Based on the thematic analysis, various themes such as (Fig 5.29) government related policies, healthcare related information and challenges, social media, convenience, choice, regulatory, legal, ethical, reliability, information security , healthcare, information and educational purpose, non-prescription, advertising and risk etc were generated . Accordingly, these themes are discussed below.

Government policies

Government policy was the theme generated and the sub themes were regulatory. Ethical, legal etc these can only be regulated if the government's implement policies, so the health related information available on the internet and social media available is safe. To ensure its safety and reliability the government should enact rules and laws which renders the healthcare information on the social media and on the other website and online pharmacies safe for the use of the customers. Accordingly, Government policies will be discussed based on Regulatory, Ethical, and Legal. The regulatory body in UK is "The Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA)", this body is regulatory body and an executive agency for the Department of Health and Social Care in the United Kingdom. The primary responsibility of MHRA is to ensure that medicines and any healthcare pharmaceutical device which is available in the market and pharmacies are safe. They also work for regulating the laws relating healthcare and pharmaceutical industry in the UK (GOV.UK, n.d.). According to GOV.UK, (n.d.) and MHRA is trying to make the online pharmacy, websites safe for the customers and consumers by regulating the ethical, legal laws. Similarly the Gov.uk (nd) has made provisions for the customers to report any website who are selling medicine and internet pharmacy which they feel is not registered with the MHRA (fig. 6.1) however the MHRA should not only provide this on the GOV.uk website but such provision for reporting the illegal online pharmacy or websites but provide information in form advertisement on the newspapers, and social media and also in the community pharmacy and the GP surgery. However, through this (fig. 6.2) the customers can report but lot of patients may not be having this information. Similarly, they can search whether the website can legally sell the medicine on the internet (fig. 6.1). but instead on providing on this only on website as per the interview doctors and pharmacist were of the opinion if this information is provided by the help of leaflet and advertisements as it will be easier for the customers and consumers.

Figure 6.1: Checking website (GOV,UK)

Figure 6.2: Reporting website (GOV,UK)

The healthcare professionals were also asked about online consultation with doctor, because at times people do not get appointments from GP, in this case one of the doctors (interviewee 13) was of similar opinion that the GP surgery and the online consultation website or if advertised on social media should be registered with the NHS, otherwise it is difficult to find out how legal it is. Further he also remarked that online doctors are good for elderly patients who find it difficult to visit the GP and also for follow-up cases it is a good initiative.

Babylone is on the online doctor consultation website, which is also used in UK by many people. Besides the Babylone NHS should come out with online doctors which will help the elderly patients and patients who are busy and suffering from chronic conditions and can't wait for the appointment. In these regards doctor also said that NHS surgeries and pharmacist should inform patients about these online consultation to the patients, so that patients do not get trapped to the online doctors' consultations which are not approved by the NHS. In such case MHRA and NHS in UK play very important role, the same applies to the online pharmacies or websites who are selling medicine and websites dealing with healthcare related information. Thus, for the benefit of the current and future patient and healthcare professional it is essential to promote institutions, specific ethical, legal guidelines in collaboration with patients' associations and professional. (Shabbir Syed-Abdul *et al.*, 2016). However, even on the non-prescription product they should write guidelines, not suitable for long term however it is more of the health regulatory work rather than pharmaceutical companies work. Moreover, even for non-prescription drug when they see the information on social media if it is used by the patient for long it is not good, however if the customer buys from pharmacy he will be usually picked up by the pharmacist but it is bought from the supermarket and the patient does not see any result for long time that's is for say for 3 weeks than he should see a medical practitioner, moreover the regulatory bodies such as MHRA or pharmaceutical company should write and stated not suitable for long term use or for x amount of days.

Healthcare related information

As per Denecke, (2015) social media is encouraging social networking by becoming a tool to gather people together to support healthcare processes by communicating topics related to health. Moreover, as per the literature review and qualitative studies social media has become a source of healthcare information. However according to the findings healthcare related information on social media is may be useful but should not be relied upon as it's not known whether the information is right or wrong however if the patient or customer wants any information on any medicine or on any diseases they can come down to the pharmacy and get the information as the people in pharmacy are qualified and real person not virtual as it is in the social media. Also, information related to healthcare which are available on internet and social media are only for educational purpose and to increase the self-awareness not for diagnoses purpose. Further, social media provides HCPs with tools for sharing and promoting health related information to the patients and public, with an objective to guide

them and educate them by developing a professional network which can keep them motivated (Ventola, 2014). Further, people do buy non-prescription medicines as suggested on social media or on the internet or on any print media. Thus, it can be concluded that people search social media and internet to get healthcare related information and also use it to diagnose themselves which can be potentially dangerous.

Reasons for buying over the counter drugs/medicines from the internet pharmacy

The main reason for buying healthcare related products and searching healthcare related information over the internet is because the internet is considered an alternative source for gaining information related to healthcare and healthcare products. Moreover, the reason for considering internet as an alternative source is because of many deficiencies and irregularities in the medical services, which include long waiting list and long waiting time, doctor's shortage etc. which has led people to search for effective and efficient ways of treating their diseases. Furthermore, online health information and drug sales with home delivery can be lifesavers for the elderly, ill, handicapped, or isolated consumers. Besides this, the other reasons for buying from online sources or online pharmacies includes discounted or low prices, the virtual anonymity, and home delivery facilities (Spain *et al.*, 2001). Moreover, as per Gurau (2005) the old and the elderly people are in particular more attracted by the convenience offered by the internet or the web.

Figure 6.3: Age and gender of people buying medicine from the online sources (ONS, 2019)

Moreover, even in UK, as per ONS (2019) (fig. 6.4) it was found that people 28% of the people who were in the age group 35-44 bought medicine from the online pharmacies or the internet, and 16% of the people in the age group 18-24, 18% in the age group 45-54 also purchased medicines from the internet. Furthermore, the percentage of female to male for buying medicine from online pharmacy was 18% to 15%. When during the interview in the qualitative research the healthcare professional such as pharmacist did say that people do buy medicine from the online pharmacy and internet. However, people buy for reasons such as convenience, in some cases even anonymity, but convenience did play a major role. So as the pharmaceutical industry is becoming more digitalized, it is very important that these companies implement changes in their value chains and prevent disruptive innovation.

Convenience

As per Gurau,(2005) for the elderly, people who are ill, handicapped, and those who are isolated getting health related information from social media and home delivery from online pharmacies of prescription and non-prescription medicine can be lifesavers, besides these reasons, customers are also attracted to convenience, low prices, anonymity, home delivery promised, moreover even in the interview it was convenience is one of reason people why buy on line as when people are busy they don't want to go to the pharmacy and prefer to order from online pharmacy, also being anonymous is a big issue, people who suffer from sexually transmitted infections etc want to remain anonymous so can prefer to buy from

online pharmacy. As per Spain *et al.*, (2001) the main reasons of using internet for health related products is because of deficiencies in medical system such as long waiting list to get an appointment, shortage of doctors and low service quality, have forced people to find different ways to treat their diseases, so convenience can be attributed for buying medical products from internet pharmacy. Gurau (2005) says despite strict regulations, online sales of prescription and non-prescription medicines is growing, reason being customer satisfaction, as internet is an attractive channel for the health-related information and for purchasing healthcare related products (Kanungo, 2004).

Non-prescription medicine

As per the NICE (2014) non-prescription medicines and over-the-counter products are known as homely remedies. These can be bought without a prescription from a pharmacy or supermarket. As it is already stated in the last paragraph people do buy medicines from in the internet pharmacy, this was also expressed by one of the interviewee, so it can be said people do buy over the counter medicine from online sources. Moreover, as per Fung *et al.* (2004), an internet-based vendor that sells prescription and non-prescription medicines is called as an online pharmacy and it includes both legitimate and illegitimate pharmacies. Further, Independent Internet-only sites, online branches of “brick-and-mortar” pharmacies, and sites representing partnership among pharmacies fall under the purview on “online pharmacies (Desai, 2016). There are thousands of accessible online and internet pharmacies on the web, but the actual size of the market is not known, as very limited or incomplete data is available on the use of online pharmacies or internet based pharmacies in terms of the number, and attitude, and the reason why people are obtaining over-the-counter drugs and other health related products from the internet based pharmacies or the online pharmacy.

Challenges

According to NHS (2018) as more people use the internet to understand their health issues, some also go online to buy prescription medication. But many online pharmacies are unregistered, so buying from them is potentially unsafe and could also be dangerous to the health because the medicine might be out-of-date, diluted or fake, there are lots of challenges in buying medicines from the internet pharmacy or the online pharmacy. Similar things were even expressed by one of the pharmacist during the interview that online pharmacy is potentially dangerous and unreliable, and people should not buy from them.

During the past two decades it is been noted that the internet has become an accepted way to purchase products and services. Similarly, buying medications online are no exception. It has been seen that consumers who are engaged in self-diagnosing their health conditions are the one who procure medicines from such online pharmacies. Furthermore, purchasing medications from these online pharmacies can be very dangerous to the life as there is no guarantee of quality or safety (Forman *et al.*, 2006).

Reliability/misleading information

Reliability/misleading information is an important issue in the buying healthcare related product or even for searching information relating to medicine or disease. Thus as per Shabbir Syed-Abdul *et al.* (2016) although social media is used as a source of health information, and accordingly Shabbir Syed-Abdul *et al.* (2016) is of the opinion that the information obtained is generally of lower quality, and can be even unreliable, similarly there are lots of risks involved with using Twitter for healthcare discourse, the major risk are misinformation or misleading information and also it is very difficult to verify the credibility of source as high volumes of information is available on Twitter (Pershad, 2018). Accordingly, similar things were expressed by few of the interviewees that online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, store base pharmacy is better, but people do buy because of convenience or at times because of price.

Information security

Information security was one of the important factors in the online marketing of any product same can be applied to online pharmacy as it is not known how the information which is supplied by the customer is used. As per Blanchard (2019), many health websites sell people's personal health related search data these also include Google, Amazon and Facebook without the people's consent, breaching British data protection laws, similar was also brought about in the interviews that these online pharmacies and share personal information of the people.

Internet

As per Pershad, (2018) in spite of fake information on the social media or digital media and other internet channels but over the counter medicines are easily accessible on the internet pharmacies, thereby making it a protentional source to improve the patient care and wellbeing. Thus, in the age of television and internet, digital medicine has created dilemma of balancing accuracy but has made medicine much more accessible and has reduced the

imbalance between the healthcare provider and patient. Thus, as per the qualitative data local pharmacy is more reliable as it can give face to face interaction, whereas in online pharmacy a consumer cannot contact them case of any side effect, they will come to the local pharmacy. Besides its benefits, several patient safety risks are linked to the purchase of medicines outside the traditional supply chain. Moreover, use of illicit online or internet based pharmacies are basically very risky for the wellbeing of the patients and a threat to patient safety and public health as most of these websites are not regulated, and do not have the required license, these online pharmacies market pharmaceutical products such as vaccines, non-communicable disease medicines, essential medicines that too without any prescription (Mackey, 2013).

This section showed how social media has an impact on the pharmaceutical consumers and customers by assessing the functions and the effectiveness of social media using the qualitative approach. Further, the qualitative study also revealed that GP surgery should provide the list of authorized online pharmacies, so that the consumer do not fall for unreliable online pharmacies, as lot of consumers buy non-prescription drugs from the online pharmacy as they feel it is very convenient, and also few of them feel it makes than anonymous. One of the interviewees also that people nowadays use online doctors as they say they don't get timely appointment at GP surgery. so if a patient is not able to get an appointment at the GP surgery, there should be a provision from the for the online doctors and video consultation, as it becomes easier for the patients and he will not look around the internet for the other option available, besides there can also be provision for online GP consultation at the community pharmacies as they are opened till late and people can consult them easily, which should be brought to the notice of the patients and customers.

6.3 Answering the research questions

Q1. How social media is changing the face of marketing especially in the pharmaceutical industry?

For the pharmaceutical companies to be successful, relationship marketing is very necessary as rightly opined by Samaha et al. (2014) as relationship marketing plays an important role in increasing the business profitability and business performance. Moreover, as per Neff (2014) pharmaceutical companies are increasingly engaging with customers by using the social media marketing. Moreover, as per Hudson *et al.* (2016, p.28):

“To leverage the interactive and engagement dimensions of social media, more and more marketers have changed their marketing objectives, focusing on building/maintaining a desirable consumer–brand relationship via social media interaction”.

Furthermore, from the literatures it is very much evident that the changing the face of marketing is not only in the pharmaceutical industry but also in other industries, however pharmaceutical industry being a regulated industry; was very late in accepting social media (Enyinda *et al.*, 2018).

Further social media research has reported that almost 86 per cent of marketers feel that the for the strategic marketing initiatives social media channels have become critical components (Stelzner, 2013), to create lead generation, sales promotion, moreover the consumers looking for the over the counter medicine are increasingly turning to social media channels for not only health related information but also non-prescription and prescription drugs from internet based pharmacy. Thus, social media has become an important marketing channel to sell over the counter pharmaceutical and health-care related product. As a result, the pharmaceutical firms want to engage with their ultimate consumers. Thus, it can be concluded that social media channels are transforming pharmaceutical and health-care marketing. Further, on seeing the popularity of social media, wherein Facebook has at 2.06 billion monthly active users, YouTube at 1.5 billion, WhatsApp at 1.3 billion and Facebook Messenger at 1.3 billion, pharmaceutical companies have adopted social media network and channels, to promote their products and services (Azer, 2017). Despite the associated risk, pharmaceutical products are on social media as the over-the-counter (OTC) drugs. Companies such as Novartis is already promoting its OTC drugs on social media to improve the sales (Markets and Markets.com,

2010). Although, social media is not free from challenges and risks, but there are huge opportunities for both pharmaceutical and health-care professionals, seeing these opportunities pharmaceutical companies have started promoting their products and services. However, the industry is yet to fully grasp the depth of these relationships, as trust very important in pharmaceutical and healthcare industry. Thus, it can be concluded that this growing importance of computer mediated communications in form of social media, will definitely bring a change in the way the pharmaceutical companies are connecting and interacting with consumers and customers. Besides, this as per the quantitative study it was seen that respondents used social media for the healthcare related information, and also used online pharmacy to buy pharmaceutical /healthcare products.

Q2. How social media is impacting the pharmaceutical industry?

Pharmaceutical industry has always been a technological driven, knowledge oriented and regulated industry and social media is an online platform for interactions and used for actively sharing information. through this online platform healthcare topics such as “patient education”, “health promotion”, “public relations”, and “crisis communication”, etc are communicated, with the view to provide transparency of information between doctors and patients, social media in healthcare is of interest (Shabbir Syed-Abdul *et al.*, 2016). Thus, there are many challenges, on engaging with social media, yet several pharmaceutical companies have already been cautiously using it for one-way communication (Aitken *et al.*, 2014) rather than engaging with HCPs and patients for the last many years. Despite many challenges there are also huge opportunities for the pharma companies (Enyinda, 2011) which can be created by providing social support, disease awareness campaigns etc by providing healthcare information. Further pharma on social media has helped pharmaceutical companies create trust with patients, moreover patients are wanting additional health related information and are becoming more involved in their health decisions.

Furthermore, as per Shankar and Li (2014) with the aid of social media marketing, pharmaceutical companies will help the customers and understand the market in the most cost-effective manner. Thus, through this new channel the firms can reach the customers easily which otherwise could had been difficult through the traditional channel, further it also provides WOM communication to increase the sales and which in turn increase the returns on investment. Seeing the current scenario people are increasingly influenced by the social media is in their search for information on health-related topics (Cordos *et al.*, 2017) such as

information on diseases and treatment, support and self-management of disease by educating themselves on a disease and treatment as they rely on the social media (Benetoli *et al.*, 2017). Different social media channels are networking, with patients and public (Aitken *et al.*, 2014) with an objective to gain access to these communities, thus aiding the pharmaceutical marketers to get connected with their customer through these social media communities (Clark and Melancon, 2013) thus transferring powers from the companies to the consumers (Felix *et al.*, 2017). The pharmaceutical companies thereby leveraging on different social media channels to get connected with the tech savvy consumers. Although, social media is an one of the important source of healthcare information, but one must be careful while using foe health related information (Bhaskaran *et al.*, 2017). Further, as per Anscombe *et al.* (2015) the pharmaceutical customers are more interactive and livelier and engaging to a digital world in comparison to the customers in other industries.

Moreover, as per Marsh (2019) Guardian reported that the social media marketing and online pharmacies do not carry out proper ID checks and use inappropriate marketing tactics to sell strong opiate drugs. Besides, two major UK online pharmacies registered with the were sending emails to customers urging them to order drugs by claiming stocks are running out. As per Antheunis *et al.* (2013), majority of the people use Twitter for knowledge, information and advice, but Facebook is normally used for social support and exchanging health information, whereas professionals mainly relied on LinkedIn. Besides, just the healthcare related information and communication, the social media and the Web platforms exchange user-generated content, which add complexity to pharmaceutical companies. Through the social media these pharmaceutical companies can quickly reach variety of consumers online and market them with their promotional content. Further, pharmaceutical companies' also have official social media accounts containing drug information and it is this place where the consumers are exposed when they search for health related information.

**Q3. How social media will influence consumer intention in pharmaceutical Industry?
What are the factors which influence the pharmaceutical consumers?**

Social media plays a very important in the marketing communication, moreover, over the past two decades it has been observed, that internet and social media have emerged out as a selling and distribution channel, by influencing the todays customers, to an open sources health

related information. As a result, De Martino *et al.*,(2017) consumers have started relying heavily on social media channels to get health-related information such as medicines, health behaviour change, disease and treatment-related information to educate themselves in understanding their health related condition. Furthermore, Griffiths *et al.* (2015) is of the opinion that social media is not only sharing information relating to health conditions in terms of “symptoms”, “diagnosis”, “treatment”, and “adverse effects”, experienced medical evidence, but also providing community health care. Moreover, it is illegal to sell the prescription drugs over the Internet, but over the counter drugs and related products such as food supplements in form of vitamins are available on the internet as it they are legal to sell. It has been reported that social media and online communities of patients have offered several advantages to consumers, that it has influenced the consumers, as it is one of the most convenient way for accessing health related information user-friendly; improved their health knowledge; empowered them; and provided social and emotional support as it as interactive and also participatory as there are several platform for health-related discussions (Tonsaker *et al.*, 2014). This participatory nature and interactive platforms have become useful for the people living with chronic diseases and thus has facilitated patients’ and healthcare professionals’ (HCPs) to communicate in one of the easiest and interested manner. Thus, it can be seen that social media has drastically changed the way in which people communicate with one another on health related issues, resulting in new opportunities and challenges to the healthcare sector (Kapoor *et al.*, 2017). Thus, social media being a versatile and user-friendly platforms has brought about a drastic change in health communication.

As per the primary studies that is quantitative studies as well as the qualitative it is noted that people do search internet and social media and social networking sites to get health related information as it is one of most convenient way to get health related information in keeping themselves informed, they also feel they can get all information by hiding their identity that is by being anonymous. Besides this, as per the qualitative study, people who are busy and do not have time to go to the community pharmacy do buy over the counter medicine such as cough expectorant, pain killers and multivitamins from the online pharmacies help. Thus, as per the primary studies it was found that people do buy over the counter medicines on the online pharmacy.

Q4. What type of diverse products/information is social media normally used for, in the pharmaceutical industry and who are major the customers who buy medicine from online sources and their age group?

The Internet has already become an established source for health information and is growing left right and centre. Moreover, as per Pohjanoksa-Mäntylä *et al.* (2010) people are increasingly turning towards Twitter and Facebook for medicines and to share information related to health and treatments (Pershad *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, using Twitter for healthcare is not risk free as it contains lot of fake information, which is difficulties to verify, but it allows patients, healthcare professionals, and researchers to be more informed; however, people should always adhere to specific guidelines for appropriate use. In spite of all these risks and challenges 9 to 20% of the medicine user in Finland use internet to gain health related and medicine related information. These medicine user were mainly suffering from long-term diseases such as mental disorders. It was also found that among the most frequently searched topics online was mostly mental health-related, as people with mental disorders were dissatisfied with the information provided by their health professionals, so they are the people who searched information over the internet anonymously to avoid stigmatisation (Pantic, 2014).

Figure 6.4: Medicine-online-purchasing-in-great-britain-by-demographic (Source: www.statista.com)

Besides as per ONS (2019) it can also be noted that the women, and people between a group 35 to 44 the age are the major purchaser of medicine from online sources this is clear from fig 6.5 and fig 6.6, this is also seen clear from the qualitative and quantitative research. Further as per the qualitative study as well as the quantitative studies it was found that convenience was the major reason, however after convenience the next major reason for buying from online source was price and being and anonymous, which is also noted from the literature. According to the qualitative research it was reported by some of the pharmacist said that normally the medicines purchased from the internet or online pharmacy are non-prescription drugs however as per them it was also highlighted that even non-prescription drug should not use for long time the symptoms do not reduce. It is already known that nonmedical use of prescription drugs is risky, however internet pharmacies do offer prescription drugs without a prescription, thus creating an illegal source of illicit drugs to anyone with an Internet connection (Festinger *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 6.5: Share of individuals who have used the internet to search for health care information in the United Kingdom in 2015

Figure 6.6: Share of individuals who have used the internet to search for health care information in the United Kingdom in 2015

According to the secondary research it was found that normally the female between the age group 35 years to 40 years purchase medicine from the online pharmacy, also based on primary research that is by the Spearman's rho correlation it was concluded that age does have an impact on the on buying medicine /related product from online pharmacy from the internet sources, that is only specific age group people buy or search medicine /related product from internet or from online sources. Even in the qualitative research it was found that people buy over the counter medicine from the online pharmacy. Moreover it is also confirmed as per the office for national statistics (ONS, 2019) it was found that people of age group in between 35 to 44 are the people who normally buy medicine from online sources also from the online pharmacy, this is also confirmed from the ordinal regression carried out by the researcher. Further as per Inciardi *et al.*,(2010) prescription drugs are already available on the Internet, but very little information is known about the purchase of medications from internet without a legitimate prescription, and who procures these non-prescribed drugs through internet shops (Inciardi *et al.*, 2010).

Moreover, internet and social media communities offer a valuable source of peer support, emotional support and also treatment information from health professionals such as a

qualified clinician. Besides, social media can also aid in behaviour change and enables patients to communicate with other patients and share information about health issues. Furthermore, many of the respondents stressed that because of the limited time in doctor consultations it is not possible to discuss certain issues, here the Internet was particularly useful for gaining health related information (Chu *et al.*, 2017). Consumers chose to get health information via the Internet because of the convenience of seeking information and this was agreed by all respondents. Convenience of Web-based health information is ease to access and is available at any time, and any location, however this was not possible with accessing traditional health services. Thus, this increased use of the Internet for health related information suggests the need for health care professionals to optimally utilized and to improve them.

6.4 Summary

This chapter was on the discussion part of the thesis, accordingly the outcomes of the qualitative and quantitative research was disused vis-à-vis the secondary sources such literature and other government documents, it was people did search health related information from the social media and other internet sources, besides based on the information they did buy non- prescription drugs from the internet and online pharmacy. The reason for buying non-prescription drugs from internet pharmacy was convenience being that they found, other factors were also considered such as price or anonymity, but as the qualitative study most of the pharmacist were of the opinion that convenience played a major role, some did say anonymity price can also be responsible factor, but the main factor was convenience. Most of the people who normally purchased over the counter medicine om online pharmacy were females in the age group 35 to 44, which was also brought forward by the primary study that females normally used online pharmacy to bur over the counter medicines. Besides both the gender did search healthcare related information on the social media and diagnosed their symptoms. Moreover as per the qualitative studies it was also brought forwards that the consumers and patients etc were informed by their GP surgery to use only the authorised online pharmacy , but as the lot of people are not aware of the authorised online pharmacy it was suggested that the GP surgeries provide patients with the list of the authorised online pharmacy so that people only use them rather than getting across the fake online pharmacy.

7 CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION, LIMITATION & RECOMMENDATION

7.1 Introduction

The main purpose of this chapter is to draw the conclusion and suggest recommendations based on the major findings. Most of the research questions were met either by quantitative analysis or by quantitative analysis. As per the literature review it was found that the way marketing was done is changing and now consumer and company both want to be in online setting, pharmaceutical industry although being a technological driven has online pharmacies and has also started promoting health related information and products on social media and on social media marketing. As per qualitative study it was found Pharmaceutical consumers buy over the counter medicine because of convenience but qualitative study inferred that convenience was one of the things people were also looking besides data security.

7.2 Conclusion

Thus, based on the study it was found that customers do search social media websites to get health related information and also many a times based on the information they get from the internet, websites and social media they actually end up buying the medicines and healthcare related products from online pharmacy. Based on the information obtained from the social media and website even buy over the counter medicine non-prescription medicine however as per the qualitative research it was found that it will not be safe if even the non-prescription medicines/drugs are used for long duration without any cure. Although buying the healthcare related product that is non-prescription medicines through the online pharmacy is considered to be safe but should not be used for long time if desired effects are not seen, however buying prescription drugs from online sources should be avoided. Besides convenience was the major reason for buying non-prescription drugs from online pharmacy. Thus, through this study it was found that people of all group did search or buy healthcare related products over the internet or on the social media, but only specific age group people used the internet or on the social media to search or buy healthcare related products. But most important thing was people of all the age and both the genders were concerned about the safety and security of their data over the social media. Thus, based on spearman's correlation following was the result of the hypothesis were accepted (Table 7.1)

Table 7.1: Results of Spearman's correlation

Relation between age and of the purchaser who buys medicine /related product from online pharmacy	Accepted Relation positive	is
Relations between age and convenience for buying online.	Accepted, relation positive	is
Relation between age and price for buying from online pharmacy	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relation between age and choice for buying from online	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relation between age and cumulative scores of various reasons for buying from online pharmacy.	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relation between age and information security as a risk factor of buying medicine online.	Accepted, Relation negative	is
Relation between ages on healthcare information from the internet	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relation between age and their healthcare app usage	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relationship between age and additional charges incurred from buying medicine from online sources	Accepted, Relation positive	is
Relation between age of the person who search health and medicine related information on the social media.	Accepted, Relation positive	is

Similarly, based on the Chi Square test following was the result of the hypothesis were accepted (table 7.2) that is both the gender use the social media for health-related information, but only the people of specific age purchased pharmaceutical related products from the online pharmacy.

Table 7.2: Results of Chi Square test

Hypotheses	Results
Associations between Gender and Using Social Media for healthcare related information.	Accepted
Relationship between age and convenience	Accepted
Associations between age and choice	Accepted
Associations between age and purchaser of medicine	Accepted
Associations between and Price	Accepted
association between age and anonymity	Accepted

Thus it can be based on the finding from qualitative and quantitative it was revealed that although in many other countries direct to consumer advertising of prescription drugs is allowed and is carried on by the pharmaceutical companies on the social media and other internet media, however in the UK because of the strict regulation of MHRA, direct to consumer advertising of prescription drugs is not allowed but the pharmaceutical companies can advertise their non-prescription over the counter drugs on the social media and internet media. Moreover it was also found information security of the patients data was considered to be one of the risk factors when sharing the information over the inter pharmacy, but yet consumers ignored it , as they felt it was easy to buy over the counter medicine from the internet or online pharmacy. So as per qualitative study it was concluded that convenience was the main reason for buying over the counter drugs from the online pharmacies, most of the interviewee said that men who were busy purchased over the counter drugs from online pharmacy, however the quantitative study shows that gender does not has any relation in buying from online pharmacies, whereas it's the age which played an important role in purchasing the medicines from online pharmacies. Further the GPs did say that lot of patients searched information on disease or probable medicines before they visited them, this was confirmed from the quantitative analysis as well. Even the ordinal regression gave a significant result. Thus, it was concluded that age did had an association with the various variable used in the study and the study was reliable which was proved by the Cronbach alpha the value of which was 0.63. Besides, both the genders searched health related information from the social media, and this was found by both qualitative and quantitative analysis.

7.3 Contribution of the study

7.3.1 Introduction:

The contribution made by the research have highlighted the significant information relating to social media in pharmaceutical industry and healthcare industry pertaining to the UK consumers.

The study examined influence of social media marketing on the UK consumers, accordingly the Internet and various online channels have become source for health related information, and the number of individuals who using the Internet for health information are growing day in and day out. Therefore, as the internet, social media provides vast amount of information, some can be genuine and some may not be correct, so relying on all information available on the internet should be done very carefully. Moreover, as this study is on the social media marketing and healthcare / pharmaceutical industry, and how it can impact the pharmaceutical customers, it was seen that lot of people search for healthcare related information on the internet on the websites such as Wikipedia and social media which is not considered to be very genuine and safe, besides people are also consulting the online doctors as people do not get the appointment at the GP easily and buying medicine from the many online pharmacy as they feel it is convenient rather than going to the community pharmacy and purchasing it.

Based on this the recommendation which were brought about as a suggestions from the healthcare professionals during the course of interview were that the GP surgery should have leaflets for the patients which provides the details of online pharmacy and online doctors, also the websites from where the patients can get the information related any medicine or diseases as it was found out during the course of interview and also from the literature review that most of the patients and also general people search for information related to their diseases on the social media and different website. Further at the GP surgery level, if a patient is not able to get an appointment, there should be a provision for the online doctors and video consultation, as it becomes easier for the patients and he will not look around the internet for the other option available, besides there can also be provision for online GP consultation at the pharmacy level as they are opened till late and people can consult them easily. Besides this it should be brought to the notice of the patients and customers that the pharmacy and the GP surgeries also hold online and video consultation, so the customers do not look around for information from the internet and social media. moreover, the patients should be informed

either by leaflets or by the way of posters etc. in the GP surgery and at the pharmacy level and even by the way of advertisement on the television and newspapers or in the tubes and trains and buses by the way of posters that their GP surgery are providing for them online consulting. All this can help the patients from searching information on the social media and on the different websites which may not be always correct.

Furthermore, as per (Blanchard, 2019) it was reported in an investigation that some health related websites in UK were sharing search personal health data to with companies such as Google, Amazon and Facebook etc, and this amounts to breaching British data protection laws as sensitive data is shared without people's consent. 79 out of 100 sites were implicated in the Financial Times investigation including WebMD, BUPA, Healthline, and the British Heart Foundation. So it can be seen that peoples information is not safe, In such a case if the NHS and GP surgery should give information to their patients on their website site and this should be informed to the patients that instead of searching health related information on third party website, the patients can search it on the NHS website. There can also be a provision for chat on the NHS website wherein if the patients feel lost on reading the information provided it can chat with the paramedical staff or nurses who can be on the other end get their query solved.

7.3.2 Contribution to knowledge

This study has adopted an mixed method of data analysis by interviewing 14 healthcare professional, consisting of doctors and pharmacists from United Kingdom, the data was analysed using thematic analysis, and 384 general people from United Kingdom were selected using random sampling to study their buying behaviour of generic or over the counter medicine or pharmaceutical product from the online sources for quantitative study however only 200 response met the requirement. On analysing the finding of the study, it was found that, the study made a key contribution in understanding of acceptance of social media and social media marketing by the UK pharmaceutical products consumers Moreover, the study also contributed in understanding how the UK pharmaceutical product consumer use of social media for getting healthcare related issues and also on over the counter medicines, thus the study helped to understand the usage, benefits, risks and challenges for the UK consumers of pharmaceutical industry. The findings of the study have also provided an insight or information on the influences of social media marketing on the different UK customers and consumers. Further, the study also provided an insight on gender, age, and experience,

education level, health conditions of the consumers and also the different reasons to use social media networks, social media forums and social media marketing. This study basically involves UK consumers and UK pharmaceutical industry, so the findings of the obtained from study is in reference to pharmaceutical industry of UK. Moreover, through this study various factors and reasons were identified, why the people used social media in health related topics and also in relations to pharmaceutical product in the pharmaceutical industry. Further it was found that people found it convenient and easy to get information related to healthcare and pharmaceutical product, and further they also relied on the information they obtained from the social media network, and channels, the reason for relying on the information obtained from social media in the pharmaceutical industry was that they trusted, moreover they also found it was one of the most easiest source of getting the information on healthcare, that too when it was difficult to get appointments of the GP with waiting time of over a week, under such circumstances they relied on the information obtained from the social media and purchased the over the counter drug/ medicines from the online shops or online pharmacy. Further the major finding in this study was that people of specific age were the major user of social media marketing and social media for healthcare and pharmaceutical product, however gender was not the major factor, based on the study people of both the genders searched social media marketing and social media for healthcare and pharmaceutical product. Further it was found that people have accepted social media and social media marketing or healthcare related products finding it to be the most convenient and easy sources. Thus, it can be said that information technology in form of social media, internet media has facilitated the dissemination of information relating to healthcare products in an easy convenient and in a rather quick manner. Moreover, these findings can be generalised from situation to situation and place to place and industry to industry. Further the consumers are also aware that although social media and social marketing are convenient and quick means to get information and make purchase but they are not risk free, so they should always be cautious and careful while making any purchase relating to pharmaceutical products should always make a note that the source where they are getting the information is authentic and the online pharmacy is an approved pharmacy. Moreover, the customers /stakeholders of the pharmaceutical industry should always be aware of risks and benefits of information provided by social media and product bought from online pharmacy. Thus, this study is not a just academic research but also important for the general public, as it provides helpful information relating to risks associated with social media for healthcare related and pharmaceutical products.

Figure 7.1 Contribution of findings to theory

7.3.3 Contribution to the Society

The main objective or the purpose of this research was basically to address the issues dealing with the safety of the human life when decisions relating to health care are taken, related to healthcare information displayed on social media. It can be said that as there so many website and channels, there can be lack of reliability and also uncertainty in the information which is being displayed in the different social media channels and websites and online pharmacy where people do buy healthcare related products based on the information obtained from the digital media. As, a result, to create awareness about the use of social media and online pharmacy relating to the safety of human health and human rights, this research has played a very important and a significant role by contributing to understand the various facts and factors that go to play an important role in motivating and demotivating the pharmaceutical consumers from using social media and online pharmacy from using health forums and to

buy over the counter drugs/medicines by UK consumers of pharmaceutical industry. Though this research it has provided an understanding to the general UK pharmaceutical consumers to check the authenticity of the website and online pharmacy before using for their health related needs. So that such platforms can be useful and lifesaving instead of being a disaster to once life. Furthermore, as per Ventola, (2014) on examination of the various prevailing literature, it was found that usually social media should not be easily relied upon as the sources of subjects related to healthcare and pharmaceutical online pharmacy can be distrustful. Thus, it can be said that the government agencies and pharmaceutical companies should focus on providing genuine information on the social media relating to healthcare and also on the over the counter medicine online shops and pharmacies thereby making it a credibility source. Further, through this study there is a need to even regularise the information provided by pharmaceutical companies to their consumers about health-related issues. Moreover, even Attuquayefio and Addo, (2014); Khechine *et al.*, (2014) is of the opinion a true and useful data and check should be made that all online pharmacy are approved the medical regulatory agencies which is very helpful for the general public to take effective healthcare related decisions. Besides through this research it was brought out that illegal online pharmacy can also inappropriate and can play with the confidential data of the people. Further through this study Denecke *et al.*, (2015) the people should understand the importance of health related decisions and should only purchase over the counter drugs or medicine only after getting correct information and not just based on the information obtained from social media or internet. Thus, it also shows that there a need for not just reliable information related to over the counter medicine and health related information, but also medical agencies approved online pharmacy along with pharmacists and physicians who can be connected the patients as and when needed. Further, Kaba and Toure, (2014) the study also dealt with various issues that restrict the consumers from using social media as a reliable source health related information and reliable online pharmacy. As this study is based on the impact of social media marketing on UK consumers it is important that they have safe experience dealing with the technology improve social situations. Moreover, with the help of this study it can create an awareness that people should be more careful and cautious when using social media marketing for health related problems as there are many misleading information on such media, so they should use the information only for knowledge purpose and not for self-diagnosis (Abubakar *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, Rolls *et al.*, (2016) the research has raised an awareness on the authenticity of health information and online pharmacy, which go to show regulatory body should take more care on this section. Besides as the people and consumers have been using

social media for health related information and use online pharmacy the regulatory bodies should bring out new laws and reforms the related topics so that consumers will safe. Thus, through this research, the researcher wants to improve the health and lifestyle of the society and all the people using social media and social media marketing for health related activities and want them to use this technology with utmost care.

Figure 7.2 contribution of the study to the society

7.4 Recommendations

The recommendation which are based on this study are for the following:

1. MHRA to make guidelines and hold workshops for the patients to inform them that they should not buy medicines from an unknown online pharmacy.
2. In order to stop people from buying medicines from online pharmacy, because of the information obtained from the social media, GP surgeries if cannot give face to face appointment to the patient should at least telephonic appointment or a video consultation.
3. There should online consultation app from National health services which is like Babylone app so that consumers can get timely services from national health service which prevent them from searching health related information on the internet, and then based on the information purchase medicines from the online pharmacy.
4. As the GP surgeries are opened only from 8am to 5pm, so there should be a provision at the community pharmacies for GPs, so that people can visit them when the surgeries are closed.
5. Consumers should avoid using over the counter drugs for longer duration if they don't find any results.
6. People normally buy from online pharmacy because it is convenient, but they should be warned about the risk associated with it.

7.5 Limitation and Future Work

The findings of the study have been interpreted in the light of certain limitations, as they can be opportunities for the future research. One of the major limitation of this study is the age of respondents, as most of the respondents were in the age group in between 20 to 45 for the quantitative study. So, the study may not give much information on people above the age of 45 years. Besides this, the quantitative study was conducted in Wolverhampton but as it was very difficult to get an interview with any healthcare professional in the Wolverhampton so the qualitative studies was conducted with any doctor or pharmacist who were available to give an interview in the whole of the UK as it was difficult to find doctors and pharmacist who were ready to give interview in Wolverhampton, so whole of UK as taken for sampling for the qualitative research. The future work should be based on the risk that are involved on the purchasing of over the counter drugs from online pharmacy based on the information obtained from internet and social media.

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9 APPENDIX :

9.1 Appendix-1 Quantitative Questionnaire

INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN A RESEARCH

Date:

Dear

Invitation to participate in doctorate research

I am Shubhra Nigam, I am a Doctorate student with the University of west of Scotland, I am currently carrying out a doctorate research on “ **To study of the influence of Social media in in Pharmaceutical Industry On UK Consumer**” under the supervision of Dr David. I would like to invite you to participate in a structured questionnaire relating to the above research based on your experience. The questionnaire will investigate the key benefits, motivation factors to the customers of the online marketing activities and marketing communication and information of products and disease. The questionnaire would last around 10-15 minutes. Please note that your response will be treated as highly confidential and transcripts will not contain references to any personal details or organisations. A further detail about the research is in the Information Sheet which is attached to this invitation letter. Should you be willing to participate, please fill in the attached Consent Form? Please inform me your available dates and times for the filling up the questionnaires. The summary of the results of this study will be available after the research. Thank you very much for your consideration of this invitation. Your participation is highly valued as it will contribute to improving online marketing / digital marketing activities of pharmaceutical companies.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours Sincerely,

Shubhra Nigam

Doctorate Researcher

University of West of Scotland,

London Campus. London Website: www.uws.ac.uk

University email add: [REDACTED]

Please tick the appropriate box that best describes your answer and give answers to questions without options

Research Questionnaire for digital marketing

1. Respondent Details

1. What your Gender? - nominal

Male	
Female	
Prefer not to say	

2. How old are you? - ordinal

18 – 29	
30-39	
40 – 49	
50 and above	

3. What is your disposable income per month? ordinal

Less £49	
£50-99	
£100- 149	
£150-199	
More than £200	

4. What is your employment status? (tick the

appropriate box) - nominal

Employed Full time	
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Employed Part-time	
Temporary staff	
Contract staff	
Unemployed	
Self employed	
Student	

5. Please tick the appropriate box (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- never, 2 - Occasionally, 3 - sometimes, 4 - often, 5- always) - ordinal

	1	2	3	4	5
Do you use Internet?					
Do you use social media					
Do you use digital marketing /online marketing?					
Do you make online purchase					
To get feedback /opinion of other customer					
Information about the product and services					

6. How long have you been using social media for product information? ordinal

Type of social media	Don't use (1)	Less than 3 months (2)	3-6 months (3)	1-2 years (4)	More than 2 years (5)
Facebook					
Twitter					
Instagram					
LinkedIn					

7. ordinal

	Clothes (1)	Electronic (2)	Cosmetics (3)	Shoes (4)	Groceries (5)
Do you get information on the social media any of the products (please tick)					
What products do you normally buy from online sources? (please tick)					

8. (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- never, 2 - Occasionally, 3 - sometimes, 4 - often, 5- always)

	1	2	3	4	5
Do you look for information about pharmaceutical product and related services online?					

9. Which social media or online or Apps do you normally use to search information regarding healthcare product (medicine) knowledge about any disease or related services and how often (Tick the appropriate box) (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- never, 2 - Occasionally, 3 - sometimes, 4 - often, 5- always)

Type of social media	1	2	3	4	5
Facebook					
Twitter					
Instagram					
LinkedIn					
Company website					
Wikipedia					
Apps relating to information on Healthcare					

10. What type of pharmaceutical product or related services you search online or on social media (Tick the appropriate box) (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- never, 2 - Occasionally, 3 - sometimes, 4 - often, 5- always)

	1	2	3	4	5
Online consultation and prescription					
Just consultation no prescription					
Over the Counter medicine					
Just information on the prescription drugs					
Information about certain disease.					
information online or on social media about symptoms of any disease					
Information on adverse effect of any drugs					
Do u search information online or on social media before visiting doctor					

11. Please give your opinion (Tick the appropriate box) (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Agree, 5- Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
In your opinion the information given on social media/ digital marketing about pharmaceutical / healthcare products can be trusted					
In your opinion is it safe to purchase pharmaceutical product online?					
In your opinion is it safe to relay on the information given about a pharmaceutical product and related service online?					
Do you purchase pharmaceutical product /related service online or from social media					
In your opinion is it safe to purchase pharmaceutical product /related service online					

12. Do you buy pharmaceutical products / service online because of the following advantages if yes (tick the appropriate box) (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- strongly disagree , 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Agree, 5- Strongly Agree)

Perceived advantages of buying online	1	2	3	4	5
Price					
Choice					
Convenience					
Anonymity					
Information					

13. Are you aware of the risk associated with online purchase of pharmaceutical products (tick the appropriate box) (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Agree, 5- Strongly Agree)

Associated risk with online purchase	1	2	3	4	5
Lack of proper licence					
Quality of product					
Additional charges					
Security of the data being sold					
Genuineness of the person who is giving prescription					

14. tick the appropriate box (Rate from 1 to 5, 1- Strongly Disagree, 2 - Disagree, 3 - Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4 - Agree, 5- Strongly Agree)

	1	2	3	4	5
Besides using online or social media do u also use any app for getting healthcare information:					

Are you happy with your overall experience of using internet/social media in getting information about any healthcare related product or service? please

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Thank you for your time...!!

9.2 Appendix II - Qualitative Questionnaire

Dear Healthcare professionals,

I am carrying out a research at the University of West of Scotland on the Topic, “**To critically study the influence of social media / digital media as a source of marketing communication and health information in healthcare industry and its impact on the consumers.**” The study is carried out under the supervision of Dr David. Chitakunye I would like to invite you to participate in a semi-structured open-ended interview relating to the above research based on your experience.

This interview will investigate how the internet, social media and mobile healthcare related apps are impacting the patients /consumers in healthcare industry. The interview would last around 10 – 15 minutes. Please note that your responses will be treated as highly confidential and transcripts will not contain references to any personal details (including yourself) or organisations.

Please see the attached interview questions. Should you be willing to participate, please email me your available dates and times for the interview. The summary of the results of this study will be available at the conclusion of the research. Should you wish to obtain a copy of these, please let me know? Thank you very much for your consideration of this invitation.

I look forward to hearing from you.

Yours sincerely,
Shubhra Nigam

Doctorate Researcher
Faculty of Social Science
University of West of Scotland

Introduction:

The aim of this study is to describe the impact of digital media marketing/social media in healthcare industry as a source of marketing communication and health information and its influence on the patients/consumers. Thus, this research aims to study the opinion from a healthcare professional on how this digital media/social media/internet etc. will have an impact on the consumers/patients.

Date	
Name of interviewee	
Email address	
Position of Interviewee	
Name of organisation	
Organisation's sector	

Interview Questions

This section will focus on general questions related to social media/online marketing in healthcare /pharmaceutical industry and its impact on the and patient engagement

1. The engagement of healthcare /pharmaceutical industry in the digital media such as having a company's official page on Facebook or Twitter or having a website which gives information about the brands and drugs and diseases, adverse drug reaction, is this information beneficial for the consumers.

- if beneficial
- if not why?

Kindly give your opinion.

As per academic journals and academic papers it has been reported that people before going to GP or doctor or a pharmacist, do a lot of research online on what they might be suffering from and what can be the probable medicine for it. Have you ever come across such patients?

So, in your opinion does this really helps the consumer.

2. The consumer being laymen, they do not have much technical knowledge on disease or medicine, so in your opinion will the information on disease or medicine available on the social media or any other website be helpful or will be misleading. (kindly comment)

3. Although DTCA (direct to consumer advertising) by Pharmaceutical company is only legal in USA and New Zealand, but as it is on the internet people from across the globe has access to it. Here the companies advertise their prescription as well as OTC brands to the consumers. What opinion do you have regarding it. Kindly give your opinion regarding this.

4. According to a 2015 survey by researchers at New York University's Langone Medical Centre, fifty-eight percent of mobile phone users have downloaded at least one Mobile Health app (mHealth app), and 41% have downloaded more than five apps. In is your opinion are these apps helpful for the consumer.

- If yes, then how they are helpful
- If No, then how.

Based on your experience, kindly give your opinion.

5. It is already a well-known fact that there are lot of online pharmacy internet pharmacy, some are legal, and some are illegal, and even the people in UK have access to it. So in your opinion do people in UK buy medicines from these online pharmacies, if why do they buy from online source.

Is it because of

- convenience,
- cost effective,
- Choice
- Anonymity

Besides this in your opinion buying medicines from online pharmacy can be safe and what medicines are normally purchased from online sources (kindly comment)

6. You must be aware of online consultation or online prescription, and how safe are they. In your opinion do consumers use them, if yes what can be the probable reasons for using them. Please give your opinion on it.

Thank you.

9.3 Appendix III: Descriptive statistics

Age of the respondents:

AGE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-29 years old	99	49.5	49.5	49.5
	30-39 years old	63	31.5	31.5	81.0
	40-49 years old	30	15.0	15.0	96.0
	50 years and above	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

3. Gender of the respondents

GENDER					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	115	57.5	57.5	57.5
	Female	85	42.5	42.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

4. Monthly disposable income

DISPOSABLE INCOME					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1	29	14.5	14.5	14.5
	2	46	23.0	23.0	37.5
	3	55	27.5	27.5	65.0
	4	35	17.5	17.5	82.5
	5	35	17.5	17.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

5. Employment status of the respondent

EMPLOYMENT STATUS					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Employed Full time	74	37.0	37.0	37.0
	Employed Part time	38	19.0	19.0	56.0
	Self-employed	12	6.0	6.0	62.0
	unemployed	6	3.0	3.0	65.0
	Student	70	35.0	35.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

6. Do the respondent use Internet

USE INTERNET					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Sometimes	10	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Often uses internet	61	30.5	30.5	35.5
	Always	129	64.5	64.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

7. Number of respondent using Social media.

USE SOCIAL MEDIA					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Occasionally	51	25.5	25.5	29.0
	Sometimes	72	36.0	36.0	65.0
	Often	51	25.5	25.5	90.5
	Always	19	9.5	9.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

8. Number of respondents using Internet marketing.

USES INTERNET MARKETING					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	8	4.0	4.0	4.0
	Occasionally	48	24.0	24.0	28.0
	Sometimes	66	33.0	33.0	61.0
	Often	54	27.0	27.0	88.0
	Always	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

9. Number of respondents using social media to get the feedback about a product from another user.

USE SOCIAL MEDIA FOR PRODUCT FEEDBACK OF ANOTHER CONSUMER					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	14	7.0	7.0	7.0
	Occasionally	59	29.5	29.5	36.5
	Sometimes	59	29.5	29.5	66.0
	Often	40	20.0	20.0	86.0
	Always	28	14.0	14.0	100.0

	Total	200	100.0	100.0	
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USE SOCIAL MEDIA FOR PROUCT INFORMATION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	31	15.5	15.5	15.5
	Occasionally	61	30.5	30.5	46.0
	Sometimes	64	32.0	32.0	78.0
	Often	31	15.5	15.5	93.5
	Always	13	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

10. Respondents searching healthcare relating information on the company website.

SEARCH HEALTHCARE COMPANY WEBSITE FOR PRODUCT INFORMATION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	4	2.0	2.0	2.0
	Occasionally	23	11.5	11.5	13.5
	Sometimes	101	50.5	50.5	64.0
	Often	48	24.0	24.0	88.0
	Always	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

11. Does the respondent search information relating to the healthcare product on the Wikipedia?

SEARCH WIKIPEDIA TO FIND OUT HEALTHCARE PRODUCT INFORMATION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never use	2	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Occasionally	34	17.0	17.0	18.0
	Sometimes	122	61.0	61.0	79.0
	Often	39	19.5	19.5	98.5
	Always	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

12. Does the respondent search information about the medicine and related healthcare products on the social media?

SEARCH INFORMATION ABOUT MEDICINE ON THE SOCIAL MEDIA					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5

	Occasionally	26	13.0	13.0	16.5
	Sometimes	93	46.5	46.5	63.0
	Often	61	30.5	30.5	93.5
	Always	13	6.5	6.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

13. Does the respondent search information on the internet about the adverse drug reaction?

SEARCH FOR INFORMATION ON MEDICINE SUCH AS ADVERSE DRUG REACTION					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	occasionally	57	28.5	28.5	32.0
	often	132	66.0	66.0	98.0
	sometimes	4	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

14. Does the respondent search about the disease online?

SEARCH INFORMATION ABOUT DISEASE ONLINE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Occasionally	34	17.0	17.0	20.5
	Often	112	56.0	56.0	76.5
	Sometimes	42	21.0	21.0	97.5
	Always	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

15. Do the respondent search information on disease based on symptoms or probable medicine before visiting the doctor.

SEARCH INFORMATION ON DISEASE OR PROBABLE MEDICINE BEFORE VISITING THE GP					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	2	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Occasionally	28	14.0	14.0	15.0
	Sometimes	80	40.0	40.0	55.0
	Often	45	22.5	22.5	77.5
	Always	45	22.5	22.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

16. Respondent's perception of the safety of information given on the social media relating to the healthcare related product.

SAFETY OF INFORMATION GIVEN ON THE SOCIAL MEDIA					
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		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Not very safe	28	14.0	14.0	14.0
	Not safe	72	36.0	36.0	50.0
	Neither safe nor not safe	80	40.0	40.0	90.0
	Safe	20	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

17. Do the respondent purchase healthcare related product or medicine from online pharmacy

PURCHASE THE MEDICINE THROUGH THE ONLINE PHARMACY					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	disagree	48	24.0	24.0	32.0
	neither Agree nor disagree	101	50.5	50.5	82.5
	Agree	32	16.0	16.0	98.5
	Strongly Agree	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

18. Is price the reason for buying the medicines or healthcare product from online pharmacy?

REASONFOR BUYING ONLINE- PRICE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	88	44.0	44.0	44.0
	Disagree	80	40.0	40.0	84.0
	neither agree nor Disagree	24	12.0	12.0	96.0
	agree	8	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

19. Is convenience the major reason for buying the medicine or healthcare related product from online pharmacy?

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -CONVENIENCE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	33	16.5	16.5	24.5
	Neither agree nor disagree	83	41.5	41.5	66.0
	agree	44	22.0	22.0	88.0

	Strongly agree	24	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

20. Do the respondents by choice buy the medicine or related products from online pharmacy?

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -CHOICE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	15	7.5	7.5	7.5
	disagree	76	38.0	38.0	45.5
	neither agree nor disagree	88	44.0	44.0	89.5
	agree	18	9.0	9.0	98.5
	Strongly agree	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

21. Does being anonymous the main reason for buying from online pharmacy.

REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -ANONYMITY					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	12	6.0	6.0	6.0
	disagree	57	28.5	28.5	34.5
	neither agree nor disagree	85	42.5	42.5	77.0
	agree	41	20.5	20.5	97.5
	Strongly agree	5	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

22. Is the information that's being given by the respondent to online pharmacy is secured.

IS THE INFORMATION SECURED					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	67	33.5	33.5	33.5
	Disagree	67	33.5	33.5	67.0
	neither agree nor disagree	52	26.0	26.0	93.0
	agree	14	7.0	7.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

23. Is the respondent aware of the risk associated with buying healthcare products from online pharmacy?

AWARE OF THE RISK WHICH ARE ASSOCAITED WITH ONLINE PURCHASE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	37	18.5	18.5	18.5
	disagree	70	35.0	35.0	53.5
	neither agree nor disagree	77	38.5	38.5	92.0
	agree	16	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

24. Is respondent aware that the online pharmacy may not be having a licence.

LACK OF LICIENCE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	46	23.0	23.0	23.0
	Disagree	89	44.5	44.5	67.5
	Neither agree nor Disagree	63	31.5	31.5	99.0
	agree	2	1.0	1.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

25. The quality can be issue of the healthcare related product with online pharmacy.

QUALITY OF THE MEDICINE WHICH IS BROUGHT ONLINE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	55	27.5	27.5	27.5
	Disagree	92	46.0	46.0	73.5
	neither agree nor Disagree	50	25.0	25.0	98.5
	agree	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

26. There might be additional charges when buying from online pharmacy.

ADDITIONAL CHARGES					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	100	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Disagree	24	12.0	12.0	62.0
	neither agree nor disagree	76	38.0	38.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

27. Is the respondent aware that the person giving information or prescription on the online pharmacy may or may not be genuine?

PERSON GIVING THE INFORMATION AND PRESCRIPTION GENUINE					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	7	3.5	3.5	3.5
	Disagree	15	7.5	7.5	11.0
	neither agree nor disagree	138	69.0	69.0	80.0
	agree	19	9.5	9.5	89.5
	Strongly agree	21	10.5	10.5	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

28. Is the respondent using the healthcare app?

RESPONDENT USES THE HEALTHCARE APP					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	9	4.5	4.5	4.5
	Occasionally	68	34.0	34.0	38.5
	Sometimes	86	43.0	43.0	81.5
	Often	31	15.5	15.5	97.0
	Always	6	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

29. Do the respondent satisfied with digital media in healthcare related product?

SATISFIED WITH DIGITAL MEDIA IN HEALTHCARE RELATED PRODUCT					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	16	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Disagree	44	22.0	22.0	30.0
	neither agree nor disagree	79	39.5	39.5	69.5
	agree	45	22.5	22.5	92.0
	Strongly agree	16	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	200	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive statistic:

Statistics						
		Age	Gender	Disposable Income	Employment Status	Use Internet
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		1.74	1.43	3.01	2.80	4.60
Median		2.00	1.00	3.00	2.00	5.00
Mode		1	1	3	1	5

Statistics						
		Use Social Media	Uses Internet Marketing	Use Social Media For Feedback Of Another Consumer	Use Social Media For Product Information	Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.12	3.19	3.05	2.67	3.33
Median		3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Mode		3	3	2 ^a	3	3

Statistics						
		Search Wikipedia To Find Out Healthcare Product Information	Search Information About Medicine On The Social Media	Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy	Search For Information On Medicine Such As Adverse Drug Reaction	Search Information About Disease Online
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.04	3.24	2.46	2.67	3.02
Median		3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00
Mode		3	3	2	3	3

Statistics						
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		Search Information On Disease Or Probable Medicine Before Visiting The GP	Safety Of Information Given On The Social Media	Purchase The Medicine Through The Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors	Reason For Buying Online-Price	Reason For Buying Online - Convenience
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.52	2.46	2.79	1.76	3.14
Median		3.00	2.50	3.00	2.00	3.00
Mode		3	3	3	1	3

Statistics						
		Reason for buying online choice	Reason for buying online anonymity	Information on security	Aware of the risk which are associated with online purchase	Lack of licence
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.59	2.85	2.07	2.36	2.11
Median		3.00	3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00
Mode		3	3	1 ^a	3	2

Statistics						
		Quality of the medicine which is brought online	Additional charges	Person giving the information and prescription genuine	Respondent uses the health app	Satisfied with digital media in healthcare related product
N	Valid	200	200	200	200	200
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.01	1.88	3.16	2.79	3.01
Median		2.00	1.50	3.00	3.00	3.00
Mode		2	1	3	3	3

a. Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown

**APPENDIX 2
CHI SQUARE TEST:**

Crosstabs

Notes		
Output Created		21-JAN-2021 03:20:50
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
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	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY CONVINIENCERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW COLUMN TOTAL /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.40
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent

AGE RECODED *	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%
CONVINIENCE RECODED						

AGE RECODED * CONVINIENCE RECODED Crosstabulation

		CONVINIENCE RECODED		Total	
		DISAGREE, DISAGREE NEUTRAL	AGREE STRONGLY AGREE		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	47	115	162
		Expected Count	39.7	122.3	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	29.0%	71.0%	100.0%
		% within CONVINIENCE RECODED	95.9%	76.2%	81.0%
		% of Total	23.5%	57.5%	81.0%
AGE RECODED	40-59	Count	2	36	38
		Expected Count	9.3	28.7	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	5.3%	94.7%	100.0%
		% within CONVINIENCE RECODED	4.1%	23.8%	19.0%
		% of Total	1.0%	18.0%	19.0%
Total		Count	49	151	200
		Expected Count	49.0	151.0	200.0
		% within AGE RECODED	24.5%	75.5%	100.0%
		% within CONVINIENCE RECODED	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% of Total	24.5%	75.5%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
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Pearson Chi-Square	9.385 ^a	1	.002		
Continuity Correction ^b	8.145	1	.004		
Likelihood Ratio	11.907	1	.001		
Fisher's Exact Test				.001	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.338	1	.002		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.31.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.217	.002
	Cramer's V	.217	.002
N of Valid Cases		200	

```
RECODE price (1=1) (2=1) (3=2) (4=2) (5=2) INTO PRICERECODED.
VARIABLE LABELS PRICERECODED 'PRICE RECODED'.
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```
EXECUTE.
```

```
CROSSTABS
```

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  /TABLES=AGERECODED BY PRICERECODED
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  /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
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  /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
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  /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
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  /COUNT ROUND CELL.
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Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created	21-JAN-2021 03:27:48	
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	Split File	<none>

	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY PRICERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.01
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	N	Valid		Cases Missing		N	Total	
		Percent		Percent			Percent	
AGE RECODED * PRICE RECODED	200	100.0%		0	0.0%	200	100.0%	

AGE RECODED * PRICE RECODED Crosstabulation

		PRICE RECODED		Total	
		SD, D, N	A, SA		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	141	21	162
		Expected Count	136.1	25.9	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	87.0%	13.0%	100.0%
40-59	Count	27	11	38	
	Expected Count	31.9	6.1	38.0	

	% within AGE RECODED	71.1%	28.9%	100.0%
Total	Count	168	32	200
	Expected Count	168.0	32.0	200.0
	% within AGE RECODED	84.0%	16.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.851 ^a	1	.016		
Continuity Correction ^b	4.723	1	.030		
Likelihood Ratio	5.179	1	.023		
Fisher's Exact Test				.025	.019
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.822	1	.016		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.08.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.171	.016
	Cramer's V	.171	.016
N of Valid Cases		200	

RECODE choice (1=1) (2=1) (3=2) (4=2) (5=2) INTO CHOICERECODED.

VARIABLE LABELS CHOICERECODED 'CHOICE RECODED'.

EXECUTE.

CROSSTABS

/TABLES=AGERECODED BY CHOICERECODED

/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES

/STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI

/CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW

/COUNT ROUND CELL.

Crosstabs

Notes

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	Active Dataset	DataSet1
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	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY CHOICERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.00
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.01
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	N	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED * CHOICE RECODED	200	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED * CHOICE RECODED Crosstabulation

		CHOICE RECODED		Total	
		SD,D,N	A,SA		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	81	81	162
		Expected Count	73.7	88.3	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	40-59	Count	10	28	38
		Expected Count	17.3	20.7	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	26.3%	73.7%	100.0%
Total	Count	91	109	200	
	Expected Count	91.0	109.0	200.0	
	% within AGE RECODED	45.5%	54.5%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	6.963 ^a	1	.008		
Continuity Correction ^b	6.040	1	.014		
Likelihood Ratio	7.256	1	.007		
Fisher's Exact Test				.011	.006
Linear-by-Linear Association	6.928	1	.008		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 17.29.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.187	.008
	Cramer's V	.187	.008
N of Valid Cases		200	

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RECODE anonimity (1=1) (2=1) (3=2) (4=3) (5=3) INTO ANONIMITYRECODED.
VARIABLE LABELS ANONIMITYRECODED 'ANONIMITY RECODED'.
EXECUTE.
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```
CROSSTABS
```

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  /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
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  /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
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/CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
/COUNT ROUND CELL.

Crosstabs

Notes

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	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY ANONIMITYRECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.01
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Cases	
Valid	Missing	Total

	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED * ANONIMITY RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED * ANONIMITY RECODED Crosstabulation

		ANONIMITY RECODED				
		1.00	2.00	3.00	Total	
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	57	76	29	162
		Expected Count	55.9	68.9	37.3	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	35.2%	46.9%	17.9%	100.0%
	40-59	Count	12	9	17	38
		Expected Count	13.1	16.2	8.7	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	31.6%	23.7%	44.7%	100.0%
Total	Count	69	85	46	200	
	Expected Count	69.0	85.0	46.0	200.0	
	% within AGE RECODED	34.5%	42.5%	23.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.662 ^a	2	.001
Likelihood Ratio	12.696	2	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.052	1	.025
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.74.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.261	.001
	Cramer's V	.261	.001
N of Valid Cases		200	

```

CROSSTABS
  /TABLES=AGERECODED BY ANONIMITYRECODED
  /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
  /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
  /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
  /COUNT ROUND CELL.

```

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		21-JAN-2021 03:59:00
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY ANONIMITYRECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.05
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED * ANONIMITY RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED * ANONIMITY RECODED Crosstabulation

		ANONIMITY RECODED			Total	
		DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	57	76	29	162
		Expected Count	55.9	68.9	37.3	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	35.2%	46.9%	17.9%	100.0%
AGE RECODED	40-59	Count	12	9	17	38
		Expected Count	13.1	16.2	8.7	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	31.6%	23.7%	44.7%	100.0%
Total		Count	69	85	46	200
		Expected Count	69.0	85.0	46.0	200.0
		% within AGE RECODED	34.5%	42.5%	23.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.662 ^a	2	.001
Likelihood Ratio	12.696	2	.002
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.052	1	.025
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.74.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.261	.001
	Cramer's V	.261	.001
N of Valid Cases		200	

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		21-JAN-2021 04:31:36
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY ADDITIONALCHARGERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.02
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED * AD CHARGE RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED * AD CHARGE RECODED Crosstabulation

		AD CHARGE RECODED		Total	
		1.00	2.00		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	105	57	162
		Expected Count	100.4	61.6	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	64.8%	35.2%	100.0%
AGE RECODED	40-59	Count	19	19	38
		Expected Count	23.6	14.4	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
Total		Count	124	76	200
		Expected Count	124.0	76.0	200.0
		% within AGE RECODED	62.0%	38.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.867 ^a	1	.090		
Continuity Correction ^b	2.273	1	.132		
Likelihood Ratio	2.805	1	.094		
Fisher's Exact Test				.098	.067
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.853	1	.091		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 14.44.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.120	.090
	Cramer's V	.120	.090
N of Valid Cases		200	

```

CROSSTABS
  /TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY ADDITIONALCHARGERECODED
  /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
  /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
  /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
  /COUNT ROUND CELL.

```

Crosstabs

Notes		
Output Created		21-JAN-2021 04:35:24
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY ADDITIONALCHARGERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.01
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED2 * AD CHARGE RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED2 * AD CHARGE RECODED Crosstabulation

		AD CHARGE RECODED		Total	
		1.00	2.00		
AGE RECODED2	18-29	Count	66	33	99
		Expected Count	61.4	37.6	99.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%
	30-39	Count	39	24	63
		Expected Count	39.1	23.9	63.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	61.9%	38.1%	100.0%
	40-59	Count	19	19	38
		Expected Count	23.6	14.4	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%
Total	Count	124	76	200	
	Expected Count	124.0	76.0	200.0	
	% within AGE RECODED2	62.0%	38.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.238 ^a	2	.198
Likelihood Ratio	3.186	2	.203
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.006	1	.083
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 14.44.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.127	.198
	Cramer's V	.127	.198
N of Valid Cases		200	

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		21-JAN-2021 04:42:27
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED BY searchdbgprecoded /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.03
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

		Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED *	SEARCHDMGP RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED * SEARCHDMGP RECODED Crosstabulation

		SEARCHDMGP RECODED			Total	
		DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE		
AGE RECODED	18-39	Count	22	66	74	162
		Expected Count	24.3	64.8	72.9	162.0
		% within AGE RECODED	13.6%	40.7%	45.7%	100.0%
AGE RECODED	40-59	Count	8	14	16	38
		Expected Count	5.7	15.2	17.1	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED	21.1%	36.8%	42.1%	100.0%
Total		Count	30	80	90	200
		Expected Count	30.0	80.0	90.0	200.0
		% within AGE RECODED	15.0%	40.0%	45.0%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.350 ^a	2	.509
Likelihood Ratio	1.257	2	.533
Linear-by-Linear Association	.733	1	.392
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.70.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.082	.509
	Cramer's V	.082	.509
N of Valid Cases		200	

CROSSTABS

```

/TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY searchdbgprecoded
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
/STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
/CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
/COUNT ROUND CELL.

```

Crosstabs

Notes		
Output Created		21-JAN-2021 04:43:20
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY searchdbgprecoded /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.04
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

		Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED2 *	SEARCHDMGP RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED2 * SEARCHDMGP RECODED Crosstabulation

		SEARCHDMGP RECODED			Total	
		DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	AGREE		
AGE RECODED2	18-29	Count	18	38	43	99
		Expected Count	14.9	39.6	44.6	99.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	18.2%	38.4%	43.4%	100.0%
	30-39	Count	4	28	31	63
		Expected Count	9.5	25.2	28.4	63.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	6.3%	44.4%	49.2%	100.0%
	40-59	Count	8	14	16	38
		Expected Count	5.7	15.2	17.1	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	21.1%	36.8%	42.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	30	80	90	200	
	Expected Count	30.0	80.0	90.0	200.0	
	% within AGE RECODED2	15.0%	40.0%	45.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.582 ^a	4	.233
Likelihood Ratio	6.302	4	.178
Linear-by-Linear Association	.028	1	.867
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.70.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.167	.233
	Cramer's V	.118	.233

N of Valid Cases	200
------------------	-----

```

RECODE purchasemedicinefromonlinesources (1=1) (4=3) (2=1) (3=2) (5=3) INTO
PURCHASEMEDONLINERECODED.
VARIABLE LABELS PURCHASEMEDONLINERECODED 'PURCHASE MED ON RECODED'.
EXECUTE.
CROSSTABS
  /TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY PURCHASEMEDONLINERECODED
  /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES
  /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI
  /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW
  /COUNT ROUND CELL.

```

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		21-JAN-2021 04:49:33
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax	CROSSTABS /TABLES=AGERECODED2 BY PURCHASEMEDONLINERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.	
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03

Elapsed Time	00:00:00.10
Dimensions Requested	2
Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
AGE RECODED2 * PURCHASE MED ON RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

AGE RECODED2 * PURCHASE MED ON RECODED Crosstabulation

		PURCHASE MED ON RECODED			Total	
		DISAGREE	NEUTRAL	DSIAGREE		
AGE RECODED2	18-29	Count	82	15	2	99
		Expected Count	60.4	25.2	13.4	99.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	82.8%	15.2%	2.0%	100.0%
	30-39	Count	38	24	1	63
		Expected Count	38.4	16.1	8.5	63.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	60.3%	38.1%	1.6%	100.0%
	40-59	Count	2	12	24	38
		Expected Count	23.2	9.7	5.1	38.0
		% within AGE RECODED2	5.3%	31.6%	63.2%	100.0%
Total	Count	122	51	27	200	
	Expected Count	122.0	51.0	27.0	200.0	
	% within AGE RECODED2	61.0%	25.5%	13.5%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	121.416 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	110.475	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	86.288	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.13.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.779	.000
	Cramer's V	.551	.000
N of Valid Cases		200	

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		21-JAN-2021 05:05:03
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\User\Desktop\new primary data final1 (1)_1.savoct2019.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	200
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=Gender BY ADDITIONALCHARGERECODED /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ PHI /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.02
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.02

Dimensions Requested	2
Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
GENDER * AD CHARGE RECODED	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

GENDER * AD CHARGE RECODED Crosstabulation

			AD CHARGE RECODED		Total
			SD, D	N	
GENDER	Male	Count	68	47	115
		Expected Count	71.3	43.7	115.0
		% within GENDER	59.1%	40.9%	100.0%
	Female	Count	56	29	85
		Expected Count	52.7	32.3	85.0
		% within GENDER	65.9%	34.1%	100.0%
Total	Count	124	76	200	
	Expected Count	124.0	76.0	200.0	
	% within GENDER	62.0%	38.0%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (1- sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.946 ^a	1	.331		
Continuity Correction ^b	.681	1	.409		
Likelihood Ratio	.950	1	.330		
Fisher's Exact Test				.378	.205
Linear-by-Linear Association	.941	1	.332		
N of Valid Cases	200				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 32.30.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	-.069	.331
	Cramer's V	.069	.331
N of Valid Cases		200	

```

PLUM cumulativesocialmedia BY Gender Employment Income WITH Age
/CRITERIA=CIN(95) DELTA(0) LCONVERGE(0) MXITER(100) MXSTEP(5)
PCONVERGE(1.0E-6) SINGULAR(1.0E-8)
/LINK=LOGIT
/PRINT=FIT PARAMETER SUMMARY TPARALLEL.
    
```

HYPOTHESIS 1

Association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

H0: there is no association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

H1: there is association between gender and information security of the patients in social media

Case processing summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * information security	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Information Security of The Patients in Social Media							
Cross Tabulation							
			Information Security				Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	43	36	29	7	115
		Expected Count	38.5	38.5	29.9	8.0	115.0
	Female	Count	24	31	23	7	85

		Expected Count	28.5	28.5	22.1	6.0	85.0
Total		Count	67	67	52	14	200
		Expected Count	67.0	67.0	52.0	14.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.998 ^a	3	.573
Likelihood Ratio	2.013	3	.570
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.306	1	.253
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.95.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.100	.573
	Cramer's V	.100	.573
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 2: Association between gender and looking for healthcare related product on the Social Media.

H0: There is no association between gender and Social Media in Healthcare Related Product.

H1: There is association between gender and Social Media in Healthcare Related product.

case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Satisfied with Social Media In Healthcare Related Product	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.007 ^a	4	.734
Likelihood Ratio	1.988	4	.738
Linear-by-Linear Association	.038	1	.845
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.80.

Gender * Satisfied with Social Media in Healthcare Related Product Cross tabulation								
			Satisfied with social Media In Healthcare Related Product					Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	
Gender	Male	Count	7	27	46	27	8	115
		Expected Count	9.2	25.3	45.4	25.9	9.2	115.0
	Female	Count	9	17	33	18	8	85
		Expected Count	6.8	18.7	33.6	19.1	6.8	85.0
Total		Count	16	44	79	45	16	200
		Expected Count	16.0	44.0	79.0	45.0	16.0	200

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.100	.734
	Cramer's V	.100	.734
N of Valid Cases		200	

Hypothesis 3: Association between Gender and Genuineness about the Information and Prescription in Social Media

H0: There is no association between gender and Genuineness about the Information and Prescription in Social Media.

H1: There is association between gender and Genuineness about the Information and Prescription in Social Media.

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent

Gender * Person Giving the Information And Prescription Genuine	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%
---	-----	--------	---	------	-----	--------

Gender * Genuineness about the Information and Prescription in Social Media cross tabulation								
		Person giving the information and prescription genuine					Total	
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree		
Gender	Male	Count	5	9	76	10	15	115
		Expected count	4.0	8.6	79.4	10.9	12.1	115.0
	Female	Count	2	6	62	9	6	85
		Expected count	3.0	6.4	58.7	8.1	8.9	85.0
Total		Count	7	15	138	19	21	200
		Expected count	7.0	15.0	138.0	19.0	21.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.778 ^a	4	.596
Likelihood Ratio	2.876	4	.579
Linear-by-Linear Association	.195	1	.658
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.98.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.118	.596
	Cramer's V	.118	.596
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 4: Association between Gender and Satisfied With Social Media in Healthcare Related Product

H0: There is no association between gender and Satisfied with information on Social Media for the Healthcare Related Product.

H1: There is association between gender and Satisfied with information on Social Media for the Healthcare Related Product.

Case Processing Summary

			Valid		Cases Missing		Total	
			N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	*	Satisfied With Digital Media In Healthcare Related Product	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

GENDER * Satisfied With Social Media In Healthcare Related Product Cross tabulation

			Satisfied With Social Media In Healthcare Related Product				Total	
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	neither agree nor disagree	agree	Strongly agree	
Gender	Male	Count	7	27	46	27	8	115
		Expected Count	9.2	25.3	45.4	25.9	9.2	115.0
	Female	Count	9	17	33	18	8	85
		Expected Count	6.8	18.7	33.6	19.1	6.8	85.0
Total		Count	16	44	79	45	16	200
		Expected Count	16.0	44.0	79.0	45.0	16.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.007 ^a	4	.734
Likelihood Ratio	1.988	4	.738
Linear-by-Linear Association	.038	1	.845
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.80.

Symmetric Measures

			Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal	by	Phi	.100	.734
Nominal		Cramer's V	.100	.734
N of Valid Cases			200	

HYPOTHESIS 5: SIGNIFICANT

Association between gender and additional charges incurred while buying the healthcare related product on the social media.

H0: There is no association between gender and Satisfied with information on Social Media for the Healthcare Related Product.

H1: There is association between gender and Satisfied with information on Social Media for the Healthcare Related Product

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	* Additional Charges	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Additional Charges Crosstabulation						
			Additional Charges			Total
			Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	
Gender	Male	Count	50	18	47	115
		Expected Count	57.5	13.8	43.7	115.0
	Female	Count	50	6	29	85
		Expected Count	42.5	10.2	32.3	85.0

Total	Count	100	24	76	200
	Expected Count	100.0	24.0	76.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.896 ^a	2	.050
Likelihood Ratio	6.066	2	.048
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.743	1	.098
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 10.20.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.172	.052
	Cramer's V	.172	.052
N of Valid Cases		200	

Hypothesis 6: Association Between Gender And who considers Risk is Associated With shops on social media/Online Purchase Of Medical Products.

H0: There is no association between gender and Risk Associated with Online Purchase of Medical Products.

H1: There Is Association Between Gender And Risk Associated With Online Purchase Of Medical Products.

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Aware Of The Risk Which Are Associated With Online Purchase	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Aware Of The Risk Which Are associated With Online Purchase Crosstabulation

			Aware Of The Risk Which Are Associated With Online Purchase				Total
			Strongly disagree	disagree	neither agree nor disagree	agree	
Gender	Male	Count	19	41	43	12	115
		Expected Count	21.3	40.3	44.3	9.2	115.0
	Female	Count	18	29	34	4	85
		Expected Count	15.7	29.8	32.7	6.8	85.0
Total		Count	37	70	77	16	200
		Expected Count	37.0	70.0	77.0	16.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.697 ^a	3	.441
Likelihood Ratio	2.818	3	.421
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.166	1	.280
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.80.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.116	.441
	Cramer's V	.116	.441
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 7:

Association between Gender and Anonymity being the Reason for buying pharmaceutical products through the social media.

H0: There is no association between gender and Anonymity being the Reason for Buying through the social media.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Anonymity being the Reason for Buying through the social media.

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Reason For Buying Online - Anonymity		200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Reason For Buying Online -Anonymity Cross tabulation								
		Reason For Buying Online -Anonymity					Total	
		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree Nor Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree		
Gender	Male	Count	6	32	49	26	2	115
		Expected Count	6.9	32.8	48.9	23.6	2.9	115.0
	Female	Count	6	25	36	15	3	85
		Expected Count	5.1	24.2	36.1	17.4	2.1	85.0
Total		Count	12	57	85	41	5	200
		Expected Count	12.0	57.0	85.0	41.0	5.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.534 ^a	4	.821
Likelihood Ratio	1.530	4	.821
Linear-by-Linear Association	.266	1	.606
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.13.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.088	.821
	Cramer's V	.088	.821
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 8: Association between Gender and perception safety of doctors online and on social media

H0: There is no association between gender and perception of safety of doctors online and on social media.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and perception of safety of doctors online and on social media.

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Purchase The Medicine Through The Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors		200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * online doctors cross tabulation								
		online pharmacy/online doctors					Total	
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree		
Gender	Male	Count	9	29	54	22	1	115
		Expected count	9.2	27.6	58.1	18.4	1.7	115.0
	Female	Count	7	19	47	10	2	85
		Expected count	6.8	20.4	42.9	13.6	1.3	85.0
Total		Count	16	48	101	32	3	200
		Expected count	16.0	48.0	101.0	32.0	3.0	200

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	3.224 ^a	4	.521
Likelihood Ratio	3.270	4	.514
Linear-by-Linear Association	.037	1	.848
N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.28.			
Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.127	.521
	Cramer's V	.127	.521

N of Valid Cases	200	
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HYPOTHESIS 9: Association between Gender and convenience being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online.

H0: There is no association between gender and convenience being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and convenience being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
GENDER * REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE CONVENIENCE -	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * reason for buying online -convenience cross tabulation								Total
		Reason for buying online -convenience						
		Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree		
Gender	Male	Count	8	21	46	24	16	115
		Expected count	9.2	19.0	48.3	24.7	13.8	115.0
	Female	Count	8	12	38	19	8	85
		Expected count	6.8	14.0	35.7	18.3	10.2	85.0
Total		Count	16	33	84	43	24	200
		Expected count	16.0	33.0	84.0	43.0	24.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.010 ^a	4	.734
Likelihood Ratio	2.033	4	.730
Linear-by-Linear Association	.287	1	.592

N of Valid Cases	200		
a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.80.			

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.100	.734
	Cramer's V	.100	.734
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 10: Association between Gender and choice being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online.

H0: There is no association between gender and choice being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and choice being the reason for buying the medical product on social media/ online

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * Reason For Buying Online -Choice	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Reason For Buying Online -Choice Crosstabulation								
			REASON FOR BUYING ONLINE -CHOICE					Total
			Strongly disagree	disagree	neither agree nor disagree	agree	Strongly agree	
Gender	Male	Count	9	46	51	9	0	115
		Expected Count	8.6	43.7	49.4	11.5	1.7	115.0
	Female	Count	6	30	35	11	3	85
		Expected Count	6.4	32.3	36.6	8.5	1.3	85.0
Total		Count	15	76	86	20	3	200
		Expected Count	15.0	76.0	86.0	20.0	3.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.775 ^a	4	.217
Likelihood Ratio	6.834	4	.145
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.425	1	.119
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.28.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.170	.217
	Cramer's V	.170	.217
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 11: Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP.

H0: There is no association between gender and searching information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP

Case processing summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	* search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP cross tabulation								
			Search information on disease or probable medicine before visiting the GP				Total	
			Never	Occasionally	Sometimes	Often		Always
Gender	Male	Count	0	17	45	23	30	115
		Expected count	1.2	16.1	46.0	25.9	25.9	115.0
		Count	2	11	35	22	15	85

	Female	Expected count	.9	11.9	34.0	19.1	19.1	85.0
Total		Count	2	28	80	45	45	200
		Expected count	2.0	28.0	80.0	45.0	45.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.174 ^a	4	.270
Likelihood Ratio	5.924	4	.205
Linear-by-Linear Association	.899	1	.343
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .85.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.161	.270
	Cramer's V	.161	.270
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 12: Association between Gender and Safety Of Information related to disease or medicine Given On The Social Media.

H0: There is no association between gender and Safety of Information related to disease or medicine Given On The Social Media.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Safety Of Information related to disease or medicine Given On The Social Media

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	* Safety Of Information Given On The Social Media	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Safety Of Information Given On The Social Media Crosstabulation							
			Safety Of Information Given On The Social Media				Total
			Not Very Safe	Not Safe	Neither Safe Nor Not Safe	Safe	
Gender	Male	Count	17	42	43	13	115

		Expected Count	16.1	41.4	46.0	11.5	115.0
	Female	Count	11	30	37	7	85
		Expected Count	11.9	30.6	34.0	8.5	85.0
Total		Count	28	72	80	20	200
		Expected Count	28.0	72.0	80.0	20.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.060 ^a	3	.787
Likelihood Ratio	1.067	3	.785
Linear-by-Linear Association	.023	1	.880
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 8.50.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.073	.787
	Cramer's V	.073	.787
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 13: Association between Gender and do they consult the /Online Doctors on social media.

H0: There is no association between gender and consult the Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and consult the Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors.

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * consult Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Online Doctors								
Cross Tabulation								
			Consult The Online Pharmacy/Online Doctors					Total
			strongly disagree	disagree	neither agree nor disagree	agree	strongly agree	
Gender	Male	Count	9	29	54	22	1	115
		Expected Count	9.2	27.6	58.1	18.4	1.7	115
	Female	Count	7	19	47	10	2	85
		Expected Count	6.8	20.4	42.9	13.6	1.3	85.0
Total		Count	16	48	101	32	3	200
		Expected Count	16.0	48.0	101.0	32.0	3.0	200.0
Chi-Square Tests								
			Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-Sided)			
Pearson Chi-Square			3.224 ^a	4	.521			
Likelihood Ratio			3.270	4	.514			
Linear-By-Linear Association			.037	1	.848			
N Of Valid Cases			200					
A. 2 Cells (20.0%) Have Expected Count Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Count Is 1.28.								

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.127	.521
	Cramer's V	.127	.521
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 14: Association between Gender and Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information.

H0: There is no association between gender and Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information.

H1: There Is Association between Gender Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	* Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information Crosstabulation								
			Search Healthcare Company Website For Product Information					Total
			Never	Occasionally	Sometimes	Often	Always	
Gender	Male	Count	3	14	54	28	16	115
		Expected Count	2.3	13.2	58.1	27.6	13.8	115.0
	Female	Count	1	9	47	20	8	85
		Expected Count	1.7	9.8	42.9	20.4	10.2	85.0
Total		Count	4	23	101	48	24	200
		Expected Count	4.0	23.0	101.0	48.0	24.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-Sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.120 ^a	4	.714
Likelihood Ratio	2.169	4	.705
Linear-By-Linear Association	.173	1	.677
N Of Valid Cases	200		

A. 2 Cells (20.0%) Have Expected Count Less Than 5. The Minimum Expected Count Is 1.70.

Symmetric Measures		
	Value	Approximate Significance

Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.103	.714
	Cramer's V	.103	.714
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS 15: Association between Gender and Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy.

H0: There is no association between gender and Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy.

H1: There Is Association between Gender and Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender * purchase of medicine /related product online pharmacy		200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy Crosstabulation								
		Purchase Of Medicine /Related Product Online Pharmacy					Total	
		Never	Occasionally	Often	Sometimes	Always		
Gender	Male	Count	11	56	32	11	5	115
		Expected Count	13.2	56.9	29.3	9.8	5.8	115.0
	Female	Count	12	43	19	6	5	85
		Expected Count	9.8	42.1	21.7	7.2	4.3	85.0
Total		Count	23	99	51	17	10	200
		Expected Count	23.0	99.0	51.0	17.0	10.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.082 ^a	4	.721
Likelihood Ratio	2.082	4	.721
Linear-by-Linear Association	.558	1	.455
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 1 cells (10.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.25.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.102	.721
	Cramer's V	.102	.721
N of Valid Cases		200	

HYPOTHESIS16: Associations between Gender and Using Social Media for healthcare related information.

H0: There is no association between gender and use social media for product information.

H1: There is association between gender and use social media for product information.

Case Processing Summary							
		Cases					
		Valid		Missing		Total	
		N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	* Use Social Media	200	100.0%	0	0.0%	200	100.0%

Gender * Use Social Media for health information Cross tabulation								
			Use Social Media For Health Information					Total
			Never	Occasionally	Sometimes	Often	Always	
Gender	Male	Count	3	26	36	40	10	115
		Expected Count	4.0	29.3	41.4	29.3	10.9	115.0
	Female	Count	4	25	36	11	9	85
		Expected Count	3.0	21.7	30.6	21.7	8.1	85.0
Total		Count	7	51	72	51	19	200
		Expected Count	7.0	51.0	72.0	51.0	19.0	200.0

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.486 ^a	4	.014
Likelihood Ratio	13.217	4	.010
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.042	1	.044
N of Valid Cases	200		

a. 2 cells (20.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.98.

Symmetric Measures			
		Value	Approximate Significance
Nominal by	Phi	.250	.014
	Cramer's V	.250	.014
N of Valid Cases		200	

9.4 Appendix IV Interview Transcripts

What is your opinion why healthcare industry came into social media quite late in comparison to other industry?

Social media being important for healthcare professional, as social media breaks down and help to read the articles easily rather than reading pages and pages on the book, it also helps to read people perception and realistic approach, and how it is impacting people.

But being in a technical sound industry it needed more of legal and ethical requirements that can be the reason that pharmaceutical industry was very late in coming to social media in comparison to other industries.

The engagement of healthcare /pharmaceutical industry in the social media such as having a company's official page on Facebook or Twitter or blogs which gives information about the brands and drugs and diseases, adverse drug reaction, is this information beneficial for the consumers. Kindly give your opinion.

Social media is helpful as it helps to get others person feedbacks and also getting more information instead of reading pages and pages, thus its easier, it helps the consumers/patients, so as I said, as per the pharmacist, I think Social media has good impact on consumer/customer as it is more easier, thus Having a page in social media is fairly helpful for the patient, as whatever they are trying to see it can be easily understood. Thus, the patients get all the information relating any medicine or disease So as a pharmacist i think definitely social media is Benefield for the customers as long as they just use social media for information and educational purpose, if they start using for diagnosing purpose then it will prove to be disastrous which can also lead to complications and eventually result in the death of the person, so it is case specific in some case it may be misleading and in other it will br helpful depending upon how they use. Besides on getting the information which medicine should be used for specific symptoms people should not buy even if it a non- medicine. They should always take opinion of a pharmacist or doctors. Besides I think people normally for use social media to check their symptom and what disease it can be.. however, They normally don't look out adverse drug reaction, but if they are on some specific drug then they want search the probable side effect of the medicine.

Have you come across patient who says he read about the disease on the social media and he feels he is suffering from that disease? As per academic journals and academic papers it has

been reported that people before going to GP or doctor or a pharmacist, do a lot of research online on what they might be suffering from and what can be the probable medicine for it. Have you ever come across such patients? So, in your opinion does this really help the consumer?

I would say so, they do, In a lot of cases it is helpful, as it helps them to research their general medical condition, a lot of people use trusted website such as NHS.com, they're helpful they give specific symptoms etc however if they use non-credible website then it can be misleading. Then it is a problem, non-credible website and medical pages on the social media will be problem as people do a lot of shady work. So yes if it is trusted website people do get correct information. People do look for medical information online and social media at times even to see how worthy the doctor is. For example if a person have rash on the leg they google it , they try to find out what can be it be, but rashes can be due to many things such fungal infection, eczema, so many different type of thing, and they come to conclude they have something whereas they have some other problem, so concluding just based on symptom Is not right, so yeah I have seen lot of people coming to pharmacy and saying they saw this on the website or social media and it seems like eczema, whereas they have fungal infection or some other infection so getting information from the social media is good but self-diagnosing is not right so yea lot of people they do look for information on sm and online.

The consumer being laymen, they do not have much technical knowledge on disease or medicine, so in your opinion will the information on disease or medicine available on the social media or any other website be helpful or will be misguiding. (kindly comment)

The drug information obtained from social media or from blogs etc should be only for information and educational purpose it should be used for diagnoses purpose, as yes, it is correct sometimes people may not understand the technical terms.

Although DTCA (direct to consumer advertising) by Pharmaceutical company is only legal in USA and New Zealand, but as it is on the internet people from across the globe has access to it. Here the companies advertise their as well as OTC brands to the consumers. What opinion do you have regarding it.

Kindly give your opinion regarding this.

It depends really on medication, if it is written by medical professional then may be ok, otherwise can cause a problem if it is straight forward information IT ok but if they are promoting Prescription based products then it should be governed and regulated by authorities

I am talking as per pharmacist prospective a healthcare professional, on the product whether it is Prescription medication or non- medicine, if prescription medicine than it not ethical to promote brand on social media, however for Non Prescription it is ethical as any other consumer product but should be promoted with guidelines. Thus, Advertising non-prescription item is fine, it just should be more accurate information. Unethical Prescription medicine and ethical non-prescription medication.

However even on the non- product they should write guidelines, not suitable for long term however it is more of the Health regulatory work rather than pharma companies work. Moreover even for non-prescription drug when they see the information on social media if it is used by the patient for long it is not good, however if the customer buys from pharmacy he will be usually picked up by the pharmacist but it is bought from the supermarket and the patient does not see any result for long time that's is for say for 3 weeks than he should see a medical practitioner, moreover I think the regulatory bodies such as MHRA should write and stated not suitable for long term use or for x amount of days. Say more than pharmaceutical company it is work of the regulatory body.

It is already a well-known fact that there are lot of online pharmacy internet pharmacy, some are legal, and some are illegal, and even the people in UK have access to it. So, in your opinion do people in UK buy medicines from these online pharmacies, if why do they buy from online source? Is it because of convenience, cost effective, Choice Anonymity

I don't agree with online pharmacy, or any medical product to be purchased online as it may be risky. I think online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, it cannot survive, moreover a patient cannot talk face to face, however people do buy because of convenience. But online pharmacy potentially dangerous store base pharmacy Is better. Thus I think Convenience is the main reason people buy on line as when people are busy they don't want to go to the pharmacy and prefer to order from online pharmacy, however I feel buying from online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, also being anonymous is a big issue, people who suffer from sexually transmitted infections etc want to remain anonymous so can prefer to buy from online pharmacy.

Besides convenience anonymity and price, moreover wide variety of things you can find online food, light, as quite a lot of people at times say I can get it online.

They should not buy any medical product from online pharmacy as it is dangerous, but as it is It is all about convenience or be anonymous or can be cheaper

Like for example lot of people come to my pharmacy and ask for a brand and if I don't have that brand, I say I don't have that brand but a different brand so they say ok. I don't want it I can get it online, If they go to local pharmacy it can give face to face interaction , however I will Online pharmacy alone will only survive, it should be store based lot of people might be taking medicine from online pharmacy, but if there is any side effect they cannot contact online pharmacy, they will come to the local pharmacy, where they will have a face to face talk, so as per me I don't like the concept of online pharmacy.

Besides this in your opinion buying medicines from online pharmacy can be safe and what medicines are normally purchased from online sources (kindly comment)

It depends which online pharmacy the person is buying, if it is registered with MHRA than it ok to buy otherwise it can harm Patient, as there will no proper service, no proper information, the drug can be low standard or not within the therapeutic windows, so buying or non- drug from any online pharmacy is not a right decision as it can even lead a to complications and eventually a patient's death.

You must be aware of online consultation or online , and how safe are they. In your opinion do consumers use them, if yes what can be the probable reasons for using them. Please give your opinion on it.

It great, it is convenience, if the doctor is registered, as it makes things easy and so don't have to wait for the doctor s appointment, where the doctor can consult the patient on the phone and based on the problem they can either be asked to gp, again the in case if the doctor feels that the patient needs physical then they can to referred to the doctor

So in a way it will not take away anything from NHs but will add to NHS for those patient who do not need physical examination. Besides it Is helpful for disabled people. So online consultancy is a good option will add to the NHS. Accuracy of and safety aspect has to take care besides it should follow confidentially. Babylon on hand and GP on hand are app for online consultancy which are legal and registered with GMC and NHS however there might be other online doctors and consultancy which may not be registered so patients should take care to see that they approach the right doctors. Babylon , Guidelines for the patients, educate people on the online pharmacy, either by the NHS can have some leaf let which have the

information about the which are the genuine online pharmacy . As people at times do not get quick appointment so it is needed that the NHS surgery and Local pharmacy should advertise about the genuine online doctors so that people who are busy or cannot wait can get a quick consultation with the genuine doctors. Gp on hand

Transcript Interview

What is your opinion why healthcare industry came into social media quite late in comparison to other industry?

According to me healthcare industry being a technical industry so it came to social media late also there might be some ethical issues that could be the reason.

The engagement of healthcare /pharmaceutical industry in the social media such as having a company's official page on Facebook or Twitter or having a website which gives information about the brands and drugs and diseases, adverse drug reaction, is this information beneficial for the consumers.

Information on Social media about any medicine or disease is helpfully but should not be relied upon as we don't know whether the information is right or wrong however if the patient or customer wants any information on any medicine or on any diseases they can come down to the pharmacy and get the information as the people in pharmacy are qualified and real person not virtual as it is in the social media. So people can look for information on social media but they should not relay on it blindly they should always consult a doctor or a pharmacist before buying any medicine based on the information they get from SC or if they are buying any medicine based on information they got from sc and yet their symptoms are not improving they should consult the doc or pharmacist

Besides getting information from pharmacist will be more reliable and person can be confident rather than when they get information on sm.

If the website is reliable then the information should be right

The type of information the patient looking for from Sm is about the symptoms they have, but at times it may scare them for example

Have you come across patient who says he read about the disease on the social media and he feels he is suffering from that disease?

As per academic journals and academic papers it has been reported that people before going to GP or doctor or a pharmacist, do a lot of research online on what they might be suffering from and what can be the probable medicine for it. Have you ever come across such patients? So, in your opinion does this really help the consumer?

I would say in a way it good as the customer is ware of his symptoms and also is aware what can be the probable medicine which will be prescribe to him but he should not buy nay medicine without the consultation of the pharmacist of the doctors

The consumer being laymen, they do not have much technical knowledge on disease or medicine, so in your opinion will the information on disease or medicine available on the social media or any other website be helpful or will be misleading. (kindly comment)

It is already a well-known fact that there are lot of online pharmacy internet pharmacy, some are legal, and some are illegal, and even the people in UK have access to it. So in your opinion do people in UK buy medicines from these online pharmacies, if why do they buy from online source?Is it because of

- convenience,
- cost effective,
- Choice
- Anonymity

Besides this in your opinion buying medicines from online pharmacy can be safe and what medicines are normally purchased from online sources (kindly comment)

To be fair there fake website and the drug s can be Convience anonymous but not reliable.

You must be aware of online consultation or online prescription, and how safe are they. In your opinion do consumers use them, if yes what can be the probable reasons for using them. Please give your opinion on it.

Online consultation is good and safe way but care should be taken that the online consultation website is a genuine one register with e NHS it I helpful for the patients who are old and cannot travel frequently or where the people are not getting appointment they can go for this mode however this will have some limitation where the physical examination is needed.

What is your opinion why healthcare industry came into social media quite late in comparison to other industry?

Social media being important for healthcare professional, as social media breaks down and help to read the articles easily rather than reading pages and pages on the book, it also helps to read people perception and realistic approach, a how it is impacting people.

But being in a technical sound industry it needed more of legal and ethical requirements that can be the reason that pharmaceutical industry was very late in coming to social media in comparison to other industries.

The engagement of healthcare /pharmaceutical industry in the social media such as having a company's official page on Facebook or Twitter or blogs which gives information about the brands and drugs and diseases, adverse drug reaction, is this information beneficial for the consumers.

Social media is helpful as it helps to get others person feedbacks and also getting more information instead of reading pages and pages, thus its easier, it helps the consumers/patients, so as I said, as per the pharmacist, I think Social media has good impact on consumer/customer as it is more easier, thus Having a page in social media is fairly helpful for the patient, as whatever they are trying to see it can be easily understood. Thus, the patients get all the information relating any medicine or disease So as a pharmacist i think definitely social media is Benefield for the customers as long as they just use social media for information and educational purpose, if they start using for diagnosing purpose then it will prove to be disastrous which can also lead to complications and eventually result in the death of the person, so it is case specific in some case it may be misleading and in other it will br helpful depending upon how they use. Besides on getting the information which medicine should be used for specific symptoms people should not buy even if it a non- medicine. They should always take opinion of a pharmacist or doctors. Besides I think people normally for use social media to check their symptom and what disease it can be. however, they normally don't look out adverse drug reaction, but if they are on some specific drug then they want search the probable side effect of the medicine.

Have you come across patient who says he read about the disease on the social media and he feels he is suffering from that disease? As per academic journals and academic papers it has been reported that people before going to GP or doctor or a pharmacist, do a lot of research online on what they might be suffering from and what can be the probable medicine for it.

Have you ever come across such patients? So, in your opinion does this really help the consumer

I would say so, they do, In a lot of cases it is helpful, as it helps them to research their general medical condition, a lot of people use trusted website such as NHS.com, they're helpful they give specific symptoms etc however if they use non-credible website then it can be misleading. Then it is a problem, non-credible website and medical pages on the social media will be problem as people do a lot of shady work. So yes if it is trusted website people do get correct information. People do look for medical information online and social media at times even to see how worthy the doctor is. For example if a person have rash on the leg they google it , they try to find out what can be it be, but rashes can be due to many things such fungal infection, eczema, so many different type of thing, and they come to conclude they have something whereas they have some other problem, so concluding just based on symptom Is not right, so yeah I have seen lot of people coming to pharmacy and saying they saw this on the website or social media and it seems like eczema, whereas they have fungal infection or some other infection so getting information from the social media is good but self-diagnosing is not right so yea lot of people they do look for information on online.

The consumer being laymen, they do not have much technical knowledge on disease or medicine, so in your opinion will the information on disease or medicine available on the social media or any other website be helpful or will be misleading.

The drug information obtained from social media or from blogs etc should be only for information and educational purpose it should be used for diagnoses purpose, as yes, it is correct sometimes people may not understand the technical terms.

Although DTCA (direct to consumer advertising) by Pharmaceutical company is only legal in USA and New Zealand, but as it is on the internet people from across the globe has access to it. Here the companies advertise their as well as OTC brands to the consumers. What opinion do you have regarding it.

It depends really on medication, if it is written by medical professional then may be ok, otherwise can cause a problem if it is straight forward information IT ok but if they are promoting Prescription based products then it should be governed and regulated by authorities

I am talking as per pharmacist prospective a healthcare professional, on the product whether it is Prescription medication or non- medicine, if prescription medicine than it not ethical to promote brand on social media, however for Non Prescription it is ethical as any other

consumer product but should be promoted with guidelines. Thus, Advertising non-prescription item is fine, it just should be more accurate information. Unethical Prescription medicine and ethical non-prescription medication.

However even on the non- product they should write guidelines, not suitable for long term however it is more of the Health regulatory work rather than pharma companies work. Moreover even for non-prescription drug when they see the information on social media if it is used by the patient for long it is not good, however if the customer buys from pharmacy he will be usually picked up by the pharmacist but it is bought from the supermarket and the patient does not see any result for long time that's is for say for 3 weeks than he should see a medical practitioner, moreover I think the regulatory bodies such as MHRA should write and stated not suitable for long term use or for x amount of days. Say more than pharmaceutical company it is work of the regulatory body.

It is already a well-known fact that there are lot of online pharmacy internet pharmacy, some are legal, and some are illegal, and even the people in UK have access to it. So in your opinion do people in UK buy medicines from these online pharmacies, if why do they buy from online source?

I don't agree with online pharmacy, or any medical product to be purchased online as it may be risky. I think online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, it cannot survive, moreover a patient cannot talk face to face, however people do buy because of convenience. But online pharmacy potentially dangerous store base pharmacy Is better. Thus I think Convenience is the main reason people buy on line as when people are busy they don't want to go to the pharmacy and prefer to order from online pharmacy, however I feel buying from online pharmacy is potentially dangerous, also being anonymous is a big issue, people who suffer from sexually transmitted infections etc want to remain anonymous so can prefer to buy from online pharmacy.

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taking medicine from online pharmacy, but if there is any side effect they cannot contact online pharmacy, they will come to the local pharmacy, where they will have a face to face talk, so as per me I don't like the concept of online pharmacy.

Besides this in your opinion buying medicines from online pharmacy can be safe and what medicines are normally purchased from online sources (kindly comment)

It depends which online pharmacy the person is buying, if it is registered with MHRA then it is ok to buy otherwise it can harm Patient, as there will be no proper service, no proper information, the drug can be low standard or not within the therapeutic windows, so buying or non-prescription drug also from any online pharmacy is not a right decision as it can even lead to complications and eventually a patient's death.

You must be aware of online consultation or online , and how safe are they. In your opinion do consumers use them, if yes what can be the probable reasons for using them. Please give your opinion on it. It is great, it is convenience, if the doctor is registered, as it makes things easy and so don't have to wait for the doctor's appointment, where the doctor can consult the patient on the phone and based on the problem they can either be asked to go, again in the case if the doctor feels that the patient needs physical then they can be referred to the doctor. So in a way it will not take away anything from NHs but will add to NHS for those patients who do not need physical examination. Besides it is helpful for disabled people. So online consultancy is a good option will add to the NHS. Accuracy of and safety aspect has to be taken care of besides it should follow confidentiality. There are apps for online consultancy which are legal and registered with GMC and NHS however there might be other online doctors and consultancy which may not be registered so patients should take care to see that they approach the right doctors.

Do people buy medicine as suggested on social media or online?

Yes, people do buy non-prescription medicines as suggested on social media or on the internet or on any print media. But then they should not continuously use it if they don't feel any difference. I would suggest maximum 3 weeks beyond that if they are not feeling relieved they should consult a healthcare professional. Besides this I would say the drug companies, NHS or MHRA should provide guidelines such as please do not use this if you don't feel relieved within 3 weeks which will help the people understand. It is because of convenience,

Interview transcript

Interview Questions:

This section will focus on general questions related to social media/online marketing in healthcare /pharmaceutical industry and its impact on the and patient engagement

What is your opinion why healthcare industry came into social media/ digital media quite late in comparison to other industry?

The engagement of healthcare /pharmaceutical industry in the social media such as having a company's official page on Facebook or Twitter or having a website which gives information about the brands and drugs and diseases, adverse drug reaction, is this information beneficial for the consumers. Kindly give your opinion.

The thing it is quite incorrect to do this, if we talk about shopping such any cold drink company then u catering to general population, so they can do to direct selling, but in case healthcare advertising on the social media is not a, there doctors and nurses who are not stupid studying pharmacology for 5-7 years studying and then suggesting the patient what medicine is in the best interest for the patient. However in the pharmaceutical company giving information on s Social media about medicine can give information to the lay man, but as a lay man, then coming down to doctors and telling to doctors than they say some information about the medicine and telling the doctor to prescribe it.

So in a way it is a false advertising and half knowledge Is dangerous. Information on Social media can be good but it gives half information and can mislead the consumer/patient as half knowledge is dangerous. It's a there are certain times it is good, like for example in India a mass campaign where the pregnant ladies in first trimester where given information that the they should take an iron supplement and they were aske d to go and physician about , thus it create an awareness., so it depends on the case specific. If giving information is a business strategy than it wrong and negative whereas if it is towards prevention than it good.

Have you come across patient who says he read about the disease on the social media and he feels he is suffering from that disease?

Pretty much Most of the patients come, in general patients would read up and say he is suffering from this, at times say I am suffering from this or that or like in psychiatry a patient can say I hear voice or see something, in a way it is way of getting secondary gain from healthcare system but to fake is not easy, quality of symptom are not great,. And is easy to understand that the patients have genuinely some problem or they have just read up something and come, but in some case it is irritating, however in some patients are really worried about the carers are really worried about the patients and they ask they read things on the social media and how and Is concerned .. so it matters from from end they come around.

As per academic journals and academic papers it has been reported that people before going to GP or doctor or a pharmacist, do a lot of research online on what they might be suffering

from and what can be the probable medicine for it. Have you ever come across such patients? So, in your opinion does this really help the consumer.

The consumer being laymen, they do not have much technical knowledge on disease or medicine, so in your opinion will the information on disease or medicine available on the social media or any other website be helpful or will be misleading.

Although DTCA (direct to consumer advertising) by Pharmaceutical company is only legal in USA and New Zealand, but as it is on the internet people from across the globe has access to it. Here the companies advertise their prescription as well as OTC brands to the consumers. What opinion do you have regarding it.

Kindly give your opinion regarding this

The thing in healthcare industry is that first of all of what product is discussed if turns out to be medication point of view, than it is not important and at the end of day the Prescription what the doctor write is more important and of the doctor wants to write a specific product, but if it's come down to supplement than it if okay than u can get from amazon or any online pharmacy but if u go for medicine, than the entire threshold will be on the doctor. So adverting on rth DCA does not makes much difference.

According to a 2015 survey by researchers at New York University's Langone Medical Centre, fifty-eight percent of mobile phone users have downloaded at least one Mobile Health app (mHealth app), and 41% have downloaded more than five apps. In is your opinion are these apps helpful for the consumer.

.Depends on what type of app, if it is just a a fitfit , or proven to be beneficial, then yes it could help in some way or if it just like iPhone or a smart watch which monitors the hr, or just the movement ten it Is not helpful even if the 5% of the population is motivated by APP than it Is good. And help them and motivates them to be fit than it Is good, but again it depends from the person to person. I would but , I would call it Pseudoscience, there I sno evidence based but if motivates it fine. I will not buy it. For me motivating come from within. In a community level it I sheading towards creating a pop culture and making OCD culture, where it says you need to have app , even somewhere its becoming OCD, but if the community is becoming healthy that it is ok. So in way it depends on people to person and circumstance to circumstances.

It is already a well-known fact that there are lot of online pharmacy internet pharmacy, some are legal, and some are illegal, and even the people in UK have access to it. So in your opinion do people in UK buy medicines from these online pharmacies, if why do they buy from online source?

Besides this in your opinion buying medicines from online pharmacy can be safe and what medicines are normally purchased from online sources

Depends on the online pharmacy, in way it I convenient for example a person has a backache for his entire life, and every time if he goes to pharmacy it is tedious, so if he get from the online pharmacy then it will be convenient for him. On the other hand if it antibiotic than it should per given in a control as if a rampant antibiotics gives it can lead to resistance way or some controlled drug Then if he buys from. I am sure there will be a lot of regularity and ethical issues People want online pharmacy

You must be aware of online consultation or online prescription, and how safe are they. In your opinion do consumers use them, if yes what can be the probable reasons for using them. Please give your opinion on it.

The thing in healthcare industry is that first of all of what product is discussed if turns out to be medication point of view, than it is not important and at the end of day the Prescription what the doctor write is more important and of the doctor wants to write a specific product, but if it's come down to supplement than it if okay than u can get from amazon or any online pharmacy but if u go for medicine, than the entire threshold will be on the doctor. So adverting on the DCA does not makes much difference.